

Deliverable 1.3

Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions

AUTh
28/02/2023

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

Funded by
the European Union

PROJECT INFORMATION

PROGRAMME	Horizon Europe
TOPIC	HORIZON-CL6-2021-GOVERNANCE-01
TYPE OF ACTION	HORIZON-CSA
PROJECT NUMBER	101060504
START DAY	1 September 2022
DURATION	36 months

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

TITLE	D1.3 Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions
WORK PACKAGE	Work Package 1
TASK	Task 1.4
AUTHORS (Organisation)	Stefanos Nastis (AUTh), Efstratios Stylianidis (AUTh), Dimitrios Natos (AUTh), Anastasios Michailidis (AUTh), Asterios Theofilou (AUTh), Alexandros Skondras (AUTh), Ifigeneia Skalidi (AUTh), Aikaterini Bakousi (AUTh), Nikolaos Tokas (AUTh), Eleni Karachaliou (AUTh), Pinelopi Kaslama (WR), Ioanna Nydrioti (WR), Maria-Eleni Chalamaki (WR)
REVIEWERS	James Gaffey (MTU), Alejandra Campos (S2I), Christos Politis (QPL), Margarita Angelidou (QPL), Sergi Costa (BPRO), Mar Cátedra Cerón (CAP), Samir Sayadi Gmada (IFA), Marta Macías Aragonés (CTA), Carmen Ronchel Barreno (CTA), Katarina Janurova (PDL)
DATE	28/2/2023

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

PU	Public, fully open	x
SEN	Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

DOCUMENT HISTORY

Version	Date	Changes	Responsible partner
0.1	07/11/2022	Titles Structure to COO	AUTh
1	31/1/2023	First draft to partners for review	AUTh
1.1	14/2/2023	Draft to partners for quality review	AUTh
1.2	24/2/2023	Final version to COO	AUTh
2	28/02/2023	Final version submitted to the European Commission	QPL

LEGAL NOTICE

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

© ROBIN Consortium, 2023

Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1.	EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	10
2.	INTRODUCTION.....	11
3.	IDENTIFICATION OF BARRIERS, OPPORTUNITIES, AND MOTIVATIONS FOR THE UPTAKE OF REGIONAL GOVERNANCE MODELS FOCUSING ON REGIONAL BIOECONOMY IN THE ROBIN REGIONS	12
3.1	Setting the scene of drivers and barriers in regional bioeconomy	12
3.1.1	The role of bioeconomy in regional schemes	12
3.1.2	Barriers to the uptake of Regional Governance Models.....	13
3.1.3	Opportunities and motivations for the uptake of Regional Governance Models.....	14
3.2	Insights from semi-structured interviews with regional actors	14
3.2.1	Methodology.....	15
3.2.1.1	Selection of the interviewing method and development of the interview guide..	15
3.2.1.2	Interviewees and interview process	15
3.2.1.3	Approach followed for the analysis.....	16
3.2.2	Regional profiles	16
3.2.2.1.	Southern Region of Ireland	16
3.2.2.2.	Žilina Region of Slovakia	29
3.2.2.3.	Region of Central Macedonia of Greece	40
3.2.2.4.	Andalusia Region of Spain.....	53
3.2.2.5.	Baden-Wuerttemberg Region of Germany	69
4.	ANALYSIS OF THE REGIONAL POLICY MIX IN THE ROBIN REGIONS	83
4.1	Methodology.....	84
4.2	Regional and local peculiarities	84
4.3	Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies	87
4.4	The Quadruple Helix actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system	93
4.5	The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs)	99
5.	CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY POLICY IN THE ROBIN REGIONS.....	106
6.	CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY GOVERNANCE PROFILES OF ROBIN REGIONS	124
6.1	Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Baden-Wuerttemberg case	124

6.1.1	Regional and local peculiarities	124
6.1.2	Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies.....	125
6.1.3	The Quadruple Helix actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system.....	127
6.1.4	The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs).....	129
6.1.5	Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT Analysis)	130
6.2	Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Central Macedonia case.....	131
6.2.1	Regional and local peculiarities	131
6.2.2	Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies.....	132
6.2.3	The QH actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system	134
6.2.4	The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs).....	135
6.2.5	Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT Analysis)	136
6.3	Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Southern region of Ireland case	137
6.3.1	Regional and local peculiarities	137
6.3.2	Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies.....	139
6.3.3	The QH actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system	144
6.3.4	The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs).....	149
6.3.5	Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy	157
6.4	Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Zilina region case	159
6.4.1	Regional and local peculiarities	159
6.4.2	Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies.....	160
6.4.3	The QH actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system	162
6.4.4	The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs).....	164
6.4.5	Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT Analysis)	166
6.5	Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Andalusia case.....	168
6.5.1	Regional and local peculiarities	168
6.5.2	Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies.....	171

6.5.3	The QH actors, operating principles, and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system	174
6.5.4	The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs).....	177
6.5.5	Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT Analysis)	183
7.	CONCLUSIONS	191
8.	BIBLIOGRAPHY	193
9.	APPENDIX	201
9.1	ANNEX A.....	201
9.2	ANNEX B.....	204
9.3	ANNEX C.....	207
9.3.1	Questionnaire	207
9.3.2	Informed consent form	208

TABLE OF FIGURES

Figure 1. Policy measures included in regional bioeconomy strategies. Source: Joint Research Centre, Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy	13
Figure 2: Regions of the ROBIN project	83

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1. General bioeconomy characteristics in the Southern Region of Ireland	18
Table 2. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland.....	22
Table 3. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Southern Region, Ireland	23
Table 4. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland	25
Table 5. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in the Southern Region of Ireland	27
Table 6. General bioeconomy characteristics in the Žilina Region of Slovakia.....	30
Table 7. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Žilina Region of Slovakia	34
Table 8. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Zilina Region, Slovakia	35
Table 9. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in the Žilina Region of Slovakia	37
Table 10. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in the Žilina Region of Slovakia.....	38
Table 11. General Bioeconomy Characteristics in the Region of Central Macedonia of Greece	41
Table 12. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia in Greece.....	45
Table 13. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Region of Central Macedonia, Greece	47
Table 14. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia in Greece	49
Table 15. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in the Region of Central Macedonia in Greece	51
Table 16. General Bioeconomy Characteristics in the Region of Andalusia in Spain.....	54
Table 17. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Andalusia in Spain.....	59
Table 18. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Andalusia Region, Spain	61
Table 19. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Andalusia in Spain.....	64
Table 20. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in the Region of Andalusia in Spain	66
Table 21. General Bioeconomy Characteristics in Baden-Wuerttemberg of Germany.....	70
Table 22. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Wuerttemberg of Germany	74
Table 23. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany	75
Table 24. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Wuerttemberg in Germany.....	78
Table 25. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in Baden-Wuerttemberg in Germany	79
Table 26: Regional Characteristics.....	84
Table 27: Regional bioeconomy value chains	85
Table 28: Regional bioeconomy sectors and products	85
Table 29: Regional bioeconomy strategies	86
Table 30: Effects of regional bioeconomy governance models to sectors	86

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

Table 31: SWOT analysis for the circular bioeconomy policy in Central Macedonia, Greece	107
Table 32: SWOT analysis for the circular bioeconomy policy in the Southern region, Ireland	108
Table 33: SWOT analysis for the circular bioeconomy policy in Zilina, Slovakia	109
Table 34: SWOT analysis for the circular bioeconomy policy in Andalusia, Spain	111
Table 35: Financial instruments for the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy	149

ABBREVIATIONS

EU	European Union
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
Mio	Million
N/A	Not available
RGM	Regional Governance Model
QH	Quadruple Helix
SWOT	Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats

1. Executive Summary

The aim of this deliverable is to analyze the circular bioeconomy policy mix in the five ROBIN regions within Germany, Greece, Ireland, Slovakia, and Spain, to profile the project areas. Specific aspects that are analyzed are: i) regional and local peculiarities, ii) the positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies, iii) the Quadruple Helix (QH) actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system, iv) the policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs) and v) challenges and opportunities for circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT analysis). The regions represent a diverse territorial array, reflecting the territorial or regional diversity of the EU, as well as a diversity of level of implementation of circular bioeconomy policies.

The deliverable is part of WP1, Setting the scene, and the analysis of the regional policy mix in the ROBIN regions provides valuable information for WP2, Co-creating the regional governance models and structures, and WP3, setting up and operating the regional governance models and structures. The analysis of the regional policy mix in the five ROBIN regions was conducted through the regional partners that are members of the ROBIN consortium, as well as with the assistance of the other consortium partners. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews with individuals involved in the design and implementation of each regional bioeconomy strategy were administered to representatives of the five ROBIN regions, that were involved in the design and implementation of each regional bioeconomy strategy.

The ROBIN regions represent a diverse representation of EU territories in terms of regional and local peculiarities, although there are commonalities in the bioeconomy sectors and products, and the bioeconomy value chains. There are differences in terms of the regions' implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy and in terms of the circular bioeconomy governance model.

In the ROBIN pilot regions, only Baden-Wuerttemberg has an already implemented bioeconomy strategy while the rest of the regions are on their way towards developing their regional bioeconomy strategy. It is interesting that all regions presented similar challenges related to the four different categories of barriers (institutional, implementation, financial, and other).

Barriers such as the lack of an official governmental framework to streamline the way to bioeconomy, and the lack of data and monitoring processes related to institutional challenges were present in all regions. Implementation barriers related to the lack of knowledge on what bioeconomy is and the lack of communication of the term bioeconomy and its benefits to the public were also present. The financial barriers were evident in every pilot region, with the lack of funding for bioeconomy initiatives standing as the main hindering factor to the uptake of a regional governance model focused on bioeconomy. In the Zilina region of Slovakia, the Andalusian region of Spain, and the Region of Central Macedonia of Greece, the bureaucratic burden was a discouraging factor to set up and further develop a regional bioeconomy strategy.

Overall, the findings from the literature review were confirmed in the regional profiles, in terms of barriers, benefits and opportunities for the uptake of regional bioeconomy governance models, however new aspects were also introduced such as the environmental benefits of bioeconomy applications (e.g., low footprint, climate change mitigation), human development (e.g., new jobs) and awareness raising (e.g., engagement of all stakeholder groups). Also, it is evident that there is a need of a streamlined framework to pave the way to regional bioeconomy governance models, and the term bioeconomy and its benefits need to be communicated effectively to wider audiences.

2. Introduction

The aim of this deliverable is to analyze the circular bioeconomy policy mix in the five ROBIN regions within Germany, Greece, Ireland, Slovakia, and Spain, to profile the project areas. Specific aspects that are analyzed are: i) regional and local peculiarities, ii) the positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies, iii) the Quadruple Helix (QH) actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system, iv) the policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs) and v) challenges and opportunities for circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT analysis). The regions represent a diverse territorial array, reflecting the territorial or regional diversity of the EU, as well as a diversity of level of implementation of circular bioeconomy policies.

The deliverable is part of WP1, Setting the scene, and the analysis of the regional policy mix in the ROBIN regions provides valuable information for WP2, Co-creating the regional governance models and structures, and WP3, setting up and operating the regional governance models and structures.

In the following Section 3, the Identification of barriers, opportunities and motivations for the uptake of Regional Governance Models focusing on regional bioeconomy in the ROBIN regions is presented, followed by the Analysis of the Regional Policy Mix in the ROBIN regions in Section 4, and the Challenges and Opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy in the ROBIN regions in Section 5. Section 6 presents the Circular bioeconomy governance profiles of ROBIN regions, followed by Conclusions in Section 6, Bibliography in Section 7 and Section 8 is the Appendix.

3. Identification of barriers, opportunities, and motivations for the uptake of Regional Governance Models focusing on regional bioeconomy in the ROBIN regions

3.1 Setting the scene of drivers and barriers in regional bioeconomy

Research activities started on September 2022 with a state-of-the-art review aiming at identifying the barriers, opportunities, and motivations for the uptake of Regional Governance Models in Europe with a focus on regional bioeconomy governance models. A state-of-the-art review was selected as the best method to collect recent literature sources and published material, in order to focus on current trends and patterns [1]. The research was focused on analysing the role of bioeconomy in regional schemes, identifying barriers to the uptake of Regional bioeconomy Governance Models (RGM) and spotting opportunities and motivations for RGM implementation.

3.1.1 *The role of bioeconomy in regional schemes*

The development of a sustainable, inclusive, and balanced bioeconomy requires a holistic approach with broad multi-stakeholder engagement and cross-sectoral collaboration [2]. The bioeconomy plays a prominent role throughout the process of achieving the EU target to become climate neutral by 2050. Bioeconomy is comprised of sectors and systems of agriculture, forestry, fisheries, food production, pulp, and paper production, as well as parts of the chemical, biotechnological, and energy industries that rely on biological resources (i.e., animals, plants, micro-organisms, and derived biomass, including organic waste) [3].

Besides different sectors and systems, bioeconomy includes many different policy domains too. As of November 2021, there were 359 bioeconomy-related strategies at the regional level in the EU-27 that involve stakeholders with different profiles and prospects [3]. According to the EU Bioeconomy Strategy Progress Report [4], bioeconomy policies should elaborate on all sustainability dimensions such as the management of land and biological resources within ecologic boundaries; sustainable value chains and consumption; and social fairness and just transition. In this regard, bioeconomy uptake depends strongly on the capacity of the relevant actors from different sectors to engage with each other to build sustainable bio-based value chains [2]. Clusters play a crucial role too in providing such collaboration opportunities through the integration of local producers of biological resources (e.g., farmers) as well as their associations (e.g., cooperatives) in regional bioeconomy governance models [5].

As indicated in Figure 1, the study of the Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy on the Bioeconomy strategy development in EU regions has identified policy measures that are included in regional bioeconomy strategies. Most of them are policy measures related to Research and Innovation (R&I) funding (in 173 strategies, or 22%) and governance funding (in 171 strategies, or 21%). There are also identified policy measures targeting collaboration (in 101 strategies, or 13%) including the facilitation of bottom-up initiatives or measures to enable multi-stakeholder involvement and dialogue. Lastly, other important policy measures are capacity-building measures that aim at raising awareness and providing information on bioeconomy (in 68 strategies, or 8%), infrastructure measures, i.e. the promotion of bioeconomy-specific research centres (or units), pilot and demonstration facilities (in 60 strategies, or 8%), training measures (in 58 strategies, or 7%), support

measures for stimulating demand that include new legal provisions, public procurement as well as labels, certification, or standards (in 54 strategies, or 7%) [3].

Despite the upward trajectory of the uptake of bioeconomy strategies at regional level, many barriers and challenges concerning their initiation and implementation persist. The next sections provide a concise account of these barriers.

Figure 1. Policy measures included in regional bioeconomy strategies. Source: Joint Research Centre, Knowledge Centre for Bioeconomy

3.1.2 Barriers to the uptake of Regional Governance Models

Regional governance can be defined as the rules, procedures, and practices used by institutions at a regional level. It is crucial for bioeconomy uptake in regional schemes to adapt to the notion of governance that includes the process of how societies adapt their rules to new challenges and how they develop new regional networks of multi-stakeholder and cross-sectoral collaboration as well as relevant supporting instruments that facilitate knowledge sharing across European regions [2].

Different challenges at different levels have been identified concerning the set-up of an effective governance framework for a sustainable bioeconomy. At the institutional level, challenges include the inefficiency of governments to monitor the strategies and the lack of impact assessment practices [6]. In the same vein, challenges such as enabling governance (political support measures) and constraining governance (regulatory tools) have been identified. Thus, one important barrier to the uptake of Regional Governance Models (RGM) is the potential negative consequences of bio-based transformations for sustainable development. Most states have mostly invested in promoting political measures to support the uptake of bioeconomy strategies and not to the management of conflicting goals such as the abovementioned potential negative consequences [6].

From the implementation perspective, challenges include the little experience of regional authorities in the implementation of regional bioeconomy models and the absence of an effective coordinated governance framework [6]. Additionally, on the economic front, challenges include a lack of financial resources/capital to implement bioeconomy strategies, and the price competitiveness with traditional/linear product offers [7].

At the regional level, there are no best practices identified and that leads to a plethora of local practices of bioeconomy that are numerous and diverse. The information or overviews on stakeholder and citizen engagement are not readily available and the information that can be found (by desk research) is not specific [8]. This results in inconsistencies in regional bioeconomy

practices. However, Salvador et al. (2022) [7]. give some proposals on how to advance regional circular bioeconomy systems such as setting strategies to overcome the lack of financial resources/capital, developing and/or making adequate technology available locally, and enabling price competitiveness with traditional (linear and non-renewable-based) options.

3.1.3 *Opportunities and motivations for the uptake of Regional Governance Models*

Besides the existing barriers to the uptake of RGM, Regional bioeconomy policies can be beneficial too. There is enough biomass feedstock and residuals that could be used and converted into real commodities. In the same aspect, there are plenty of business opportunities and information in the sector of bioeconomy as well as a high potential for research and innovation development [9].

More specifically, there are also plenty opportunities for policy development in bioeconomy strategies. From an institutional perspective, bioeconomy policy development could support existing policy frameworks at the national and EU level as well as raising awareness in society [9]. Furthermore, motivations include the establishment of public policies with governmental support as well as waste management potential [7]. The establishment of RGM with a focus on bioeconomy could also offer policy changes by establishing synergies with other policy trends and collaboration across sectors and networks. Lastly, taking advantage of existing EU or national funding mechanisms could help to boost innovation and development in the bioeconomy sector and mobilise new funding opportunities.

As analysed above, there are different barriers and motivations regarding the uptake of RGM in Europe. The study on Mapping of EU Member States'/regions' Research and Innovation plans & Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3) on Bioeconomy for 2014-2020 has provided some recommendations for better deployment of bioeconomy strategies. These include bioeconomy strategic planning and governance, the engagement of small and medium enterprises (SMEs), the knowledge transfer of Research and Innovation on new bioeconomy skills, the coordinated funding and synergies between instruments, and awareness raising on the bioeconomy strategy development (2017). Also, the interaction and empowerment of all bioeconomy actors (e.g., business, academia, primary biomass producers, civil society) is crucial to overcome their limited engagement in implementing bioeconomy policy at the regional level and enhancing their participation in collaborative governance schemes for bioeconomy.

3.2 **Insights from semi-structured interviews with regional actors**

The next step was the performance of 4 semi-structured interviews in each ROBIN region i.e., the Southern Region in Ireland, Zilina Region in Slovakia, Region of Central Macedonia in Greece, Andalusia Region in Spain, Baden-Wuerttemberg Region in Germany (20 interviews in total). The interviews were performed with key stakeholders, members of the multi-actor region constellations (MARC) that have been set up in each region, to complement the information found in international literature and aggregate them to regional need and opportunities.

The objective was to capture individual experiences, perceptions and attitudes regarding the bioeconomy status, the challenges in the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy and the reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in each region within the five different regional settings. Consequently, the core research question of the interviews was the following: where does the region

stand on the way to bioeconomy, and what are the key barriers to and drivers of a regional bioeconomy strategy and an effective governance framework at regional level?

Since the national literature offered limited information, the interviews functioned as the optimal complementary technique to fill in missing information and reveal specificities about the regional ecosystems that are unknown.

3.2.1 Methodology

3.2.1.1 Selection of the interviewing method and development of the interview guide

The findings from the literature review were calibrated into a single interview guide. Interviews were performed in the form of semi-structured, face-to-face, or online interviews. This approach offered flexibility to the interviewer to adapt the sequence of questionnaire items according to the flow of the interviewing process, and to follow-up with probes. A set of questionnaire items were developed based on the literature findings, but these items were not treated as fixed items that the interviewer should adhere to, but rather as baseline points for the discussion with the interviewee. Given that the aim of the interviews was not to validate or reject pre-existing theoretical constructs but rather to produce new insights from the interviewee's viewpoint, a semi-structured interview guide was the most appropriate tool [10].

Process-wise, White Research (WR) developed the interview guide and distributed it to all consortium partners to provide their comments. Once WR had incorporated the partners' feedback, the interview guide was finalised, and the interviews started. The interview guide consisted of an introductory note and four core parts:

- ❖ **Introduction:** The interviewee was informed about the ROBIN project, the concept, and the overall purpose of the interview.
- ❖ **Opening (warm-up):** The interviewee was asked some opening questions related to their background, familiarity, and previous experience with bioeconomy.
- ❖ **Main part (core questions):** The interviewee was asked about the bioeconomy practises and governance models already adopted in the region, the specific challenges in the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy and the reasons why the development of a sustainable bioeconomy requires an effective governance framework and how the region can benefit from it.
- ❖ **Closing (clean-up):** The interviewee was asked to follow-up with any additional information or thoughts they would like to provide (e.g., the type of experience needed for the further uptake of regional bioeconomy strategies).
- ❖ **Background information:** The interviewee was asked a series of background information, such as nationality and educational level.

The complete version of the interview guide can be found in Annex A of the Deliverable.

3.2.1.2 Interviewees and interview process

In total, 20 MARC members (i.e., stakeholders involved in the Multi-Actor Regional Constellations of the project) were interviewed – 4 members per region. The regional partners suggested the MARC members who were interviewed based on their experience in bioeconomy and the stakeholder category that they represent, respecting also gender mix. Then, the regional partner nominated each member and contacted him/her to arrange the date and time slot for the interview. Before the interview, all interviewees were provided with the formal privacy policy document of the project, while they also had to sign and send to WR a document whereby they were giving their consent to

participate in the interview, agreeing that their anonymised data could be used for the development of this document. The privacy policy and consent form documents are found in Annex B.

Interviews lasted approximately 30 to 40 minutes, including the opening, and closing sections. The interviews were performed in the local language or in English. The interviews were conducted by the regional partners and usually a team member of White Research joined the interview to support each project partner. Upon completion of the interviews, the interviewees were thanked for their participation and informed about the upcoming development of this document. After the interview, the regional partner completed the information collection template (one for each interviewee), provided by WR, with the core insights from the interview in English and send it to WR in a short time frame. All interviewees' personal data and notes were kept by WR and regional partners, in line with the overall data management plan of the project.

3.2.1.3 Approach followed for the analysis

Once all individual reports were collected and stored in a single database by WR, a qualitative data analysis was performed to transform the raw data and original phrases into meaningful results. To that end, a thematic analysis was selected as the method for the analysis. This type of analysis can be defined as “a method for identifying, analysing and reporting patterns (themes) within data. It minimally organises and describes your data set in (rich) detail”. Through the thematic analysis, the original data were broken down, re-formulated and re-appeared in the form of organised themes, through which the original data can be understood in new, meaningful lenses [10]. The main advantage of thematic analysis was the flexibility of the method. In the case of the 20 semi-structured interviews, the notes were categorised into organising themes as indicated from the questions of the interviews and aggregated further into basic themes identified from the literature review. The organising themes were grouped under global themes, that are the most high-level theoretical categories. In this case, global themes already existed either as barriers and obstacles or as drivers and opportunities. This posed a certain limitation regarding the generation of theoretical insights; however, the flexibility that the framework allowed in the inductive formulation of basic and organising themes did not compromise the qualitative nature of the data analysis.

To present all findings in a coherent way, a traditional thematic framework was deployed. The latter can be defined as “a matrix base method for ordering and synthesising data”. To support and substantiate the codes and themes of the matrix, quoted material was retrieved from the notes[10]. The matrix offered the possibility to simultaneously examine the themes within each regional context, but also under a cross-regional, comparative approach, by looking how two or more regions either share or do not the same themes. This, in turn, helps the reader to identify similarities and differences across national realities [10]. Interestingly, the analysis revealed that in some regions additional themes were identified based on the answers of the interviews that were not indicated in the literature. Also, only in some regions that already have a bioeconomy strategy, actors involved in the strategy could be identified.

3.2.2 Regional profiles

In this section, we present the findings from the semi-structured interviews. The analysis was carried out at the regional level and the insights from the interviews were analysed by considering the different backgrounds of the MARC members.

3.2.2.1. Southern Region of Ireland

I. Overview of the bioeconomy status in the Southern Region of Ireland

The Multi-Actor Regional Constellation (MARC) in the Southern Regional Assembly consists of 11 members. ROBIN partners in Ireland interviewed 4 MARC members: 1 Local Authority female

stakeholder, 2 Business Community/Civil Society stakeholders, 1 male and 1 female respectively, and one male MARC member who represented Academia.

The status of the bioeconomy in the Southern Region of Ireland is in its infancy. Even though there is no official regional bioeconomy strategy in place yet, there is an increased presence of multiple bioeconomy practices in the region. The interviewees talked about the potential of a bioeconomy strategy and the action areas that should be focused on.

Securing funding, a better connection of bioeconomy with the industry sector, clear communication with local communities, information sharing on the bioeconomy's potential, and empowerment of local action related to bioeconomy practices are some of the action areas that were mentioned during the interviews. As mentioned by one interviewee, there is a need for a streamlined governmental framework to support the bioeconomy actions in the region:

“..We need policies that will act like a support scheme and drive community engagement.”

In the region, there are several ongoing EU-funded bioeconomy projects, such as the BioWill project that has a strong focus on utilising willow trees for extraction of value-add materials with by-products being utilized in anaerobic digestion (AD) for biomethane production, the Biorefinery Glas project, the AgriChemWhey project, the BioBeo project and a local project named Creative Climate Action which explores creative ways of how the local community could reduce its carbon footprint. There are also other regional initiatives such as the Sustainable Energy Community, specific energy plans, and the West Kerry Dairy Farmers Sustainable Energy Community that push the bioeconomy in the region upwards. Table 1 provides further insights into the bioeconomy practices mentioned.

The interviewees also mentioned multiple categories of stakeholders who are already and could be involved in bioeconomy practices in the region. Local authorities, industries, local communities, academia actors, AD biomethane developers, farmers, producers involved in agriculture, distributors, and retailers, consumers, waste producers, end-users, manufacturers, fishermen, hospitality/ tourism industry, youth groups, women who are looking to work on the sustainability field and minority groups could play a key role when it comes to developing the regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland.

Table 1. General bioeconomy characteristics in the Southern Region of Ireland

Global theme	General Bioeconomy characteristics of the region				
Organising themes	Status of bioeconomy in the region		Specific governance model with bioeconomy focus / bioeconomy strategy in place (if any)		
Basic themes	Level of implementation of the model/strategy	Specific action plan	Bioeconomy practices in the region	Stakeholders involved	Main action areas of the bioeconomy model
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	Infant stage.	Not yet.	BioWill project (the project focuses on utilizing Willow trees to extract an anti-inflammatory cream and utilising the by-product in anaerobic digestion (AD) biomethane production. The fibre material is used as a recycling material for packaging and when that packaging comes back into the recycling system it can be digested in an AD plant.	<p>The answers refer to the BioWill project:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Local Authorities 2. Industries 3. Local communities 4. Other state agencies 5. Academia 6. AD Biomethane developers 7. Farmers across all disciplines 	<p>The answers refer to what is needed for the uptake of a bioeconomy model:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Identifying early where the key opportunities are within bioeconomy 2. Industry collocating 3. To be seen as a biorefinery 4. Securing government funding 5. Develop integrated business cases ensuring 6. Support industry and communities 7. Communicating with local communities about what is a biorefinery

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Local Government)</p>	<p>Lower steps of the ladder in terms of achievements.</p>	<p>Not yet</p> <p>The MARC member made reference to the Irish Bioeconomy Foundation National Bioeconomy Campus in Lisheen, Tipperary in the Region and explained that it could be used to push a regional strategy.</p>	<p>The answer refers to the work of the Southern Waste Region since there is not a regional bioeconomy strategy in place.</p> <p>Projects related to the commercial sector and to Local Authorities on how to educate to consume and procure better and how to generate less waste</p> <p><i>“There are a number of policies around circular strategies and a lot of them would have a role in the bioeconomy, in particular, there are strategies surrounding municipal waste and commercial waste and there is one completely dedicated to food waste. Within the plan, there are sixteen focus areas, and three of those sixteen are focused on the bioeconomy and biomaterials.”</i></p>	<p>The answer refers to the work on waste management:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Producers involved in agriculture or other bio-based materials 2. Distributors and retailers 3. Consumers 4. Waste Producers 5. End users 6. The manufacturers 	<p>The answers refer to the work of the Southern Waste Region:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Collaborating with Environmental Protection Agency food waste programmes 2. Informing businesses and households about best practices when it comes to food waste 3. Driving behavioural improvements 4. Putting on a National Food Waste Recycling Week held in June 5. Implementing a separate commercial food waste campaign 6. Enforcing by-laws for food waste bins in the household and non-household sector
--	--	---	--	--	--

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 3 (F, Business Community / Civil Society)</p>	<p>A lot of activity are being generated from the Bioeconomy Cluster Southwest - they are connecting a lot of bio-based companies and promoting anaerobic digestion (AD).</p>	<p>There is no specific bioeconomy policy in the south of Ireland and more specifically in the southwest. <i>“We need policies that will act like a support scheme and drive community engagement.”</i></p>	<p>There are no specific bioeconomy practices in place but there are several initiatives such as:</p> <p>Sustainable Energy Community (A project that is fostering a sustainable energy community through events, projects, and developing knowledge across a wide range of stakeholder groups).</p> <p>An energy master plan that surveyed existing use that will directly feed into the development of anaerobic digestion on the peninsula.</p> <p>West Kerry Dairy Farmers Sustainable Energy Community (SEC) (a community that explores how the agriculture sector on the Dingle Peninsula can reduce its carbon footprint).</p> <p>‘Creative Climate Action’ (project with a local artist who is working with ten farming families to explore creative ways on how the community can reduce its carbon footprint).</p>	<p>The answers refer to the stakeholders involved in the bioeconomy initiatives in the region:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Fishermen – marine primary stakeholders 2. Farmers – agriculture primary stakeholders 3. Community Groups 4. Hospitality / Tourism Industry 5. Food / Short supply chain community groups 6. Youth groups – are great in the area & engaged! 7. Women who are looking to come back into the workplace are looking for bioeconomy / sustainability jobs as an option. 8. Minority groups are becoming very interested also. 	<p>Referring to the projects that have worked on:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Shorter supply chains – too much is coming into and going out of the peninsula. 2. Develop emerging businesses in a practical sustainable manner 3. Develop local processing 4. Demonstrations that work! 5. Restaurants – ‘Local Plate’ was used to show what can be brought to the market at a local level.
<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)</p>	<p>Not at a regional level but the MARC member highlighted the 2018 national Bioeconomy Strategy which operates at a national level.</p>	<p>Not yet.</p>	<p>Bioeconomy practices in place are related to academic research activities (e.g., Projects that are related to bioeconomy such as Biorefinery Glas, ROBIN, AgriChemWhey, BioBeo).</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Answers refer to the existed bioeconomy projects:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Southern Region has the most potential in the country due to the abundance of natural resources. 2. Farming / Agriculture 3. Marine / Blue Economy 4. More support for existing research activity 5. Greater connectivity between research institutions 6. Greater connectivity between bioeconomy sectors 7. Education in understanding the Bioeconomy

II. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland

The interviewees mentioned multiple barriers and obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy related to different aspects, which are summarised as follows:

Institutional challenges

In line with the literature, there are several institutional challenges to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy such as the inefficiency of governments to monitor the strategies, the lack of impact assessment practices, the lack of political support measures, complicated regulatory tools, and the inefficient management of conflicting goals between traditional and bio-based products.

One interviewee mentioned that personal interests and conflicting goals have been a burden to the uptake of an official regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland. Specifically, he mentioned:

“[..] There were cases that a personal opinion of a person in a local authority has blocked a project.”

Another institutional challenge that was mentioned was the further need for the government to map and understand the demand for bioeconomy per region.

Implementation challenges

The lack of human resources available for the development of a regional strategy and the difficulty in efficiently engaging all stakeholders that should be involved were often mentioned. In the same vein, the interviewees reported difficulties to engage with local authorities that work as a burden to the further uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland.

Financial challenges

On the financial front, the interviewees mentioned the existence of financial challenges such as the lack of financial resources and the inexistence of a specific market focus when it comes to bioeconomy practices that would upgrade the region. Indeed, Overbeek et al. (2016) have already highlighted the lack of official best practices that would streamline the way to a successful bioeconomy strategy.

Other challenges

Another barrier to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the region is the lack of knowledge of stakeholders on what bioeconomy is, a challenge that was mentioned also by interviewees from other regions. The lack of communication of what bioeconomy is and the difficulty to communicate it to a wide range of stakeholders was further highlighted by almost all interviewees, which makes it an important element to take into consideration. The intersectionality of the bioeconomy and the absence of specific best practices make it more difficult to uptake a regional bioeconomy strategy with a specific focus.

Interviewees in the Southern Region of Ireland also mentioned that specific stakeholder groups such as local authorities, farmers, primary biomass producers, and the manufacturing, commercial, and marine sector stakeholders need further elaboration on their engagement because of diverse aspects. Table 2 provides further insights into the respective difficulties to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy.

Table 2. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles			
Organising themes	Challenges in the uptake of the regional bioeconomy strategy			
Basic themes (identified from the literature review)	Institutional challenges	Implementation challenges	Financial challenges	General barriers
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal interests/conflicting goals: <i>"a personal opinion of a person in local authority has blocked a project"</i>. Further need for the government to understand the demand for bioeconomy per region. 	Difficult engagement/collaboration with local authorities: <i>"engagement is difficult with local authorities – people in the Environmental Department are not available"</i> .	N/A	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Local Government)	N/A	Lack of human resources: <i>"[...] it can be a challenge for stakeholders to allocate the time for the establishment of a new strategy alongside their day-to-day jobs"</i> .	Lack of financial resources.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge of stakeholders on what bioeconomy is. Intersectionality of bioeconomy: <i>"..the uptake of a potential regional bioeconomy strategy is difficult because it is not related to one section either within government or local government and therefore communicating with a wider variety of stakeholders can be challenging."</i>
Interviewee 3 (F, Business Community/ Civil Society)	N/A	Hard to engage all stakeholder groups.	Not specific market focus: <i>"need to focus on what is abundant first in the region"</i> .	Intersectionality of bioeconomy.
Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)	N/A	Hard to engage all stakeholder groups.	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge of stakeholders on what bioeconomy is. Difficulty to communicate to a wide variety of stakeholders what bioeconomy is.

Table 3. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Southern Region, Ireland

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles	
Organising themes	Pillar/stakeholder group that needs further elaboration on the stakeholder's engagement	Aspects that make it difficult to set up a regional bioeconomy strategy
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	Local authorities: “[...] when planning applications related to the bioeconomy, the public should know that the local authority is fully behind it and fully understands the reasons why it is needed.”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficult to identify feedstock. • Profiling the bioeconomy in the Region: “<i>what the strengths and weaknesses are of the bioeconomy in the Region</i>”. • Securing food production: “<i>ensuring that the equilibrium of food production is not slowed down</i>”.
Interviewee 2 (F, Local Government)	Manufacturing and commercial sector: “[...] manufacturing and commercial sectors are the most difficult due to resource issues.” “[...] something that has worked in reaching these stakeholder groups and their representative organisations is very specialised publications.”	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hard to engage all stakeholder groups. • Difficulty to communicate to a wide variety of stakeholders what bioeconomy is: “<i>the size of the stakeholder group involved is one of the biggest barriers, getting that commitment from everyone might be difficult bringing the strategy into the language that is currently being used by the stakeholder sectors and how it fits in with current policy and social enterprise needs really helps with advancing a potential strategy.</i>”
Interviewee 3 (F, Business Community/ Civil Society)	The Marine sector.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty to communicate to a wide variety of stakeholders what bioeconomy is. • Difficulty to communicate what needs to be done next at a regional level: “<i>communication with local stakeholders to understand what is happening and more importantly what needs to happen at a local level to drive solutions that are specific to the region</i>”.
Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Primary biomass producers. • Farmers. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication with all stakeholders about the advantages of bioeconomy. • Ability to show in practical terms the advantages of bioeconomy practices: “<i>education and communication of what the bioeconomy is and the advantages to them and to be able to show to the stakeholders the practical advantages of bioeconomy-based practices</i>”.

III. Opportunities and motivations for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland

As shown in Table 4 and Table 5, the interviewees mentioned diverse reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in place. Some of them mentioned that a bioeconomy strategy in place could be a sign to show leadership and could spread information and engage further people who live in rural areas. It could also work as an incentive for industry collocation and could mark the start of the initiation of entering bioproducts in the market. Waste management and the right utilisation of waste products, the efficient use of resources, and the promotion of business development were also mentioned as important reasons and opportunities to initiate the uptake of a regional strategy with a focus on bioeconomy.

Utilising available feedstock, promotion of business development, research and innovation development, policy development related to bioeconomy, empowerment of existing policy frameworks, awareness raising/information sharing, and environmental benefits are some of the benefits that were identified in the literature review. The insights from the interviews could confirm the following categories of benefits:

- i. **Utilisation of feedstock** which includes the minimisation of waste and the uptake of natural capital in the region.
- ii. **Promotion of business development** which includes the creation of new jobs, new opportunities for rural employment, the development of sustainable rural economies, and the economic empowerment of rural areas.
- iii. **Research and Innovation development** which includes the creation of new skills.
- iv. **Awareness raising/information sharing** which includes clear knowledge of what bioeconomy is, communication to all the potential of bioeconomy and its benefits, and the engagement of all stakeholder groups.
- v. **Environmental benefits** which include the reduction of the overall carbon impact and the creation of an environmentally safer future.

Table 4. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern Region of Ireland

Global Theme	Drivers and Opportunities						
Organising themes	Benefits of a regional bioeconomy strategy in place						
Basic Themes	Utilising available feedstock (A sufficient amount of biomass feedstock and residuals that could be used and converted into real commodities)	Promotion of business development (Business opportunities in the bioeconomy sectors)	Research and Innovation Development (High potential for research and innovation development)	Policy development related to bioeconomy (Opportunities for policy development in bioeconomy strategies)	Empowerment of existing policy frameworks (Bioeconomy policy could support existing policy frameworks)	Awareness raising/ Information sharing (Bioeconomy policy could raise awareness in society on bioeconomy practices)	Environmental
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New jobs. New opportunities for rural employment. Development of Sustainable Rural Economies. 	New skills.	N/A	N/A	Clear knowledge of what bioeconomy is.	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Local government)	<p>Minimisation of waste: "significant food producers in the region, [...] a strategy in place would help [...] minimise waste".</p> <p>Promotion of natural capital in the region: "significant food producers in the region, [...] a strategy in place would help promote the natural capital of the Region".</p>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Reduction of overall carbon impact/footprint.

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 3 (F, Business Community/Civil Society)</p>	<p>Utilising all resources/wealth of resources.</p>	<p>Economic empowerment of rural areas: <i>"[...] financially secure and grow the economy in a rural area of the southwest that has struggled to grow outside of the tourism sector in the recent past".</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>A governance framework empowers existing work related to bioeconomy.</p>	<p>Communicating to all the potential of bioeconomy: <i>"show all locals and all groups of stakeholders what is possible".</i></p>	<p>Environmental safer future.</p>
<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communicate the premises and benefits of bioeconomy. • Engagement of all stakeholder groups. 	<p>N/A</p>

Table 5. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in the Southern Region of Ireland

Global theme	Drivers and Opportunities						
Organising themes	Reasons for the existence of an effective governance framework throughout the development of a sustainable bioeconomy						
Basic themes	Reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in the region	Establishment of public policies with governmental support	Waste management potential	Policy changes by establishing synergies	Collaboration with other sectors and networks	Utilising EU or national funding	Boost of innovation and development
<p>Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Shows leadership. Information to the rural communities on what is happening with the bioeconomy in the region: <i>"[...] a clear pathway for the local communities to understand what is happening with the bioeconomy in their Region".</i> Engaging rural communities: <i>"any potential bioeconomy strategy must fundamentally have the rural communities and farmers central to its development because getting their buy-in and doing it at scale will ensure the bioeconomy reaches its full potential regionally".</i> Industry collocating – entering bioproducts in the market: <i>"[...] source of a route to market for the bioproducts".</i> 	<p>Long term plan needs proper governance: <i>"[...] ensure the ESG's and climate act goals are met and deliver their key milestones by improving the environment".</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Create fertile environments to support industries for the transition to bioproducts: <i>"Experience should be drawn from the CircBio and BiOrBic to bring bioeconomy research to implementation".</i></p>

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Local Government)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mapping the bioeconomy in the region could lead to reaching its full potential: <i>"if we do not have a strategy we do not know if some producers might be able to use the bioproduct of another producer, therefore the bioeconomy of the Region is not reaching its full potential."</i> Sufficient waste management. 	<p>A proper governance framework facilitates engagement with stakeholders: <i>"[...] you need working grids to work on each of the different areas and if that is not established at the start it is very hard to reach targets and goals".</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Better organisation of stakeholders <i>"[...] it is also very hard to organise engagement with stakeholders and different sectors".</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Interviewee 3 (F, Business Community/ Civil Society)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilisation of waste products / efficient use of resources: <i>"[...] drive circularity, basically on the dingle peninsula we need to start using our waste products".</i> Promotion of business development. 	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Sets the stage for deploying the bioeconomy potential: <i>"a strategy in place would set the stage for deploying the potential of bioeconomy in the region".</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Enable EU and national funding mechanisms: <i>"Enable and inform people on EU funding mechanisms [...] approach stakeholder groups that are hard to reach such as the marine sector".</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Empowerment of existing experience and work. Drives Local capacity building.
<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Financial benefits. Environmental/sustainability benefits. 	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Research projects with right structure and framework to operate with.</p>	<p>Better communication and demonstration of existing projects that have worked and work on bioeconomy: <i>"a framework is needed for projects to not operate in silos".</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>

3.2.2.2. *Žilina Region of Slovakia*

I. Overview of the bioeconomy status in Žilina

The Multi-Actor Regional Constellation (MARC) in the Žilina region consists of 8 members. ROBIN partners in Slovakia interviewed 4 MARC members: 3 male members (2 of whom are part of the Local Government while 1 who falls under the category of Business Community), and 1 female member of the Business Community.

The status of the bioeconomy in the region is not advanced. Even though there is not a bioeconomy strategy in place yet, there is an agricultural tradition in almost all Slovak regions. The Economic and Social Development Programme is a strategic document that has some aspects related to the bioeconomy. So far, there are some bioeconomy practices in the region that could be summarised in financial support and internationalisation practices both provided by the Slovak Bioeconomy Cluster, awareness raising on sustainable topics, and at a higher level the application of EU regulations such as the ban of single-use plastic products.

The stakeholders involved in the development of the future regional bioeconomy strategy and the national bioeconomy strategy are businesses, academic actors, experts, citizens, representatives of other regional authorities, state forests of the Slovak Republic, private forest owners, innovation centres, and local action groups.

Table 6. General bioeconomy characteristics in the Žilina Region of Slovakia

Global theme	General Bioeconomy characteristics of the region				
Organising themes	Status of bioeconomy in the region		Specific governance model with bioeconomy focus / bioeconomy strategy in place (if any)		
Basic themes	Level of implementation of the model/strategy	Specific action plan	Bioeconomy practices in the region	Stakeholders involved	Main action areas of the bioeconomy model
Interviewee 1 (M, Local Government)	<p>Work in progress.</p> <p>Tradition with agriculture.</p> <p>Small farms and cooperatives are emerging.</p> <p>Wood processing industry, paper, pulp mill, and printing.</p> <p>Treatment of waste.</p> <p>New biogas plant to be developed.</p>	<p>Not a strategy in place yet.</p> <p>There is the Economic and Social Development Programme (Programme), a strategic document with some aspects related to bioeconomy, the new Programme is being prepared.</p>	<p>At the city level; the provision of small grants.</p>	<p>The answer refers to the development of the new Programme:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Businesses. 2. Academia. 3. Experts. 4. Citizens. 5. Representatives of other municipalities, etc. 	N/A

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Business Community/ Civil Society)</p>	<p>The answer refers to the bioeconomy status of different Slovak regions:</p> <p>Nitra region – work in progress.</p> <p>Agricultural tradition.</p> <p>Geographic conditions.</p> <p>Fertile soil.</p> <p>Research Infrastructure (University of Agriculture, National Agricultural and Food Centre).</p> <p>Exhibition Centre Agrokomplex.</p> <p>Banská Bystrica region – Focus on social innovation related to bioeconomy (agriculture) and involvement of disadvantaged groups.</p> <p>The western regions - more activities - it's also about access to infrastructure - research centers - helps a lot if businesses have access (SMEs don't have facilities to do research activities).</p>	<p>Not a strategy in the Zilina region yet.</p> <p>The national strategy is being developed.</p>	<p>The answer refers to general bioeconomy practices in Slovakia:</p> <p>Financial support.</p> <p>Internationalisation support.</p> <p>(both provided by the Slovak Bioeconomy cluster)</p> <p>Regulations – e.g., at the EU level the ban on single-use plastics.</p> <p>Awareness raising on sustainable topics.</p> <p>Financial resources – some green SMEs are already on the market:</p> <p><i>“The young generation is aware of the importance of sustainable approaches.”</i></p>	<p>The answer refers to the national strategy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Businesses. 2. Clusters. 3. Academia. 	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)</p>	<p>The MARC member did not give information about the bioeconomy in the region:</p> <p><i>“...Development of circulation bioeconomy has meaning for the whole society, while special meanings follow especially for rural communities. From the point of view of the development of the rural economy, it is also about the support of innovations, the creation of new business models and the development of value chains.”</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>The answer refers to the future regional bioeconomy strategy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Žilina Self-Governing Region. 2. State forests of the Slovak Republic. 3. Private forest owners. 	<p>N/A</p>

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Local Government)</p>	<p>Not a strategy is in place yet but a regional strategy is being prepared: <i>“In accordance with the Social and economic development plan 2021+, the Žilina Region plans to implement the principles of bioeconomy and prepare to achieve the goals of the European Union.”</i></p>	<p>The answer refers to the future regional strategy that is being prepared. The Žilina region plans to move ahead with: Implementation of bioeconomy principles in the region. Involvement of the region in innovative projects in the field of bioeconomy. Incorporation of bioeconomy principles into regional public procurement. Support for building a network of product reuse centers in the region.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>The answer refers to the future regional bioeconomy strategy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Žilina Self-Governing Region. 2. Innovation Centre INOVIA. 3. University of Žilina. 4. Local action groups in the Žilina region. 5. Bioclimatic park Drieňová. 	<p>N/A</p>
--	--	--	------------	--	------------

II. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Žilina Region of Slovakia

The interviewees mentioned diverse barriers related to institutional, implementation, and financial challenges as well as general barriers that are like the barriers mentioned by the interviewees from other regions.

Table 7 presents the insights from the interviews regarding Barriers and Obstacles.

Institutional Challenges

The institutional challenges in this region include the bureaucratic burden and the absence of an effective governance framework and the regional bioeconomy strategy that could act as a roadmap to the way to bioeconomy.

Implementation Challenges

Implementation challenges in this region include ownership relations which hinder the development of regional bioeconomy strategies and the difficulty to engage all stakeholder groups as well as the inefficient use of biomass.

Financial Challenges

Part of the financial challenges to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy is the lack of financial resources, the reduced funding, and the high prices of bioproducts in comparison with the traditional ones.

Other Challenges

The lack of interest of stakeholders in bioeconomy and the lack of knowledge of what bioeconomy is and its benefits as well as the lack of trust in new bioeconomy initiatives have been thoroughly mentioned by the interviewees in the Zilina region of Slovakia.

When it comes to the harder-to-engage stakeholder group, the interviewees mentioned different stakeholders such as the farmers and foresters who do not have guidelines on how to proceed with bioeconomy practices. They also mentioned the difficulty to engage trade unions and associations that have strength and connections with the government, an element that works as a burden to the uptake of an official bioeconomy strategy.

Table 7. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Žilina Region of Slovakia

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles			
Organising themes	Challenges in the uptake of the regional bioeconomy strategy			
Basic themes <i>(identified from the literature review)</i>	Institutional challenges	Implementation challenges	Financial challenges	General barriers
Interviewee 1 (M, Local Government)	Bureaucracy.	Ownership relations: <i>"In the case of some measures, the ownership of land or properties is hindering the planning and/or implementation".</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of financial resources. 	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Business Community/ Civil Society)	Bureaucracy: <i>"The development of Strategic documents in Slovakia takes too much time, action plans are not created or narrowed."</i>	Difficulty to engage all stakeholder groups.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High prices of bioproducts. Reduced funding. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of interest of stakeholders: <i>"It is not a "profit theme" – even companies still have to invest".</i> Lack of knowledge of stakeholders on what bioeconomy is. Lack of trust for new/bioeconomy initiatives: <i>"If the strategy is not supported by the government, the importance of the document is questionable".</i>
Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In existed governance framework. Absence of a regional strategy for the bioeconomy. 	Inefficient use of biomass.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> High prices of bioproducts: <i>"[...] lower added value of the wood industry, or comparatively high export of raw wood and lumber without higher added value values."</i> 	N/A
Interviewee 4 (M, Local Government)	Absence of a regional strategy for the bioeconomy.	N/A	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of knowledge on the benefits of bioeconomy: <i>"[...] low level of information and public awareness on the advantages of biological products compared to fossil products."</i> Lack of knowledge of stakeholders on what bioeconomy is: <i>"[...] bioeconomy is a hardly comprehensible terminology for the public."</i>

Table 8. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Zilina Region, Slovakia

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles	
Organising themes	Pillar/stakeholder group that needs further elaboration on the stakeholder's engagement	Aspects that make it difficult to set up a regional bioeconomy strategy
Interviewee 1 (M, Local Government)	Different stakeholder groups: <i>"Interest is lost among different groups if strategies and action plans are not implemented and remain only on paper."</i>	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Business Community/ Civil Society)	Trade Unions. Associations: <i>"Big and strong unions and associations have the strength and connections with the government but needs to be a clear link with their interests (e.g., investments, funding)."</i>	N/A
Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Farmers. • Foresters. 	Non-existent advisory system for farmers and biomass producers.
Interviewee 4 (M, Local Government)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inconsistency and fragmentation of policies relevant to the area of bioeconomy. • Ambiguity of its position and role in development policies. • Inconsistency of methodologies for policy making in the area of bioeconomy. • Lack and unavailability of data for creating a strategy for bioeconomy and its subsequent monitoring and evaluation.

III. Opportunities and motivations for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Žilina Region of Slovakia

Since there is no bioeconomy strategy in place, the interviewees talked about the potential benefits of the future regional bioeconomy strategy. Table 9 provides further insights into the opportunities and motivations for the uptake of a regional strategy with a focus on bioeconomy.

The following categories include the insights of the interviewees:

- i. **Utilising available feedstock** which includes further support for the bioeconomy and the management of small forests, the sustainable use of natural resources, and biomass and the production of renewable energy.
- ii. **Promotion of business development** that could come through enhanced social entrepreneurship linked to Agriculture, the development of rural employment, and the increase in employment shares.
- iii. **Research and Innovation Development** that includes the development and use of biotechnologies and innovative technologies.
- iv. **Policy development related to bioeconomy** includes official strategies to foster the adoption of concrete actions.
- v. **Awareness raising/information sharing** that includes the communication of the potential and the benefits of bioeconomy and the strengthening advice in the field of bioeconomy.
- vi. **Environmental benefits** which include solving environmental issues and giving the motivation to deal with impacts of climate change, the production of renewable energy, the development of a low carbon economy.

As a general note, the interviewees mentioned multiple reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy and the development of an effective bioeconomy governance framework in the region focusing mainly on the agricultural potential and the utilisation of the available biomass in the region. Table 9 and Table 10 could provide further insights into that. It is important to highlight that one interviewee mentioned thoroughly the aspect of human development through bioeconomy practices, including the activation of the local and rural population and the involvement of citizens in the decision-making process.

Table 9. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in the Žilina Region of Slovakia

Global Theme	Drivers and Opportunities						
Organising themes	Benefits of the bioeconomy strategy in place						
Basic Themes	Utilising available feedstock (A sufficient amount of biomass feedstock and residuals that could be used and converted into real commodities)	Promotion of business development (Business opportunities in the bioeconomy sectors)	Research and Innovation Development (High potential for research and innovation development)	Policy development related to bioeconomy (Opportunities for policy development in bioeconomy strategies)	Empowerment of existing policy frameworks (Bioeconomy policy could support existing policy frameworks)	Awareness raising/ Information sharing (Bioeconomy policy could raise awareness in society on bioeconomy practices)	Environmental
Interviewee 1 (M, Local Government)	N/A	N/A	N/A	Official strategies foster the adoption of concrete actions - officials have a mandate and arguments to prepare the necessary actions, it also serves as a basis for financial allocation.	N/A	N/A	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Business Community/ Civil Society)	N/A	Enhances social entrepreneurship in agriculture.	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Solving environmental issues. Gives the motivation to deal with the impacts of climate change.
Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support for the management of small forests. Support for bioeconomy, Sustainable and efficient use of natural resources and biomass, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of rural employment Increasing employment 	N/A	N/A	N/A	Communicating to all the potential of bioeconomy: "show all locals and all groups of stakeholders what is possible".	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Production of renewable energy. Mitigating climate change. Development of a low-carbon economy. Environmental safer future.
Interviewee 4 (M, Local Government)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Efficient use of resources. Production of renewable energy. 	N/A	Development and use of biotechnologies and innovative technologies,	N/A	N/A	Strengthening advice in the field of bioeconomy.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mitigating climate change. Developing a low-carbon economy.

Table 10. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in the Žilina Region of Slovakia

Global theme	Drivers and Opportunities							
Organising themes	Reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in the region	Reasons for the existence of an effective governance framework throughout the development of a sustainable bioeconomy						
Basic themes		Establishment of public policies with governmental support	Waste management potential	Policy changes by establishing synergies	Collaboration with other sectors and networks	Utilising EU or national funding	Boost of innovation and development	Human Development (new)
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Local Government)	Better environment for people.	To have the vision and structure with responsibilities, competencies, and resources.	N/A	N/A	Knowledge transfer.	N/A	N/A	N/A
Interviewee 3 (F, Business Community/ Civil Society)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support of education. • Support consulting on the use of modern technology. • Development of cross-border cooperation. 	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support the development of innovative circular bioeconomy. • Replacing fossil fuels. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More active role of the rural population. • Activation of the local population. • Involvement of citizens in the decision-making process.

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Production potential of the region. • Concentrated agricultural production. • Inclusion of forests in the bioeconomy. 	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with international workplaces and competence centers. • Support the development of clusters and associations in the bioeconomy. 	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>
--	---	------------	------------	------------	--	------------	------------	------------

3.2.2.3. Region of Central Macedonia of Greece

I. Overview of the bioeconomy status in the Region of Central Macedonia of Greece

The MARC in the Region of Central Macedonia consists of 8 members: 4 out of them were interviewed, 3 of whom were females and fall under the categories of local government and business community respectively while 1 male member represents both business community and academia.

The situation of bioeconomy in the region of Central Macedonia is at a medium level of maturity. The region does not have a bioeconomy strategy in place yet but there are 3 Action Plans that are being prepared for the promotion of the circular economy and in particular the bioeconomy. The main action areas for the future regional bioeconomy strategy in the region are bio-waste, food residues, packaging materials, recovery of secondary materials from bio-waste, energy utilisation of biomass. Also, some practices that are followed by the Greek Bioeconomy Forum to promote the bioeconomy are awareness raising through events and exhibitions, the promotion of collaborations by bringing stakeholders together, exhibitions of bio-based products and training on financing/ funding opportunities.

The region is quite active in terms of EU-funded projects and is a regional partner in different projects related to the bioeconomy. Table 11 presents multiple insights into that and the stakeholders involved in the implemented bioeconomy practices. In the region, there are multiple key players such as the Regional Authority of the Region of Central Macedonia, the Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia, the Special Managing Authority of Operational Programme in Central Macedonia, the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, the Centre for Research & Technology Hellas, the Regional Association of Solid Waste Management Agencies (FODSA) and the organisation of local development ANATOLIKI SA.

Table 11. General Bioeconomy Characteristics in the Region of Central Macedonia of Greece

Global theme	General Bioeconomy characteristics of the region				
Organising themes	Status of bioeconomy in the region		Specific governance model with bioeconomy focus / bioeconomy strategy in place (if any)		
Basic themes	Level of implementation of the model/strategy	Specific action plan	Bioeconomy practices in the region	Stakeholders involved	Main action areas of the bioeconomy model
Interviewee 1 (F, Regional Authority)	<p>Not a strategy in place.</p> <p>3 Action Plans prepared for the promotion of the circular economy and in particular the bioeconomy, in the framework of EU-funded projects:</p> <p>RCM participates as</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o a fellow in the initiative CCRI – Circular cities and regions initiative. o a member of the ERIAFF - European Regions for Innovation in Agriculture, Food and Forestry. o a member of the BIC – bio-economy platform. 	<p>No applied bioeconomy strategy, apart from the above 3 Action Plans, which focused on the Regional Operational Programme of Central Macedonia, as the main policy tool with a specific budget.</p>	<p>3 EU funded projects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – BIOREGIO – CESME – SinCE-AFC 	<p>The answers refer to stakeholders involved in actions related to bioeconomy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RCM, One Stop Liaison Office. 2. Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia. 3. Special Managing Authority of Operational Programme in Central Macedonia. 4. Aristotle University of Thessaloniki. 5. Centre for Research & Technology Hellas. 6. Regional Association of Solid Waste Management Agencies (FODSA). 7. ANATOLIKI SA. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bio-waste. 2. Food residues. 3. Packaging materials. 4. Recovery of secondary materials from bio-waste. 5. Energy utilisation of biomass.

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Civil Society)</p>	<p>Not a strategy in place: “[...] There isn’t currently any strategy/ policy for the bioeconomy, neither at the national nor the regional level. In RCM, two action plans aim at the wider adoption of bioeconomy practices. The action plans were developed by two European projects.”</p> <p>“[...] The best possible utilisation of waste is burning them for energy. Unfortunately, there is no other option, such as an urban biorefinery for waste processing.”</p>	<p>Greek Bioeconomy Forum (GBF), as a governance model, was established in 2016. It is a think tank that aims to bring closer people that can join forces for the wider adoption of bioeconomy practices in Greece.</p> <p>Main roles:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ raise awareness about the bioeconomy. ○ bring together scientist, business actors, public sector. 	<p>GBF aims to advocate bioeconomy practices to stakeholders and citizens, being as inclusive as possible.</p> <p>Local citizens could understand the importance of bioeconomy and the various incentives available to adopt bioeconomy practices. Also, GBF provided citizens with useful information on what can be recycled because many people were confused about this issue. Also, informs stakeholders on the various financing and funding opportunities available in the bioeconomy sector.</p>	<p>The answers refer to stakeholders involved in actions related to bioeconomy:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Policy-makers from relevant bodies and public organisations. 2. The faculty of engineering at some Greek universities. 3. Business actors. 	<p>The answers refer to GBF’s bioeconomy model:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Awareness raising through events and exhibitions. 2. Promotion of collaborations by bringing stakeholders together. 3. Exhibitions of bio-based products. 4. Training on financing/ funding opportunities.
<p>Interviewee 3 (F, Regional Authority)</p>	<p>The introduction of the concept of Circular Economy in RCM started with the co-funded project CESME (Interreg Europe), while there are 2 other ongoing relevant projects: BIOREGIO and SINCE-AFC. “[...] The concepts of circular economy, bioeconomy, sustainable management, or even recycling, are still unclear to most of the stakeholders and sometimes tend to overlap.”</p> <p>Bioeconomy introduces also the aspect of saving natural resources and not only the repurposing of waste to raw material.</p>	<p>There is no regional policy on the circular economy or the bioeconomy. There are, though:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A national action plan. ○ A priority set in the new RIS by RCM ○ CE projects and the OSLO platform that supports businesses oriented to CE (HORIZON SCAN), which are considered benchmarks. ○ Innovation clusters that, even though, they are not decision-makers, bring some policy changes. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creativity platform: an initiative developed by the agrodesign cluster. • SKG MAKERS. • In Common an NGO initiative. <p>Project 1. Kyklos: Urban Sustainability & Circularity Lab.</p> <p>Project 2. Kafsimo.</p> <p>Project 3. FoodTreasure.</p>	<p>The answers refer to stakeholders involved in bioeconomy practices in the region:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. RCM, One Stop Liaison Office. 2. Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia. 3. Innovation Clusters. 4. University of Macedonia. 5. Centre for Research & Technology Hellas. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Bio-waste. 2. Food residues. 3. Packaging materials. 4. Recovery of secondary materials from bio-waste. 5. Energy utilisation of biomass.

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)</p>	<p>Relatively low rate of development <i>"[...]Efforts to support the further development of successful circular bioeconomy models are being made at the regional level"</i></p>	<p>Innovation clusters that, even though, they are not decision-makers, bring some policy changes.</p> <p>2 Action plans in the framework of two Interreg projects: BIOREGIO CESME</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Domaine Agrovision (a winery in Ierissos, Halkidiki, which applies circular economy principles to its production process and has developed an innovative practice to produce disinfectants through the reuse of by-products and waste produced during the wine and spirits production process in the era of Covid-19.) • The dairy industry Kri-Kri (uses leftovers from dairy products, in order to produce biogas that can be used for energy and heat.) 	<p>The answer refers to the stakeholders involved in a potential governance model:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Public Bodies (e.g., municipalities, regions, ministries) 2. Citizens 3. Academic and research institutions 4. Secondary sector (e.g., industries) 5. Tertiary sector (e.g., businesses) 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Health 2. Food-waste 3. Biogas 4. Energy 5. Forestry 6. Bio-waste 7. Biomass
--	--	--	---	--	---

II. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia in Greece

The interviewees mentioned that the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia in Greece hinders many challenges that are introduced in Table 12.

Institutional Challenges

There are institutional challenges such as the lack of a legal framework for secondary materials, the lack of coordinated actions, the lack of facilitation of legislation, the lack of flexible policies and heavy bureaucracy.

Implementation Challenges

Implementation challenges in this region include the lack of statistics which makes difficult the monitoring process and the minimal role of local citizens in the implementation of bioeconomy projects.

Financial Challenges

Financial challenges include the lack of funding.

Other Challenges

There are also other challenges identified by the interviewees such as the lack of green consumer consciousness, the lack of cooperation culture between businesses, and the lack of knowledge of what bioeconomy is.

As shown in Table 13, business community stakeholders and policymakers are the most difficult group to engage in the process of bioeconomy transition. Aspects that were mentioned by the interviewees and make it difficult to set up a regional bioeconomy strategy are the legislative jurisdiction that falls under the central government, the nature of the agrifood clusters that consist of small and scattered cooperatives and the inexistent connection or exchange information between Research and Business.

Table 12. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia in Greece

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles			
Organizing themes	Challenges in the uptake of the regional bioeconomy strategy			
Basic themes (identified from the literature review)	Institutional challenges	Implementation challenges	Financial challenges	General barriers
Interviewee 1 (F, Regional Authority)	Lack of legal framework for secondary materials.	Lack of statistics.	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of green consumer consciousness. • Lack of cooperation culture between businesses.
Interviewee 2 (F, Civil Society)	Lack of coordinated actions: “[...] The transition to a bioeconomy requires coordinated action and the long-term commitment of many stakeholders (i.e., advocates of the bioeconomy). However, people usually undertake projects with a short time horizon and a fragmented approach.”	Minimal role of local citizens in the implementation of bioeconomy projects.	N/A	Lack of knowledge of what bioeconomy is: “Citizens don’t realise the importance of the bioeconomy and the participation levels remain low”.
Interviewee 3 (F, Regional Authority)	N/A	N/A	Lack of funding: “[...] Clusters and initiatives need funding to continue their projects and expand their activities.” “[...] Final recipients/businesses need financial incentives to be able to support such synergies and shift to a bioeconomy model.”	N/A

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)</p>	<p>Lack of facilitation from legislation in Greece (which often hamper the development of good practices in the region)</p> <p>Lack of flexible policies</p> <p>Bureaucracy <i>"[.]There is also too much bureaucracy in what is required for licenses and services, thus being time consuming and not efficient for the fast-track implementation of new strategies and practices"</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Lack of knowledge on the benefits of bioeconomy</p>
--	---	------------	------------	--

Table 13. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Region of Central Macedonia, Greece

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles	
Organizing themes	Pillar/stakeholder group that needs further elaboration on the stakeholder's engagement	Aspects that make it difficult to set up a regional bioeconomy strategy
Interviewee 1 (F, Regional Authority)	N/A	The legislative jurisdiction does not fall into the ones of the Region of Central Macedonia but to the central government and the co-competent Ministries.
Interviewee 2 (F, Civil Society)	<p>Business community: <i>"[...] business people will feel incentivised only if they see an opportunity to improve the quality of the product or produce an existing product more cheaply or comply with some regulation."</i></p> <p>Policy Makers: <i>"[...] Policy-makers are often not aware of the benefits of the bioeconomy."</i></p> <p><i>"[...] there are cases of people who aimed to operate in the bioeconomy, but they didn't get permission from the state because the related agencies couldn't understand the purpose and proposed activities."</i></p>	N/A
Interviewee 3 (F, Regional Authority)	<p>Business community: <i>"[...] Businesses need financial incentives in order to adopt bioeconomy models."</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agrifood clusters consist of small and scattered cooperatives – there isn't an organised group that would minimise costs. • There is no connection or exchange of information between Research and Business.
Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)	Public bodies	Especially in practices regarding bio-waste management

III. Opportunities and motivations for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia

The benefits mentioned by the interviewees could fall under the identified categories:

- i. **Promotion of business development** that includes the creation of new jobs.
- ii. **Research and Innovation Development** which includes the identification of existing and specific demands, the participation in European projects and the establishment of alliances beyond Andalusia, and the collaboration in Research and Development projects.
- iii. **Policy development related to bioeconomy** includes the development of new policy frameworks and the establishment of funding schemes.
- iv. **Empowerment of existing policy frameworks** that include the development of infrastructures critical to deploying several bioeconomy initiatives.
- v. **Awareness-raising/information-sharing** practices that include the encouragement of many stakeholders to plan and operate in alignment with the principles of bioeconomy.

Table 14. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia in Greece

Global Theme	Drivers and Opportunities						
Organizing themes	Benefits of the bioeconomy strategy in place						
Basic Themes	Utilising available feedstock (A sufficient amount of biomass feedstock and residuals that could be used and converted into real commodities)	Promotion of business development (Business opportunities in the bioeconomy sectors)	Research and Innovation Development (High potential for research and innovation development)	Policy development related to bioeconomy (Opportunities for policy development in bioeconomy strategies)	Empowerment of existing policy frameworks (Bioeconomy policy could support existing policy frameworks)	Awareness-raising/ Information sharing (Bioeconomy policy could raise awareness in society on bioeconomy practices)	Human Development
Interviewee 1 (F, Regional Authority)	N/A	<i>"[...] Bioeconomy is a business opportunity for SMEs in the Region. With the mandatory introduction of the brown bin and separate sorting of household bio-waste, you open up a large chunk of new markets (services and products)."</i>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Civil Society)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	A bioeconomy strategy or policy would entail developing infrastructures critical to deploying several bioeconomy initiatives: <i>"[...] Any strategy or policy promoting the bioeconomy must apply to the national and not the regional level."</i>	Urge many stakeholders to plan and operate in alignment with the principles of bioeconomy.	N/A
Interviewee 3 (F, Regional Authority)	N/A	New jobs.	N/A	Establishment of regional policies that need to be clear.	N/A	N/A	N/A

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)	N/A	More business opportunities	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Improvement of social well-being
--------------------------------	-----	-----------------------------	-----	-----	-----	-----	----------------------------------

Table 15. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in the Region of Central Macedonia in Greece

Global theme		Drivers and Opportunities					
Organizing themes	Reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in the region	Reasons for the existence of an effective governance framework throughout the development of a sustainable bioeconomy					
Basic themes		Establishment of public policies with governmental support	Waste management potential	Policy changes by establishing synergies	Collaboration with other sectors and networks	Utilising EU or national funding	Boost of innovation and development
Interviewee 1 (F, Regional Authority)	The large potential of agri-food and tourism enterprises in RCM as well as academic/research institutions that can offer the know-how to SMEs and the development of innovative techniques.	N/A	N/A	N/A	Attract investment.	N/A	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Civil Society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operating in alignment with the principles of the bioeconomy will eventually become obligatory at an EU level. Help the local economy to grow faster. The more bio-based products produced, the more self-sufficient in energy and other goods the RCM will be. Local economy would be stronger and less dependent on factors that could wreck the region's prosperity. 	<p><i>"[...] The existence of an effective governance framework throughout developing a sustainable bioeconomy is very important, especially when governance models, involve the public sector so that any conclusion reached can be easier communicated and be heard by policy-makers."</i></p> <p>Any activities undertaken align with the national planning and strategies and are financially prudent</p>	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 3 (F, Regional Authority)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biomass feedstock and residuals that could be used and converted into real commodities. • Business opportunities in the bioeconomy sector and new jobs. 	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Support businesses by providing scientific and innovative assistance and communicating an effective governance framework through understandable language and procedures. “[...] For example, Strategies that lead to financial tools, give the opportunity to bioeconomy stakeholders to introduce new technologies and change existing models.”</p>
<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)</p>	<p>“[...] the growth of sustainability in the region will be vast. There will be a better potential for the use of alternative fuels such as biofuels, biogas, and biomass. This will lead to better energy sufficiency. Moreover, there is a potential for better garbage disposal condition, especially in the field of organic waste, food waste and more generally bio waste. Last but not least, with a bioeconomy strategy in the region, there will be better conditions for research and innovation development.”</p>	<p>Decentralisation of the current governance structures</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Better collaboration across sectors and networks</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Transformation of the current energy system</p>

3.2.2.4. Andalusia Region of Spain

I. Overview of the bioeconomy status in Andalusia in Spain

The MARC in Andalusia consists of 12 members and the interviews were performed with 4 members: 3 females (2 of them fall under the category of Business Community, 1 works in an academic institution and R&D and Innovation agency, and 1 male member who works at a private cooperative under the category of Business Community).

The bioeconomy situation in the region of Andalusia is advanced. The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) is in the process of development and actualization. The region is rich in terms of biomass resources in the agri-food sector. Even though the strategy has not been already implemented, there are diverse working groups for its formulation since 2016.

Table 16 provides more insights into the bioeconomy practices followed in the region. Among others, the olive agricultural, horticulture and orange sector biomass, use of algae and the establishment of biorefineries. The main action areas of the bioeconomy strategy are diverse sectors such as agriculture, utilisation of available feedstock, sustainable production, innovation and research in the process and management of biomass producers, infrastructure and logistic management, cooperation between stakeholders, etc.

During this bioeconomy transition process in the Andalusian region, the private, public, academic, and applied sectors as well as consumers and the public play a key role in its development.

Table 16. General Bioeconomy Characteristics in the Region of Andalusia in Spain

Global theme	General Bioeconomy characteristics of the region				
Organising themes	Status of bioeconomy in the region		Specific governance model with bioeconomy focus / bioeconomy strategy in place (if any)		
Basic themes	Level of implementation of the model/strategy	Actors involved in the implementation	Specific action plan	Bioeconomy practices in the region	Main action areas of the bioeconomy model
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community)	<p>Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) has developed.</p> <p>The Andalusian Regional Government has a powerful structure of entities to control the planned implementation actions of bioeconomy: diverse Regional Ministries, Andalusian Institute for Research and Training in Agriculture, Fishery, Food and Ecological Production (IFAPA) has 15 operational Research and Training centres throughout Andalusia, 47 Rural Development Groups and 69 Regional Agricultural Offices.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Private sector: Farmers, Cooperatives, Authorised Advisers, and Waste Managers. Public sector: Andalusian Government - Junta de Andalusia. Academic sector: Research Centers. Consumers. 	<p>Diverse working groups have been set up for the formulation of the ACBS since 2016.</p> <p>The strategy has not been already implemented.</p> <p>Within framework of the ACBS, the real availability of biomass resources from the agroindustry in Andalusia has been analysed and quantified.</p> <p>Entities such as this cooperative could be established as a governance model example to advance towards the biomass resources use of the agricultural sector in Andalusia.</p>	<p>Some specific bioeconomy practices developed in Andalusia are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Taking the olive grove and orange sector, the crushed agricultural biomass is incorporated into the soil. The industrial biomass of olive grove sector is used for energy production. It is a potential use of the byproducts and wastes. In the case of orange sector, the industrial biomass is used for livestock feed Using the horticultural sector, agricultural biomass is managed on farms by direct incorporation into the soil or by self-composting. Use of algae. Use of sludge from Urban Waste Water Treatment Plants (WWTPs). 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> Applied different sectors: agriculture, livestock, industry, urban (WWTPs and bio-waste), etc. Any sector capable of producing renewable biomass for compost production. Ensure the sustainable production and availability of biomass resources. Development of markets- based biomass resources and new bioeconomy business models. Infrastructure and logistic management. Innovation and research in the process and management of biomass resources. Implementation of a legal framework and funding access. Cooperation between stakeholders. Training in bioeconomy.

<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Academia)</p>	<p>Andalusia was one of the first European regions to plan a Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, involving different groups of experts and key stakeholders.</p> <p>The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) was prepared with the participation of different Regional Ministries, in addition to IFAPA as the Andalusian R&D and training Institute with 15 centres distributed throughout the region.</p> <p>The region has different types of biomass resources in the agri-food sector, making it one of the regions with more potential in Europe.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Private sector: mainly Agri-food sector. 2. Policy makers: Public Administration. 3. Researchers and scholars, and vocational training. 4. Society. 5. AKIS actors (Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems). 	<p>As a model of support for the ACBS, this campusCampus of International Excellence in Agrifood has its own strategy to boost actions including the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting the alignment of all the areas and actions of the members of the centre with regional, national and European bioeconomy policies and strategies. • Promoting and strengthening joint actions in R&D and knowledge transfer whose aims are aligned with sustainable agri-food production. • Reinforcing and promoting education and training, the professionalisation of the sector and the employability of graduates from ceiA3 Universities in the bioeconomy by meeting the sector demand. • Promoting research and innovation carried out at ceiA3 Universities and associated centres as well as disseminating and raising awareness in society. 	<p>Specific bioeconomy practices in Andalusia, within the framework of the actions proposed by the EABC and in which the campus is a promoter:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the Master's degree in Bioeconomy at the Universities of Cordoba and Almeria. • The Ceia3 Annual Magazine: C3Bioeconomym. • AgroMIS Project: digital transformation of the Andalusian agri-food sector linked to bioeconomy actions. • European BLOOM project: aimed at raising public awareness of bioeconomy issues. • SUBPGAN Operational Group: Improvement of the handling, valuation and marketing of livestock by-products through innovation, developed in the Pedroches Valley (Cordoba). • BIORRUMIOLI Operational Group: Bioeconomic products derived from small ruminants through the revaluation of olive oil by-products. • BIOSUERO Operational Group: revaluation of cheese whey for use as a biofertiliser/biostimulant. • Membership and promotion of actions within the framework of INNOVAGRO with bioeconomy as one of the common points. 	<p>Application to different sectors, mainly to the agri-food sector:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Aid programmes. 2. Participation in networks, platforms and working groups. 3. Participation in projects. 4. Joint actions as a Master's programme. 5. Dissemination actions.
---	---	--	--	--	---

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 3 (F, Industry)</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>The answer refers to the work of the company: Research Groups. Private Companies.</p>	<p>The company has no direct relationship with the Andalusian Regional Government:</p> <p><i>"[...]There are no mechanisms for interaction promoted by the regional council between companies and other stakeholders involved in the bioeconomy such as biomass producers, technological centers, research group, etc. Contact with research groups or other companies for cooperation projects is done by the company itself. Companies working on R&D projects are informed through different organizations such as CTA, Biovegen, or Andalusian Knowledge Agency."</i></p>	<p>From 2016-2018: Biorefineries.</p>	<p>N/A</p>
--	------------	--	---	---	------------

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 4 (F, Industry)</p>	<p>The company is very active in bioeconomy projects – they participated in the development of the Andalusian bioeconomy cluster.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Private companies. • Technological Centers. • Universities. • Andalusian Regional Government. 	<p>The Andalusian circular bioeconomy strategy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of biorefineries. • Biodigesters. • Developing alternatives to plastic (<i>there is an important evolution in packaging, the reuse of plastic film in greenhouses and the use of other materials.</i>) • Revaluation of fresh fruit in pre-prepared and pre-cooked. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Resources optimization in the fields (water, fertilisers) using sensor-based techniques. 2. Real time data control for decision making, which implies lower economic costs by optimising energy, water and input consumption, and lower environmental impact. 3. Photovoltaic energy in their facilities (they have renewed the existing PV panels). 4. They have also improved the system for preserving fresh produce in the conservation chambers. 5. As for the different products, the portfolio of pre-cooked food (5th range) is a product that economically and circularly closes the cycle. However, waste is also generated. In this moment they are looking at the possibilities of using by-products from the 5th range to obtain bio-based products to be used not only in food but in other sectors (pharmaceuticals, animal feed, cosmetics, etc.). This requires a lot of research and evaluation of the cost of investment and logistics. 6. Digital transformation.
---	---	--	---	--	---

II. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Andalusian region of Spain

The barriers and obstacles regarding the uptake of the regional bioeconomy strategy fall under the already identified categories. Specifically, Table 17 presents all barriers and obstacles per region.

Institutional Challenges

There are multiple institutional challenges such as the limited awareness of the application of regulations regarding bioeconomy, the lack of standard guaranteed processes and products, the lack of monitoring and evaluation processes, and the burden of bureaucracy.

Implementation Challenges

Implementation challenges in this region include the lack of training and information on sustainable practices and the lack of bioeconomy advisors, strategic alliances with strategic partners, inexistent streamlined approach to enhance the value of actions and avoid duplications, lack of collaboration between departments, and logistics challenges.

Financial Challenges

Financial challenges include reinforcing support and financing policies, and problems with securing funding.

Other Challenges

Part of other challenges in this region is the lack of communication about what bioeconomy is, an element that is common in all regions, and the lack of a validation process.

The interviewees in Andalusia mentioned that biomass producers, agents related to logistics and transportation, consumers, the public, and younger people are the stakeholder groups that are difficult to engage. Table 18 presents the aspects that make it difficult to set up a regional bioeconomy strategy in Andalusia.

Table 17. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Andalusia in Spain

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles			
Organizing themes	Challenges in the uptake of the regional bioeconomy strategy			
Basic themes (identified from the literature review)	Institutional challenges	Implementation challenges	Financial challenges	General barriers
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited awareness of the application of regulations and concern for sustainability, prevent the massive use of biomass as a resource. Lack of standard guaranteed processes and products. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need for "in situ" recovery in the own agricultural exploitation, saving space, time, optimisation, and management. Lack of training and information on sustainable practices. Lack of bioeconomy advisors: "[...] are a point of union between the public and private sectors, which would allow for a real implementation of the projects." 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reinforcing support and financing policies. Securing funding. 	Lack of fostering in communication concerning to the implementation of sustainable practices
Interviewee 2 (F, Academia)	Lack of monitoring and evaluation: "[...] Hold regular meetings with stakeholders to report on the implementation and progress of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy." "[...] Including effective monitoring with realistic indicators to assess the impact and outcomes of actions of the bioeconomy strategy."	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of strategic alliances with strategic partners. In existing streamlined approach to enhance the value of actions and avoid duplications. Lack of collaboration between departments: "[...] The Departments of Innovation and Agriculture must work together to make adequate progress in the bioeconomy." 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Securing funding: "[...] Make available both financial resources and other types of support." 	N/A
Interviewee 3 (F, Industry)	Bureaucracy: "[...] Certification of organic products involves a high-demanding bureaucratic process, sometimes due to lack of information, sometimes due to excessive paperwork or because the process is too long."	Logistics: "[...] Regarding biomass, the main barrier is logistics, mobilising large volumes of forest residues, liquids, etc. New biomasses, such as insects, are also difficult to use due to the lack of proper information."	N/A	Lack of validation process: "[...] At the level of research projects, a lot of work is being done, but the validation of final products is a limiting factor in the region."

Interviewee 4 (F, Industry)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Bureaucracy.• Legislation needs to be updated.	N/A	N/A	Poor monitoring of bioeconomy progress.
--------------------------------	---	-----	-----	---

Table 18. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Andalusia Region, Spain

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles	
Organizing themes	Pillar/stakeholder group that needs further elaboration on the stakeholder's engagement	Aspects that make it difficult to set up a regional bioeconomy strategy
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	<p>Biomass producers: <i>"[...] since they are responsible for its management and do not want to directly assume the cost of implementing new models. They are the ones that guarantee continuous supply, to ensure the success of any project."</i></p> <p>Agents related to logistics and transportation: <i>"[...] Agents related to logistics are a necessary pillar for the development the biomass resources. They assume a shared responsibility together with producers. It must exist a guarantee of supplies by them."</i></p> <p>Consumers.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic aspect: <i>"[...] as there is no official retribution system to promote and remunerate these implementations, as well as the refusal to assume a new cost for adopting more sustainable solutions by producers."</i> • Lack of accompanying measures to alleviate the management cost. • No mechanisms to revalue bioeconomy processes and products. • Low boosting in human resources and machinery. • There is no established label to mark good practices. • Every stakeholder needs to be aware of the advantages and disadvantages of this model. • Missing link between the whole bioeconomy chain and stakeholders. • Guaranteeing the traceability of the products, processes, and waste.
Interviewee 2 (F, Academia)	<p>General Public: <i>"[...] The most difficult group to engage is the public because they are the ones who will bear the cost as consumers (higher price). They are the ones who should demand the products. They represent most of the population, and their demand and awareness of this business model is a factor in boosting and promoting the bioeconomy in the region."</i></p> <p>Young people in secondary schools: <i>"[...] Attention should be paid to young people in secondary schools (mainly those aged 14-16) to raise their awareness. Actions should be implemented for students with programme for teachers. It should be possible to implement 5-hour education programmes in all schools to involve students from an early age."</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It should go hand in hand with specific actions to achieve the objectives set. • It should not be limited to agriculture alone. All sectors should be represented. • It should involve the public and private sectors. • It should increase the awareness of society (demand) so that the actions are more visible and crystallised in the corresponding offers.
Interviewee 3 (F, Industry)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The regional ministry does not inform enough the stakeholders involved about aspects such as improving the strategy.

Interviewee 4
(F, Industry)

- Regional government.
- Research Centres.
- Companies.

- Bureaucracy.
- Andalusia has a circular bioeconomy strategy, but it has not been implemented: “[..] *The administration should work with companies and universities on measures to move from theory to practice, there is no teamwork.*”

III. Opportunities and motivations for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Andalusia in Spain

The interviewees know the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, and they have highlighted that Andalusia was one of the first European regions in having its own circular bioeconomy strategy and it's a pathway of a wide range of bioeconomy opportunities. The insights from the interviews could be found in 19 and validate the basic themes identified by the literature review, summarised as follows:

- i. **Utilising available feedstock** which includes the reassurance of the economic, technical, and environmental sustainability of biomass resources and better management and exploitation of all biological resources.
- ii. **Promotion of business development** that includes new production and trade models, collaboration with different actors, and networking.
- iii. **Research and Innovation Development** which includes the identification of existing and specific demands, the participation in European projects and the establishment of alliances beyond Andalusia, and the collaboration in Research and Development projects.
- iv. **Policy development** related to bioeconomy includes the development of new policy frameworks and the establishment of funding schemes.
- v. **Empowerment of existing policy frameworks** that include the establishment of operational groups and priorities for the region and support identifying successful examples of the bioeconomy and applying them in different regions.
- vi. **Awareness raising/information sharing** that includes the development of awareness-raising programmes and the contribution to increasing the general awareness of all stakeholders in the bioeconomy (sector, administration, society, and academia).

Besides the benefits mentioned by the interviewees, the reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in the region include the promotion of cooperation and collaboration between key stakeholders, the creation of dedicated clusters to support the key stakeholders, the clarification of a regulatory and legal framework to take advantage of European, national and regional funding mechanism, the creation of good habits and practices of production based on circular bioeconomy, the establishments of some standards to obtain high-quality certified products, the promotion of mechanisms to optimise productions costs, the development of new business models and the provision of human resources and emerging new professions. Table 20 provides some insights into the reasons for the existence of an effective governance framework related to the bioeconomy progress in Andalusia.

Table 19. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Andalusia in Spain

Global Theme	Drivers and Opportunities						
Organising themes	Benefits of a future bioeconomy strategy in place						
Basic Themes	Utilising available feedstock <small>(A sufficient amount of biomass feedstock and residuals that could be used and converted into real commodities)</small>	Promotion of business development <small>(Business opportunities in the bioeconomy sectors)</small>	Research and Innovation Development <small>(High potential for research and innovation development)</small>	Policy development related to bioeconomy <small>(Opportunities for policy development in bioeconomy strategies)</small>	Empowerment of existing policy frameworks <small>(Bioeconomy policy could support existing policy frameworks)</small>	Awareness- raising/ Information sharing <small>(Bioeconomy policy could raise awareness in society on bioeconomy practices)</small>	Environmental
Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Ensuring the economic, technical and environmental sustainability of biomass resources. Better management and exploitation of all biological resources and waste. 	New production and trade models.	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Development of new policy frameworks to support the biomass processes and bioproducts. Establishment of funding schemes to guarantee the new products and processes. 	N/A	Development of awareness-raising programmes.	N/A

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Academia)</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Different key actors from different sectors interact with each other. • Long-lasting links have been established between researchers, academia, Universities, the Administration and the agri-food sector. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identification of existing and specific demands. <i>"[...] As a result of the ACBS, academia has developed specific training initiatives, such as the Masters in Bioeconomy at the University of Cordoba and the University of Almeria."</i> • Participation in European projects and establishment of alliances beyond Andalusia. 	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of operational groups and priorities for the region. • Supporting to identify successful examples of the bioeconomy and applying them in different regions. 	<p>Contribution and increasing the general awareness of all stakeholders in the bioeconomy (sector, administration, society, and academia).</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Interviewee 3 (F, Industry)</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Collaboration in R&D projects.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Interviewee 4 (F, Industry)</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Private sector more aware and responsible for their actions.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>

Table 20. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in the Region of Andalusia in Spain

Global theme	Drivers and Opportunities						
Organizing themes	Reasons for the existence of an effective governance framework throughout the development of a sustainable bioeconomy						
Basic themes	Reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in the region	Establishment of public policies with governmental support	Waste management potential	Policy changes by establishing synergies	Collaboration with other sectors and networks	Utilising EU or national funding	Boost of innovation and development
<p>Interviewee 1 (M, Business Community/ Civil Society)</p>	<p>Promotion of cooperation and collaboration between key stakeholders.</p> <p>Creating clusters to support the key stakeholders and establishing public-private cooperation.</p> <p>Clarifying the regulatory and legal framework, and taking advantage of European, national and regional funding mechanisms.</p> <p>Creating good habits and practices of production, market and consumption based on circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Establishing some standards to obtain high-quality certified products.</p> <p>Promoting mechanisms to optimise production costs.</p> <p>Providing human resources and emerging professions.</p> <p>Development of new business models to provide new windfall revenues under the carbon market.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Independence in the use of fossil resources. • Guaranteed certifiable level of quality. • Raw material supply and sustainability. 	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involving all key stakeholders and sectors in the bioeconomy. • Consistent performance for all actors involved in the bioeconomy value chain. 	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creating new business opportunities. • Continuing research and innovation in bioeconomy practices. • New value-added products. • New emerging professions.

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Academia)</p>	<p>Andalusia is a region with a high biomass production, especially in the agri-food and forestry sectors, which represents a great potential for developing the bioeconomy and an associated strategy.</p> <p>Opportunity to increase added value to productions and meet needs: <i>"[...] for example, in terms of animal feeding, and therefore create new economic activities and opportunities for local employment and market."</i></p> <p>Development of guidelines for waste management.</p> <p>Support and encourage R&D and training activities.</p>	<p>Establishing a government strategy that involves all ministries (multi-ministerial), even if led by the Regional Ministry of Agriculture.</p> <p>Involving AKIS, because they can generate a multiplier effect and foster links between all key stakeholders. They can translate the message and facilitate dissemination. To this end, networks of AKIS associated with the EABC should be created.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Facilitating monitoring of bioeconomy actions and outcomes. Avoiding duplication, and exploiting synergies between stakeholders, pooling efforts and common interests to strengthen actions. 	<p>Promoting expert focus groups.</p>	<p>Facilitating economic resources for the development of the bioeconomy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identifying success examples and making them known among stakeholders, not only at a regional level, but also outside Andalusia. Promoting the multiplier effect by making use of existing initiatives.
<p>Interviewee 3 (F, Industry)</p>	<p><i>"[...] Having a strategy is positive, there is room for improvement, but having guidelines is always positive."</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Collaboration with different stakeholders: <i>"[...] Working groups are a good way to collaborate, they allow you to be in contact with other stakeholders and to get a full picture of the issues. Participation in collaborative workshops should be encouraged in order to get the views of stakeholders."</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 4 (M, Academia)</p>	<p><i>"[...] It is positive, you have to analyse each region in terms of population, resources, local problems, how the entities in that region can adapt, etc. Having a bioeconomy strategy is necessary to put stakeholders in place, it guides you to be more optimal on a day-to-day basis."</i></p> <p><i>"It has to be done in a planned way and with concrete actions."</i></p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Liaising with other stakeholders so the planning stage can be design involving all actors' perspectives and expectations.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>
---	--	------------	------------	------------	--	------------	------------

3.2.2.5. Baden-Wuerttemberg Region of Germany

I. Overview of the bioeconomy status in Baden-Wuerttemberg in Germany

The Multi-Actor Regional Constellation (MARC) in the Baden-Wuerttemberg (BW) region consists of 8 members. ROBIN partners in BW interviewed 4 MARC members: 3 of them are females; 1 working in the Parliament, and 2 of them in academia. The fourth interviewee is male and represents the Business Community.

The bioeconomy in the region is at quite an advanced level. There is a specific action plan and a regional bioeconomy strategy in place. According to the interviewees, there are 27 concrete measures for the next four years (2021-2024). The main action areas of the bioeconomy model are the dimension of rural bioeconomy, urban and industrial bioeconomy, and wastewater and exhaust air.

The interviewees mentioned the funding for Research and Development projects and for start-ups as a core element of the regional bioeconomy strategy. The region focuses on sustainable practices, the development of bioproducts (e.g., bioplastics and biofuels), and the use of biomass in energy production. Table 21 introduces further details on the bioeconomy status in the region of Baden-Wuerttemberg.

On the way to establishing the bioeconomy in the region, there are multiple stakeholders involved such as the state's government, academic and research institutions, companies in the chemical and automotive sectors, farmers, foresters, NGOs, associations, innovative SMEs, agile start-ups, ministries with experienced funding agencies, venture capitalists, green banks, media representatives.

Table 21. General Bioeconomy Characteristics in Baden-Wuerttemberg of Germany

Global theme	General Bioeconomy characteristics of the region				
Organising themes	Status of bioeconomy in the region		Specific governance model with bioeconomy focus / bioeconomy strategy in place (if any)		
Basic themes	Level of implementation of the model/strategy	Specific action plan	Bioeconomy practices in the region	Stakeholders involved	Main action areas of the bioeconomy model
Interviewee 1 (F, Academia)	<i>The relevant questions were not used in the interview due to the level of expertise of the interviewee and the maturity level of bioeconomy in BW</i>				
Interviewee 2 (F, Government)	N/A	Yes. State Strategy for a Sustainable Bioeconomy	<p>37 concrete measures in 4 years (2021-2024):</p> <p><i>"[...]The parliament approved more than 50 Mio euros for the implementation of the measures. Most of the funds were (in my former ministry, Ministry of the Environment, Climate Protection and the Energy Sector) obligated in 2021 which really made it a race against time to design the support programmes (partly ERDF), to publish the funding calls, to process the applications, bring about jury decisions and grant the money to the projects."</i></p> <p><i>"At the same time, there was a website to develop Bioökonomie Baden-Wuerttemberg - Home (baden-wuerttemberg.de), and further demanding tasks to fulfil, like to establish a bioeconomy advisory council with 17 experts from the whole of Germany and prepare and document the meetings."</i></p>	N/A	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Rural bioeconomy (concerning biomass especially from agriculture). 2. Urban and industrial bioeconomy [concerning the recovery of raw materials from waste (bio-waste, metals, etc.)] 3. Wastewater and exhaust air [(mainly Carbon Capture and Usage CCU Bio) with biological, bio-inspired or biotechnological methods].]

<p>Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community)</p>	<p>Advanced</p>	<p>Yes:</p> <p><i>"[...]Baden-Wuerttemberg is a state that has made a strong commitment to developing its bioeconomy. The state government has set ambitious goals for increasing the share of bio-based products and promoting the use of renewable resources in industry. We've seen a lot of investment in R&D, funding for start-ups, and the creation of a supportive framework for the bioeconomy in BW."</i></p> <p><i>"Additionally, many companies in the state, particularly in the chemical and automotive sectors, are investing in the development of bio-based products and processes. Overall, we believe that BW is a leading region in the development of the bioeconomy in Germany, and we're excited to be a part of this growing industry."</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of bio-based products (e.g., bioplastics and biofuels). • Renewable resources (e.g., use of biomass in energy production): <p><i>"[...] We focus on producing high-quality and nutritious hemp-based food products that are suitable for a wide range of consumers. We also contribute to circular economy by reusing the by-products of our production process, which reduce waste and improve the sustainability of our operations."</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State government. • Academic and research institutions. • Companies in the chemical and automotive sectors. • Farmers and foresters. • NGOs. • Associations. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Setting goals. 2. Creation of supporting framework. 3. Funding for R&D and start-ups.
--	-----------------	---	---	---	--

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 4 (F, Business Community)</p>	<p>Advanced: “[...] Baden-Wuerttemberg (BW) holds a quite advanced position on the road to a fully functional bioeconomy where sustainability, resource efficiency and circular economy are key elements.”</p>	<p>Yes.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Holistic approach. • Sustainable practices: “[...] Guiding principles are based on the Baden-Wuerttemberg research strategy “Bioökonomie im System aufstellen” 2013 and “Landesstrategie Nachhaltige Bioökonomie” 2019.” 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Universities. • Research institutes of applied research (e.g., Fraunhofer). • Innovative SMEs. • Agile start-ups. • Ministries with experienced funding agencies. • Venture capitalists. • Green banks. • NGOs. • Media representatives. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analytical work (analysis of key actors in urban bioeconomy). • Setting up new and feasible economic models as evaluation tools for enterprises.
--	--	-------------	--	--	---

II. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in the Baden-Wuerttemberg Region in Germany

Baden-Wuerttemberg pilot region has an established regional bioeconomy strategy. Even though the strategy has already been active for some years, the interviewees mentioned multiple challenges, summarised as follows.

Table 2222 and Table 233 present the insights from the interviews regarding Barriers and Obstacles in the implementation of the regional bioeconomy strategy and could be grouped as follows.

Institutional Challenges

The institutional challenges mentioned include the lack of a clear regulatory framework and the lack of regulations with a holistic approach.

Implementation Challenges

Implementation challenges in this region include insufficient human resources and the heavy workload that might be necessary for the smooth implementation of the regional bioeconomy strategy, the lack of infrastructure and logistics support for bio-based products, and the lack of standardisation.

Financial Challenges

The only financial challenge mentioned by the interviewees in the BW region is the lack of funding. However it should be noted that there are funding programmes to finance bioeconomy projects in BW, probably the interviewee misunderstood the question to imply own funding.

Other Challenges

Other general barriers mentioned by the interviewees include the difficulty for people to understand the strategy, the lack of awareness of what bioproducts are, and the lack of consistent data on the use of bio-based products.

On the question of which is the pillar/stakeholder group that needs further elaboration on their engagement the interviewees mentioned that farmers, growers, consumers, private investors, start-ups, and financing institutions need further elaboration and the main reason for that is the lack of awareness and the difficulty to communicate what bioeconomy is.

Table 22. Barriers and Obstacles to the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Wuerttemberg of Germany

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles			
Organising themes	Challenges in the uptake of the regional bioeconomy strategy			
Basic themes (identified from the literature review)	Institutional challenges	Implementation challenges	Financial challenges	General barriers
Interviewee 1 (F, Academia)	The relevant questions were not used in the interview due to the level of expertise of the interviewee and the maturity level of bioeconomy in BW			
Interviewee 2 (F, Government)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Heavy workload. • Not enough human resources. 	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty to understand the strategy.
Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community)	Lack of clear regulatory framework.	Lack of infrastructure and logistics support for bio-based products: “[...] This can make it difficult for companies to transport and store these products, which can increase costs and reduce the competitiveness of these products.”	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of awareness of what bio-products are: “[...] Many people are still not familiar with the benefits of bio-based products, such as hemp-based foods, and the potential environmental and health benefits they offer.” • Lack of consistent data on the use of bio-based products.
Interviewee 4 (F, Business Community)	Lack of regulations with a holistic approach.	Lack of standardization.	Lack of funding.	N/A

Table 23. Stakeholder groups in need of support on bioeconomy and challenges for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany

Global theme	Barriers and obstacles	
Organizing themes	Pillar/stakeholder group that needs further elaboration on the stakeholder's engagement	Aspects that make it difficult to set up a regional bioeconomy strategy
<p>Interviewee 1 (F, Academia)</p>	<p>Farmers: <i>"[...] farmers are the ones more difficult to be engaged in the bioeconomy in our region. They receive a lot of requirements from different administrative levels (EU, national and regional). [...] Sometimes, they might feel overwhelmed due to the administrative workload that these demands represent to them."</i></p> <p><i>"[...] It should also be considered that Baden-Wuerttemberg is a region of family farming properties. Nonetheless, farmers and biomass producers are at the heart of the bioeconomy strategy, so it should be considered how important they are. It is very relevant to design the bioeconomic transition with them with a bottom-up approach. But they might feel a bit sceptical about these policy processes, sometimes."</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty to communicate to a wide variety of stakeholders what bioeconomy is: <i>"[...] In general, I would say that it is very important to explain to people what the bioeconomy is. That might help e.g., the biomass producers to feel less overwhelmed with the administrative requirements collated to this process."</i> • Dynamics of bioeconomy: <i>"[...] Secondly, the policymakers should know the trade-offs of the bioeconomy, since the bioeconomy is not sustainable per se. It is needed to assess how global trade affects regional strategies, or how policies in one region can affect other regions. No region in the world is an island."</i>
<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Government)</p>	<p>Biomass is limited: <i>"[...] From an economical point of view- it is worthwhile concentrating on urban and industrial bioeconomy since waste, wastewater and exhaust air is available in inexhaustible quantities."</i></p> <p>Not enough stakeholder engagement: <i>"[...] In Baden-Wuerttemberg nevertheless, a big group of stakeholders is concentrating on rural bioeconomy and almost neglecting urban and industrial bioeconomy. This second pillar of the state strategy needs more awareness-raising, so more stakeholder's engagement."</i></p>	<p>Bioeconomy is a term that is difficult to understand: <i>"[...] I feel that the term bioeconomy is difficult to understand. Governments are reluctant to deal with a topic which is not understood by the public. Here it could be helpful to describe the matter, like "We live in a world of limited resources. In future, we need to replace fossil energy sources to fight climate change and reach climate neutrality. It is necessary to save resources, and to use better what we already use and use well what we don't use yet. It could be actually ensuring survival when we are able to use our biomass, waste, wastewater and exhaust air and recover raw materials from these sources or even upcycle them to products.""</i></p>
<p>Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Traditional farmers. • Growers: <i>"[...] who may not be familiar with the potential of bio-based products, such as hemp, or may be hesitant to change their existing practices."</i> • Consumers: <i>"[...] Another group that can be difficult to engage are consumers, who may not be familiar with the benefits of bio-based products, or may be hesitant to try something new."</i> 	<p>Lack of education and awareness: <i>"[...] To engage these groups more effectively, it's important to educate them about the potential of bio-based products and the benefits of a bioeconomy strategy. This can be done through events and workshops, informational materials, and by building relationships with key leaders and influencers in these groups. Additionally, providing incentives and technical assistance may also encourage the adoption of bioeconomy practices."</i></p>

<p>Interviewee 4 (F, Business Community)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Private investors and financing institutions.• Start-ups.	<p>Stakeholders need further information about options to integrate themselves as actors in bioeconomy: <i>"[.] Start-ups are highly motivated to fill and strengthen their role as active, innovative and agile actors but are limited by the lack of suitable funding schemes or specific tax incentives."</i></p>
--	--	--

III. Opportunities and motivations for the uptake of a regional bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Wuerttemberg in Germany

The benefits of the bioeconomy strategy in place in this region fall under the following categories:

- i. **Promotion of Business Development** includes the development of new value chains and rural sustainable practices, the opportunity to develop new and innovative products by using bio-based ingredients, and the creation of new jobs and economic growth.
- ii. **Research and Innovation Development** includes the potential for diversification of crop production.
- iii. **Empowerment of existing policy frameworks** including the application for funding.
- iv. **Awareness raising/ Information sharing** includes the participation of all stakeholders, a better understanding of their role as actors, integrating themselves into the system, and networking.
- v. **Environmental benefits** include the creation of a sustainable and resilient region and interlinked economic and social benefits.

The interviewees also mentioned that the key element of BW related to the bioeconomy is the inter-ministerial work when it comes to developing the strategy and the social benefits provided. Table 25 presents how the existence of an effective government throughout the development of a sustainable bioeconomy could provide benefits related to aspects such as the establishment of public policies with governmental support, the waste management potential, policy changes by establishing synergies, collaboration with other sectors and networks, utilising EU or national funding, the boost of innovation and development as well as the environmental perspective.

Table 24. Benefits of a future regional bioeconomy strategy in Baden-Wuerttemberg in Germany

Global Theme	Drivers and Opportunities						
Organising themes	Benefits of the bioeconomy strategy in place						
Basic Themes	Utilising available feedstock (A sufficient amount of biomass feedstock and residuals that could be used and converted into real commodities)	Promotion of business development (Business opportunities in the bioeconomy sectors)	Research and Innovation Development (High potential for research and innovation development)	Policy development related to bioeconomy (Opportunities for policy development in bioeconomy strategies)	Empowerment of existing policy frameworks (Bioeconomy policy could support existing policy frameworks)	Awareness raising/ Information sharing (Bioeconomy policy could raise awareness in society on bioeconomy practices)	Environmental
Interviewee 1 (F, Academia)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Value chain development. Sustainable rural development. 	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
Interviewee 2 (F, Government)	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	Participation of all stakeholders.	N/A
Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community)	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Opportunity to develop new and innovative products by using bio-based ingredients like hemp. New jobs and economic growth. 	Potential for diversification of crop production.	N/A	N/A	N/A	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sustainable and resilient region. Economic and social benefits.
Interviewee 4 (F, Business Community)	N/A	Increasing visibility and impact.	N/A	N/A	Apply for funding support.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Better understanding their role as actors Integrating themselves in the system Networking 	N/A

Table 25. Reasons for the uptake and the existence of an effective governance framework with a focus on bioeconomy in Baden-Wuerttemberg in Germany

Global theme	Drivers and Opportunities							
Organising themes	Reasons for the existence of an effective governance framework throughout the development of a sustainable bioeconomy							
Basic themes	Reasons for the uptake of a bioeconomy strategy in the region	Establishment of public policies with governmental support	Waste management potential	Policy changes by establishing synergies	Collaboration with other sectors and networks	Utilising EU or national funding	Boost innovation and development	Environmental
<p>Interviewee 1 (F, Academia)</p>	<p>A strategy of bioeconomy facilitates the cohesive and holistic approach of the framework model set. It allows considering the economy, society, and environment along the process.</p> <p>Moreover, inter-ministerial work – as it happens in Baden-Wuerttemberg – assures this approach.</p> <p>If this is lacking, ministerial policies tend to be too sectoral, and too narrow-oriented.</p>	N/A	Enhancement of biodiversity and agriculture productivity.	N/A	More synergies.	N/A	N/A	N/A
<p>Interviewee 2 (F, Government)</p>	N/A	N/A	Utilisation of feedstock.	Policy changes.	Business Opportunities.	N/A	N/A	N/A

D1.3: Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions, 24/02/2023

<p>Interviewee 3 (M, Business Community)</p>	<p>Social benefits: “[...] By promoting sustainable and environmentally friendly products, a bioeconomy strategy can help to ensure that future generations have access to healthy and nutritious food, and a more sustainable environment.”</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic benefits. • New jobs. 	<p>N/A</p>	<p>Sustainable and environmentally friendly products.</p>	<p>Sustainable development.</p>
<p>Interviewee 4 (F, Business Community)</p>	<p>Provides clear guidance. Marketing tool for the region: “[...] A bioeconomy strategy is the guiding principle for a region. It can be referred to for road mapping processes, benchmarking with other strategies (national, European, international) and is key to long term for sighting. It is also a marketing tool for the region and can be used as a brand of excellence “Bioeconomy made in BW”</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>N/A</p>

The interviewees presented insights into the barriers, opportunities, and motivations for the uptake of Regional Governance Models with a focus on bioeconomy in the ROBIN pilot regions.

In the ROBIN pilot regions, only Baden-Wuerttemberg and Andalusia have an already implemented bioeconomy strategy while the rest of the regions are on their way towards developing their regional bioeconomy strategy. It is interesting that all regions presented similar challenges related to the four different categories of barriers (institutional, implementation, financial, and other) as identified and categorized through the literature review.

Barriers such as the lack of an official governmental framework to streamline the way to bioeconomy, and the lack of data and monitoring processes related to **institutional challenges** were mentioned in all regions. **Implementation barriers** related to the lack of knowledge on what bioeconomy is and the lack of communication of the term bioeconomy and its benefits to the public were also mentioned thoroughly by all interviewees. It is important to highlight that the transition from a linear to a circular economy with bioeconomy taking the lead, is a dynamic process and requires the participation of multiple stakeholders. As mentioned by many interviewees, it is very difficult to advance quickly in the sector as many stakeholders including the public do not have the necessary information about its benefits and real-life applications and therefore, need further elaboration on their engagement.

The **financial barriers** were evident in every pilot region, with the lack of funding for bioeconomy initiatives standing as the main hindering factor to the uptake of a regional governance model focused on bioeconomy. In the Zilina region of Slovakia, the Andalusian region of Spain, and the Region of Central Macedonia of Greece, the bureaucratic burden was mentioned as a discouraging factor to set up and further develop a regional bioeconomy strategy.

Among all the stakeholders mentioned as a difficult group to engage, the interviewees in the Southern Region of Ireland underlined that stakeholders who fall under the marine sector could be characterized as a hard-to-engage category as they present strong union characteristics, and they already possess sufficient power in the sector. Ireland as a coastal country depends strongly on the marine sector which works as an important source of income and employment in the region [12]. Similarly, in the Zilina region in Slovakia, the interviewees mentioned that foresters are a very difficult stakeholder group to engage deeper in bioeconomy practices. That might have implications for local stakeholder engagement and should be an important point to consider when designing regional bioeconomy strategies as forests in Slovakia cover almost 40% of the country's agricultural fields.

From the insights gathered from the interviews, it could be argued that a strong existence of regulatory guidelines in combination with adequate funding and efficient stakeholder participation could open the road to deploy the potential of bioeconomy and its benefits in each region. Even though there are multiple barriers to the uptake of a regional strategy related to bioeconomy, the interviewees were asked about the benefits and opportunities of having a bioeconomy strategy in place.

All categories identified in the literature review such as the utilisation of feedstock, promotion of business development, research and innovation deployment, policy development related to bioeconomy initiatives, empowerment of existing policy frameworks, awareness-raising and information sharing, the waste management potential were introduced by all interviewees. Irish and Slovak interviewees mentioned multiple environmental benefits when deploying bioeconomy practices whereas, in the other regions, the interviewees did not mention anything else related to environmental benefits apart from the utilisation of available feedstock in the region which could fall under the development of biodiversity. It is also interesting to see that in the Zilina region and the Region of Central Macedonia, the interviewees talked about the empowerment of the rural population through bioeconomy practices, the improvement of well-being, and the overall enhancement of human development in rural areas.

Taking advantage of EU funding mechanisms was one element that only interviewees from SRA mentioned. This might have implications for the existing gaps in how to develop regional bioeconomy governance models in each region as the public in most ROBIN pilot regions does not know the term bioeconomy and therefore, they do not know about funding opportunities on the topic. The fact that only 2 interviewees mentioned the aspect of human development could relate to the inexistent knowledge of the bioeconomy as a term. People do not know the benefits of it so therefore how the applications of bioeconomy in real life could also improve their personal quality of life.

Overall, the interviews insights confirmed the findings in international literature in terms of barriers, benefits, and opportunities for the uptake of regional bioeconomy governance models, however new aspects were also introduced such as the environmental benefits of bioeconomy applications (e.g., low footprint, climate change mitigation), human development (e.g., new jobs) and awareness raising (e.g., engagement of all stakeholder groups). Also, there is a need of a streamlined framework to pave the way to regional bioeconomy governance models, and the term bioeconomy and its benefits need to be communicated effectively to wider audiences.

4. Analysis of the Regional Policy Mix in the ROBIN Regions

The five regions in the ROBIN project are 1) Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany, 2) Central Macedonia, Greece, 3) Southern Region, Ireland, 4) Zilina, Slovakia and 5) Andalusia, Spain (Figure 2). They extend across the EU, covering the territorial diversity, from East to West and from South to North, of the EU, and as such, they represent a diverse group of regions in terms of regional peculiarities.

Figure 2: Regions of the ROBIN project

4.1 Methodology

The analysis of the regional policy mix in the five ROBIN regions was conducted through the regional partners that are members of the ROBIN consortium, as well as with the assistance of the other consortium partners. Furthermore, semi-structured interviews with individuals involved in the design and implementation of each regional bioeconomy strategy were administered to representatives of the five ROBIN regions, that were involved in the design and implementation of each regional bioeconomy strategy.

In case more information was needed on the particular specificities of each region in focus, a short questionnaire was developed to be distributed/used for semi-structured interviews with individuals involved in the design and implementation of each regional bioeconomy strategy. The questionnaire aimed at collecting additional insights on the successful circular bioeconomy strategies conducted within the regions as well as identify success factors and strong points, but also barriers and challenges. From the five (5) ROBIN regions, additional information were collected for the Baden Württemberg region. The questionnaire template and the informed consent form are available in ANNEX C.

4.2 Regional and local peculiarities

The five ROBIN regions represent a diverse territorial group, representative of the heterogeneity of the European Union, as this was one of the reasons they were selected for the project.

In Table 26, a presentation of 4 basic regional characteristics is provided for the five ROBIN regions. Specifically, the location, the size, the population, and the GDP per capita. Due to lack of available data, GDP per capita is missing for the regions of Zilina and Central Macedonia. The regions vary in size from 19 km² in Central Macedonia, Greece to 35751 km² in Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany. Regarding population size, there is also a large diversity from 0,7 Million inhabitants (Mio) in Zilina, Slovakia to 11 Mio in Baden-Wuerttemberg, Germany. Similarly, differences in GDP per capita reflect differences in GDP per capita across the EU, thus, for the regions that have available data, the range is between 19991 euros in Andalusia, Spain and 88500 euros in the Southern region, Ireland.

Table 26: Regional Characteristics

Region	Location	Size	Population	GDP per capita
Baden-Wuerttemberg	Southwest Germany	35751 km ²	11 Mio	48727 Euros
Central Macedonia	Northern Greece	19 km ²	1,8 Mio	N/A
Southern region	Ireland	29 km ²	1,7 Mio	88500 Euros
Zilina	Slovakia	6809 km ²	0,7 Mio	N/A

Andalusia	Spain	87 km ²	8,5 Mio	19991 Euros
------------------	-------	--------------------	---------	----------------

Following, in Table 27, the existence or lack of regional bioeconomy value chains is displayed. Each ROBIN region is marked with an “X”, if an Agriculture, Forestry, Agroindustry, Chemical industry, or Energy value chain, operates/functions in that region. No Chemical industry value chain exists in Baden-Wuerttemberg, and no Agriculture, Agroindustry, or a Chemical industry value chain operates in the region of Zilina.

Table 27: Regional bioeconomy value chains

Region	Agriculture	Forestry	Agroindustry	Chemical industry	Energy
Baden-Wuerttemberg	x	x	x		x
Central Macedonia	x	x	x	x	x
Southern region	x	x	x	x	x
Zilina		x			x
Andalusia	x	x	x	x	x

The sectors and products of bioeconomy are presented in Table 28 for each one of the five ROBIN regions. They are classified in three categories: Biomass for energy/Biofuels, Biowaste, and Maritime. Baden-Wuerttemberg and Zilina, do not have a Maritime sector, and the region of Central Macedonia lacks all three sectors.

Table 28: Regional bioeconomy sectors and products

Region	Biomass for energy / Biofuels	Biowaste	Maritime
Baden-Wuerttemberg	x	x	
Central Macedonia	x	x	

Southern region	x	x	x
Zilina	x	x	
Andalusia	x	x	x

The implemented bioeconomy strategy and the establishment year is provided for each one of the five regions in Table 29. The Central Macedonia region is in the process of taking the first in implementing one.

Table 29: Regional bioeconomy strategies

Region	Establishment	Strategy
Baden-Wuerttemberg	2019	Sustainable Bioeconomy Strategy
Central Macedonia	First steps taken	
Southern region	2016	Regional, Spatial and Economy Strategy for the Southern Region (RSES) [not a dedicated regional bioeconomy strategy, however there is a National]
Zilina	N/A	Strategy for bioeconomy in Slovakia" Contribution of Slovak Bioeconomy to the Strategic Plan 2021-2027
Andalusia	2018	Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy

Concluding the five ROBIN regions' overview, Table 30 outlines the effects that regional bioeconomy governance models had on them.

Table 30: Effects of regional bioeconomy governance models to sectors

Region	
Baden-Wuerttemberg	Increase in the turnover from the bio-based innovations, settle new value chains, bring environmental benefits (e.g. through improvement of the valorisation of bio-waste [13]), as well as establish new examples of social innovation in form of bioeconomy labs / hubs e.g. the urban BioEconomyLab [14] or the Innovation Hub CCUBIO [15]
Central Macedonia	The implementation of the circular bioeconomy affects the region to a great extent. Its effect is enormous on positive environmental terms (less emissions of CO2, less water consumption, soil fertility. Its societal effect is strongly positive because of increased rate of employment especially in agriculture, waste management &

	energy. Economically, Circular Bioeconomy will also result to a positive effect as development of the Circular bioeconomy creates a climate that promotes the development, & modernisation of new start – ups and other enterprises.
Southern region	One of the benefits of the implementation of Bioeconomy statements and strategies that relate and reference the bioeconomy for the Southern Region is that the region is already home to a vast amount of biological raw materials and infrastructure resources along with world renowned research institutes in the circular bioeconomy sector. There is a strong collaboration between the industry and academia which fosters cutting edge advancements with the potential for a globally competitive and sustainable bioeconomy. There is a willingness to learn in the region that creates a good atmosphere for cross-sectorial partnership towards sustainable development. The Southern Region is moving towards becoming a UNESCO Learning Region. The Southern Regional Assembly's ' <i>Towards a Learning Region</i> ' identifies 19 actions which will move the region towards establishing a Learning Region. One of these actions is to ensure more students and workers across all sectors participate in educational courses and skills development that support the transition to a Low Carbon and Circular Economy.
Zilina	The effect of the strategy was mainly on the forestry sector, the volumes of wood salvaged from natural losses (salvage fellings) consistently represent more than half of total fellings (actual logging) and have continuously increased since 2000, in line with planned logging that increases on average by 4% annually. However, the use of renewable resources in Žilina region is estimated to be very small compared to its potential.
Andalusia	The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy is in the process of being implemented with a framework until 2030. When the implementation of ABCS starts, an interim report will analyse the impact of the Strategy on the region's bioeconomy.

4.3 Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies

In the case of **Baden-Wuerttemberg**, the basic objectives of the bioeconomy strategy are the development of biological concepts for the exploitation of renewable or recyclable raw materials, and the development of Baden-Wuerttemberg as a model region for sustainable and circular economy, as well as, strengthening the role of the rural areas. Other aspects are relevantly considered e.g., impact of climate change, protection of the biodiversity and the promotion of bio-based innovations. The scope of the strategy is wide, covering rural, urban, and industrial areas.

The strategy is characterized as remarkably cross-sector and cross-policy. The main cross-border element of the strategy is the organization of the international “Bioeconomy Congress Baden-Wuerttemberg” every two years, as well as participation in EU initiatives and (particularly) in Interreg projects. The Congress is an initiative out of the Bioeconomy Research Programme set in 2013. It is aimed at a regional, national, and international audience.

Moreover, the bioeconomy and the circular economy are explicitly mentioned in the chapter 5.8 (“Innovation for more resource efficiency, circular economy and climate protection”) of the Innovation Strategy Baden-Wuerttemberg (Update in 2020) [16]. In this strategy aspects such as the role of the

bioeconomy, the adaptation of the automotive industry -one of the key sectors in the region- to the circular economy principles, and the prospects for a hydrogen-based economy are mentioned or elaborated. Social innovation is mentioned in the document in form of “sharing economy”.

As already mentioned, the regional bioeconomy strategy advocates deliberately for a wide definition of the bioeconomy. Three interdisciplinary areas of action related with networking, education and information are listed in the strategy. The systemic approach of the *thematic initiatives* (measure 26 of the strategy) is also a relevant element on this regard. An example of bio-based solutions integrated to existing systems can be found in a recent co-funded project via European Regional Development Fund called Biowaste to Products (BW₂Pro), in which a modular biorefinery will be installed in the location of the public company Abfallwirtschaft Rems-Murr, so secondary raw materials can be obtained from municipal waste and wastewater treatment plants in a county with 425,000 inhabitants. The project has a 2.5-year duration.

In the case of **Central Macedonia**, The Regional Development Fund on behalf of the Region of Central Macedonia participates in the European scheme “Regional Models of circular economy & best available techniques for biological streams” – *BIOREGIO* [17]. *BIOREGIO*’s target is the direction of regional policies to support the best practices of circular economy and it is funded by the inter-region programme INTERREG EUROPE 2014-2020. It is realized locally by the Heat Transfer & Environmental Engineering Laboratory of the *Department of Mechanical Engineers* [18] of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and the *Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia* [19].

CESME (Circular Economy for SMEs) aims to the transition from a linear to a circular economy where all outflows from a production activity are reused as inflows to another production activity resulting to greener methods.

The circular bioeconomy strategy is cross-sector, cross policy and cross border/inter -region., e.g., there are inter-regional programs between Greece and Bulgaria, and Greece and North Macedonia. Also, it is cross-policy and cross sector strategy as environment, agriculture, and energy are the basis for a more positive future, economically, socially, and environmentally.

The strategic vision/s and objectives of the circular bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia is the direction of regional policies to support the best practices of circular economy (by reduction of environmental impact through management of wastes and reuse/recycle of the feedstocks/biomass to energy creation). There are bio-based solutions integrated to existing systems/processes and they may be independent. Public awareness and acceptance of the circular bioeconomy strategy is characterized as medium since more training & education of the general population is needed. Finally, the degree of concern, interest, and knowledge of farmers/producers/businesses (stakeholders) about the circular bioeconomy strategies available, the problem of waste, etc., and the circularity opportunities (marketing, social, etc) is high. Consulting Agencies, Farm Advisors via workshops & seminars & on-site training in the field can incorporate Circular Bioeconomy into their Development Plan. On the public sector side and the Chamber’s side, public officers, auditors and Chambers officers may communicate many of Circular Bioeconomy’s aspects through legislation and Best Practice techniques.

In the case of the **Southern region**, there is no specific regional bioeconomy strategy, however there are several both national and regional strategies that are informing regional bioeconomy development including Regional Policy Objectives contained in the RSES for the Southern Region. The National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy (NPS) is part of a broader bioeconomy strategy for the whole of the country. First published in 2018, the NPS was introduced with the purpose of

capitalising on the Bioeconomy's future potential. The Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy is Ireland's first circular economy strategy and a key component of the government's plans for a circular economy to contribute to net-zero emissions by no later than 2050. Its primary objective is to provide a national policy framework to reduce Ireland's circularity gap and includes instruments that address the economic, regulatory, and social barriers to achieving this objective. It also promotes the development of the Irish circular bioeconomy. The Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy for the Southern Region (RSES) is a strategic development framework for the future development of the regions three main rural and urban areas. This framework aims to protect and enhance the environment and successfully combat climate change. The bioeconomy is identified as a sector offering significant development opportunities and a key instrument in the transition to a low carbon economy. Renewable Fuels for Transport Policy Statement 2021 –2023 sets out a roadmap for the supply and use of renewable fuels in transport energy in meeting targets set out in the Climate Action Plan 2021 and European obligations for renewable energy supply and use in transport. Finally, the South East Energy Agency, with collaboration from the Southern Regional Assembly, are currently finalising a South East Bioenergy Implementation Plan.

The NPS is built upon the following core policy objectives:

- Research, Innovation & Skills,
- Enhancement of markets and competitiveness,
- Policy co-ordination and stakeholder engagement.

The Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy:

- Aligns itself to policy objectives of the NPS
- Outlines the importance of setting up a National Bioeconomy Forum and the High-Level Implementation Group
- Notes that one of the primary objectives of the bioeconomy is to aid Ireland's transition to a carbon neutral and circular economy while emphasizing the importance of a "coherent, horizontal approach to policymaking across sectors".

The Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy for the Southern Region:

- The Strategy planning and economic strategy is underpinned by strong National policy in the National Planning Framework, which sets the context for the RSES through 10 National Strategic Outcomes, several of which apply to the development of the bioeconomy within the 3 urban regions: Compact Growth, Strengthened Rural Economies and Communities, Transition to Sustainable Energy and Sustainable Management of Water and other Environmental Resources.

Renewable Fuels for Transport Policy Statement 2021 –2023:

- Support Ireland's commitment to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.
- Meet and exceed the renewable energy targets set out in RED II and future ambition under the EU Fit for 55 proposals.
- To ensure a shift towards non-crop fuels and more robust sustainability criteria.
- Establish a framework of obligations to support these objectives.

The circular bioeconomy strategy can be characterized as cross-sector, cross-policy and cross-border / inter-region as follows:

- Cross Sectoral
 - NPS & The Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy – recognise that the bioeconomy consists of farming and the agri-food businesses, marine-based industries, forestry, waste management, energy suppliers, and pharma and biotechnology products.
 - The Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy for the Southern Region also identifies the importance that the bioeconomy plays within different industries across rural and urban areas.
- Cross-Policy
 - The NPS outlines that the *Action Plan for Rural Development (2017)* [20] “underlines how the bioeconomy can contribute to decarbonisation, sustainable growth and job creation in the agricultural, industrial and technological sectors in rural areas” and is also recognised in the *Action plan for jobs (2017)* [21].
 - The Bioeconomy Interdepartmental Group (2016) outlined in the NPS is chaired by An Taoiseach and is comprised of seven governmental departments which reflects the need for policy coherence across governmental departments.
- Cross-border / inter-region
 - The NPS has no cross-border references, however the government along with its Northern Irish counterparts, have established an annual All-Island Bio-based Industries Day with support from Intertrade Ireland. The event is now in its fourth year.
 - However, as the NPS and the Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy are national strategies, they are interregional.
 - The RSES report outlines policy objectives for the 3 areas of the Cork metropolitan area, Limerick-Shannon area, and Waterford metropolitan area.

There is a strong connection between the circular bioeconomy strategy and other related strategies. More specifically, in addition to Ireland’s NPS, published in 2018, the country will introduce its first Bioeconomy Action Plan covering the 2023-2025 period which has been outlined in the Climate Action Plan 2021 Action List. The Bioeconomy and the opportunities that it creates is also recognised as an important opportunity within the Action Plans for Rural Development and Jobs also published in 2018. Regarding Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs): Whilst documents like the NPS do not mention them directly it is recognised that an array of bioeconomy activities supports around half of SDGs. Goals like 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth, 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure and 12: Responsible Consumption and Production do align with the aims of existing national and regional strategies on the bioeconomy. The National Implementation Plan for the Sustainable Development Goals 2022-2024. Published October 2022, it is structured around five strategic objectives:

- Embed SDG framework across all government policy.
- Integrate SDG into local authorities to support localisation of SDGs.
- Greater partnerships for the SDGss.
- Incorporate the principle of Leave No One Behind into Ireland’s Agenda 2030 implementation.
- Strong reporting mechanisms.

As a result of these objectives, it is expected to see a higher prominence of the SDGs in future strategies particularly at a regional level.

Furthermore, the circular bioeconomy strategy is linked to the S3 and the Climate Action Plan.

The NPS sets out four strategic policy objectives:

- Sustainable economy & Society: Developing the Irish Bioeconomy will be the basis for the entire economy to be more sustainable and encourage a greater ethos of circularity.
- Decarbonisation of the economy: Greenhouse gases can be reduced by developing the bioeconomy, new and innovative processes and practices will encourage efficiency in sectors with high emissions like Agriculture and Forestry. Replacing high embedded carbon products with bio-based alternative and developing bioprocessing and biorefining will also play a large part in reducing emissions.
- Jobs & Competitiveness: Bioeconomy inputs are sourced nationally opening the possibilities for future employment as these bio-based industries develop. With unpredictability arising from international pressures like the war in Ukraine and Brexit, the bioeconomy offers an opportunity replace imported fossil-based inputs.
- Regional prosperity: Many bio-based industries are regionally based, and a developed bioeconomy will help reduce regional decline. Involving regional assemblies in the policy making process will help further the effectiveness of development of regional bioeconomy's.

Within the current sphere of bioeconomy stakeholders, bioeconomy awareness is high, and several educational programmes and activities are underway nationally and within the region to promote awareness among new actors. However, outside of this sphere, it is still a developing sector. Recent studies show that important regional stakeholders such as consumers, public and primary producers still have a relatively lack a deep awareness of the bioeconomy, despite holding relatively positive impressions of the concept.

There is limited information available to reflect the degree of concern, interest and knowledge of stakeholders surrounding circular bioeconomy strategies, the problem of waste and the circularity opportunities available. Anecdotally, primary producers do have a strong concern that bio-based alternatives etc are cost prohibitive and the degree of investment and time required results in them not being a viable alternative.

In the case of **Zilina**, and in accordance with the social and economic development plan 2021+, Zilina region plans to implement the principles of bioeconomy and prepare to achieve the goals of the European Union. The strategy for bioeconomy in Slovakia is the national strategic plan related to the circular bioeconomy. Currently, no bio-based solutions are present or integrated into existing systems or processes.

There is a low level of information and public awareness on the advantages of biological products compared to fossil products. Terms such as bioeconomy are considered hardly comprehensible terminology for the public. However, there is a growing interest of society (especially the young generation) in topics close to bioeconomy.

In the case of **Andalusia**, the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) was developed by the Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Sustainable Development (CAGPDS by its name in Spanish) and approved by the Andalusian Government on September 18th, 2018.

With the support of EU funding, the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy project promotes sustainable growth and regional development by fostering the production of renewable and biological products and processes.

The targeted sectors include agriculture, forestry, fishing, food, and paper production, as well as part of the chemical, biotechnology, and energy industries.

The strategy works with a timeframe for 2030 and has resources worth around 1 400 Mio euros, aimed at specific actions that have been developed with the collaboration of more than 50 external experts from the sectors of interest.

The strategy will be implemented through a set of four instrumental programs of a transversal nature: communication and awareness, promotion of R+D+i and education, access to financing, and cooperation and collaboration. In total, 17 measures and 39 actions have been defined.

Aside from this, the government has promoted the creation of rural development working groups aiming to boost the agri-food sector in rural areas. Concerning regulation, the regional government will soon pass the regional Law for the Circular Economy. Also, in 2021, the "Andalusian Overall Plan for Waste. Towards a Circular Economy in 2030 Horizon" (PIRec 2030) was approved.

The focus of the ACBS is the development of activities among three segments of the bioeconomy value chain: the production of biomass, the technical processing, and the consumer markets. In addition, the general aim is to involve all actors of the fourfold approach: knowledge centres, administrations, companies, and citizens.

Vision: Building a diversified and sustainable region in which the circular bioeconomy is the cornerstone for development combined with the improvement of human welfare and social equity, thus generating opportunities for quality jobs for citizens, with greater resilience to current changes and transformations and future trends, adapted to climate change that will gradually reduce its dependence on external resources

The strategy focuses on the regional bioeconomy areas less developed and aims to support the implementation of specific actions that facilitate its take-off and consolidation in the medium-long term. The relevant sectors for the bioeconomy include agriculture, forestry, fishing, food, and paper production, as well as part of the chemical, biotechnology, and energy industries. The time horizon of the strategy is 2030.

The main objective of the ACBS is to contribute to sustainable growth and development in Andalusia by carrying out actions toward the production of renewable and biological products and processes. Three strategic objectives can be pointed out:

- Increase the availability of sustainable biomass for its use through innovative treatments.
- Increase the number of bio-industries and biorefineries in Andalusia.
- Increase markets and the consumption of bioproducts and bioenergy in Andalusia.

There is a need for technological developments specifically adapted to every type of biological resource and industrial process and the need to make progress on the development of integrated biorefineries.

The experience gained by Andalusia after being selected by the European Commission as a model demonstrator region to lead the way towards a chemical sustainable production in Europe constitutes another opportunity for the circular bioeconomy in our region. Thanks to this project, Andalusia has received the advisory and technical support of the European Sustainable Chemicals Support Service. This has enabled it to define this new concept of industry and help to generate new investment and employment opportunities to bring wealth and make progress in the achievement of

a circular economy, the aim of zero residues, and the reduction of pollutant emissions. At the same time, the project has strengthened the intersectoral relations between the chemical industries and those which are involved in the processes that produce raw materials.

The ACBS points out that there is some misinformation from the citizenship side about what bioeconomy means and what it implies. There are also weaknesses in the promotion of products and services related to bioeconomy fields.

To make the implementation of bioproducts on the markets come true, a system allowing their identification by final consumers must be established. The standardization of bioproducts seems to be a key element for their recognition by society.

The ACBS points out that there is limited knowledge of alternative uses of different raw materials and their introduction in alternative value chains in the field of circular bioeconomy.

4.4 The Quadruple Helix actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system

In the case of **Baden-Wuerttemberg**, the regional bioeconomy strategy is backed-up politically by the State Ministry. The conception and drafting of the strategy were driven by two leading ministries in 2019, the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection, and the Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy Sector, both finally featuring as co-publishers. The implementation is based in a cross-departmental work also involving the Ministry of Science, Research and the Arts, and the Ministry of Economic Affairs, Labour and Tourism. Besides that, the Sustainable Bioeconomy Council acts as a board of experts advising, guiding, and supporting the strategy process; it is consulted in a periodic basis. This Council is currently composed of 17 experts coming from different sectors (industry, academia, and research), including Prof. Dr. Ralf Kindervater, CEO of BIOPRO Baden-Wuerttemberg. Civil and environmental NGOs are not represented in this Council. Nonetheless they participated in the consultation and participative process ran in 2017/2018.

Baden-Wuerttemberg as a region has an extend pool of academia, research, clusters, business support organisations and companies related with the bioeconomy. The universities, universities of applied science and research institutions cover the entire range of research topics that are important for the bioeconomy (e.g., agricultural science, forestry, plastics technology, materials science, textile technology or energy). A relevant example is the University of Hohenheim in Stuttgart, that launched the first bioeconomy degree programme in Europe and has its own Research Faculty of Bioeconomy.

Baden-Wuerttemberg has a long tradition on participative governance, and it is highly valued. In 2013, the participation portal Baden-Wuerttemberg [22] was launched, in which citizens can participate online. An example would be civil society involvement around land readjustment. These are agri-structural reorganisation measures related e.g., to the construction of a new road. This action can fragment land ownership, but it can be reunited during the process to facilitate working conditions in agriculture. A platform [23] provides information about current procedures, and citizens can actively give comments and opinions and participate in workshops or events.

There are several examples as citizens' initiatives and non-profit organizations like associations which lobby for topics as e. g. permaculture, e-mobility, and renewable energies. It is interesting to mention that, from a first glance, land use for agriculture and renewable energies (photovoltaic, wind, biomethanol production, etc.) might be considered contradictive but could be merged by combining

both in Agri-Photovoltaic projects (Agri-PV) [24]. The special characteristic about citizens' initiatives is that there are events to different topics (among them, rural development), in which citizens' initiatives can speak directly with representatives of the regional government and local administration to present their concerns and ideas.

In the case of primary producers such as farmers and farmer cooperatives/associations there has been a continuous advance on the positive position toward the bioeconomy since 2017. The introduction of the European Green Deal and the new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) even reinforced this trend. The main two agricultural sector organizations in Baden-Wuerttemberg are the Genossenschaftsverband e.V. (BWGV) and the Landesbauerverband in Baden-Wuerttemberg e.V., LBV. "Tank-plate" discussions from the past have got over and now the main topic might be the land use change.

In the case of **Central Macedonia**, the policy departments in the local and regional administrations that are currently involved in the development and implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy are the Decentralized Administration of Macedonia and Thrace, the Hellenic Environmental Inspectorate of MoEE, and the Directorate of Development & Environment of the Region of Central Macedonia, Division of Agro-economy & Veterinary. Policy departments that should also be involved in the future include the Departments of Environment & Quality of Life of all local Towns inside the Region of Central Macedonia. A specific cluster has been developed, CERTH (Centre for Research and Technology Hellas). Among its areas of expertise, activities in renewable energy sources, solid biofuels production and utilization, energy saving, and environmental protection are included. It is involved in several EU funded projects regarding agrobiomass utilization and market uptake of bioenergy, such as *AGROinLOG* [25], *SECURECHAIN* [26], *uP running* [27], *Biomassud Plus* [28] and *BIOFIT* [29].

People's attitudes towards co-creation with policymakers are currently characterized as hesitantly positive. Currently no bioeconomy strategy council or similar structure is present to overview the implementation of policy. The main stakeholders in the region for the circular bioeconomy strategy are farmers, industry owners, universities, the public and private sectors. As the actors involved derive from different fields, they are considered to represent a diversity of perspectives and interests among them. Their common priorities are environmental management and economic incentives. The role of public authorities, i.e., public officers, auditors and Chambers officers is to communicate many of Circular Bioeconomy's aspects through legislation and Best Practice techniques and to familiarize stakeholders about the circular bioeconomy strategies available, the problem of waste, etc., and the circularity opportunities, convincing them to incorporate Circular Bioeconomy into their Development Plan.

In the case of the **Southern region**, since there is no specific regional Bioeconomy strategy, but a broader statement for the whole country, the relevant policy departments involved in the development and the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy also include many involved ones at the national and regional levels:

National Policy Statement in the Bioeconomy (National):

- Department of the Taoiseach (Irish prime minister)
- Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine
- Department of Environment, Climate and Communications
- Department of Enterprise Trade and Employment

- Department of Rural and Community Development
- Department of Transport
- Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media (The Gaeltacht is the term used to refer to those areas of Ireland where the Irish language (Gaeilge) is still spoken as a community language)
- Department of Education

Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy (National):

- Department of Environment, Climate and Communications

Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy for the Southern Region (Regional):

- Southern Regional Assembly's Regional Planning and EU Programmes Division (Southern Regional Assembly lead the implementation of the RSES)
- Department of Enterprise, Trade and Employment
- Department of Education (Contributed to the production of the RSES)
- Department of Foreign Affairs (Contributed to the production of the RSES)
- Department of Rural and Community Development (Contributed to the production of the RSES)
- Department of Transport (Contributed to the production of the RSES)
- Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media
- Relevant departments in Local Authorities across the region. Expertise would usually be located in 'Environment' Departments /Sections but Planning and Economic Development Departments would also be involved.

Furthermore, policy departments in local and regional administrations that should also be involved in the future or have shown interest in being involved are: Local Authorities (Carlow, Kilkenny, Wexford, Cork, Kerry, Limerick, Clare, Tipperary, Waterford) Environment, Planning, Community/Social & Finance. In most Local Authorities the Environment/ Planning and Economic Development Departments would be the departments most likely to be involved; Regional Assemblies (Southern Regional Assembly)- Regional Planning and EU Programmes; Atlantic Seaboard South Climate Action Regional Office CARO- Local Authority Climate Action; Southern Region Waste Management Office; Enterprise Ireland- Funding and Research and Innovation; Irish Water; Environmental Protection Agency EPA- Climate change, Waste; Sustainable Energy Authority Ireland- Low Carbon Heating and Cooling Technologies; Teagasc- Animal and Grassland Research and Innovation, Crops, Environment and Land Use, Food, Rural Economy and Development; Science Foundation Ireland- Climate research, Bioeconomy research; South East Energy Agency and Tipperary Energy Agency.

Several working groups were established among administrative departments involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy. These include are: the Bioeconomy Implementation Group which is co-chaired by DECC and DAFM and was established by the NPS, the National Bioeconomy Forum that was established in 2021 to promote, support and advocate for the sustainable development of the bioeconomy in Ireland in line with the progression of a circular economy, climate action and a climate-neutral, sustainable and innovative agri-food sector and the Southeast Energy Agency: The agency published a Bioenergy Roadmap (July 2022), part of which is developing regional stakeholder groups to drive policy change.

Several clusters were developed related to the operation of the bioeconomy in the region:

Circular Bioeconomy Cluster Southwest (*CircBio*) [30]

A first-of-a-kind regional bioeconomy cluster, established by the CircBio Research Group at MTU with a goal to develop and promote bioeconomy in the South-west region, with a focus on marine, agriculture, and waste-to-value thematic areas. The cluster has the aim of unlocking and accelerating business opportunities and new value chains across these sectors. The cluster fosters collaboration through events and workshops, site visits and project matchmaking, linking industry partners to R&D expertise in the region. They also support members with funding opportunities, communications and marketing, and education and training.

Irish Bioeconomy Foundation (*IBF*) [31]

IBFs is a national bioeconomy foundation based at Lisheen Co. Tipperary with the mission to promote the conversion of Ireland's natural land & sea resources to high value products for the development of a sustainable bioeconomy that is globally competitive and creates local development. The foundation facilitates the agrifood, forestry, marine, energy sectors to create synergies enabling innovative projects at a global, regional and local level. Operating on a national level, but are located within the Southern Region, and their activities influence bioeconomy development within the region.

No studies regarding people's attitudes towards co-creation with policy makers in the region are available. However, public consultation in the development of sustainable government policy is the norm, and this was also the case in the development of the national bioeconomy policy statement. In addition, part of the role of Ireland's National Bioeconomy Forum is to help inform the development of bioeconomy policy with input from different stakeholders, and to date it has been an effective mechanism.

There can be many competing interests among the stakeholders. Even in terms of sourcing biomass, it can still be challenging to understand which biomass may be harvested without having a negative impact on things like biodiversity and eco-systems services. The development of new value chains can also bring competing interests as each stakeholder will have specific needs. For example – primary producers need to get a fair return for their biomass or residual stream to help maintain the profitability for their farms, often technology developers will require the biomass to be as affordable as possible in order to have a viable process, and meanwhile consumers expect to buy affordable products which are also sustainable. With all of these different priorities, it is sometimes difficult to reconcile these competing interests to develop new value chains and enterprises.

Finally, it should be noted that the Southern Regional Assembly is part of the regional tier of government in Ireland. Part of the local government sector, the assembly forges links between the EU, and national and local levels through regional, spatial and economic planning for the Southern Region. The Southern Regional Assembly interact with a wide variety of the QH actors of Government Departments, agencies, local authorities, and stakeholders from the private and the third sectors at local, regional, national and EU level. Therefore, the Southern Regional Assembly's role in leading the implementation of the Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy's and its objectives to transition to a low carbon economy and to support the National Policy Statement on the bioeconomy will allow for the bringing together of QH actors to achieve this through regional planning and EU projects and programmes. SRA being tasked with assisting in the writing of the Regional Renewable Energy Strategy.

In the case of **Zilina**, a key role in the coordination of the implementation of the bioeconomy strategy is the ŽSK Office and the Regional Development department. The Department of the Environment is believed that should also be involved in the coordination and implementation of the circular

bioeconomy strategy in the region. Currently, there are no working groups among administrative departments involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy as it is coordinated by a single department. However, there is a Bioeconomy Cluster (BEC), which is an association of legal entities founded in December 2015 with the aim of promoting cooperation in the field of innovation and mutual exchange of information between cluster members, who are primarily representatives of the business sphere (companies in the agricultural and food sector), representatives of research, development, and education. representatives of regional and local governments and, last but not least, representatives of the third sector. There is also no bioeconomy strategy council or similar structure overseeing the policy.

There have been no previous co-creation initiatives towards governance models or policies in the region. There are also no civil society organizations or non-governmental organizations involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy. However, there is a growing interest, especially among the young generation, towards co-creation with policymakers.

The common priorities of the actors involved in circular bioeconomy activities is agriculture, as agriculture and rural areas play an important role in development bioeconomy, because agriculture and forestry represent a large part of biomass production. For this reason, there is a need to support investments in production and use of biomass, which at the same time supports natural values and becomes economically attractive for entrepreneurs in the countryside.

There are several integrated development trends within the RIS3 domain "Healthy food and environment". development trends in the sectors of agriculture, forestry, and logging, which were designed based on the identification of areas of common interest of companies and research and development organizations, and which create synergies with the proposed focus investment activities mentioned above. These integrated development trends domains include:

1. Sustainable and competitive primary agricultural and forestry production resources
2. Production of safe, health-supporting foods with high nutritional value and added value value
3. New technologies of mechanical, chemical and energy processing of agricultural and forest biomass into products with high added value
4. Complex technologies and systems for reducing the negative impacts of agriculture activities on the environment, protection and sustainable use of land and water in changing climatic conditions

There are currently no intermediary organizations that operate as bridges/links between clusters and/or sectors. However, there are research and innovation centers within the bioeconomy governance system.

In the case of **Andalusia**, the Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural (Regional Ministry for Agriculture, Fishing, Water and Rural Development) from the Junta de Andalucía (Andalusian Government) is the policy department in the regional administration in charge of implementing the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy that was issued in 2018 by the regional government.

Other policy departments in the region are linked to the bioeconomy field. The Consejería de Sostenibilidad, Medio Ambiente y Economía Azul (Regional Ministry for sustainability, environment, and blue economy) is the one in charge of circular economy issues and has pushed for regulation for a circular economy that has been approved at the regional level recently. Moreover, the Consejería de Política Industrial y Energía (Regional Ministry for industrial policy and energy) would be also related to bioeconomy due to bioenergy production. Aside from regional ministries, there are public agencies whose activity might be related to circular bioeconomy as well. These are Agencia de Gestión Agraria y Pesquera de Andalucía (Agency for farming and fish management),

Agencia Andaluza de la Energía (Andalusian Agency for Energy), and Agencia de Medio Ambiente y Agua (Agency for environment and water).

The Andalusian Bioeconomy Cluster is planned to be developed in the framework of the 2030 strategy (the aim of participating in ROBIN is to further shape, launch, and start the operation of the cluster). There is also the Technological Corporation of Andalusia (ROBIN partner), a multi-sectoral Andalusian cluster of private companies that includes biotechnology among its seven sectors.

In the frame of the BBI-JU funded project “ICT-BIOCHAIN”, a co-creation event was conducted among QH stakeholders to identify the main challenges, needs, and ideas for the development of a Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) devoted to biomass mobilisation through the digitalisation of logistics.

5. The experience in the ICT-BIOCHAIN project was very positive with high participation of QH stakeholders. A summary of the whole experience can be found in “**Digital Innovation Hubs as a Tool for Boosting Biomass Valorisation in Regional Bioeconomies: Andalusian and South-East Irish Case Studies**” [32].

From the academia side, The Agrifood Campus of International Excellence comprising the universities of Jaén, Córdoba, Huelva, Cádiz, and Almería has projects in the field of the valorisation of agriculture by-products, biorefineries, and algae (e.g., the FP7 MIRACLE project - a multi-product integrated algae refinery). Other important institutions for academic training relevant to Bioeconomy are the Andalusian Institute for Research and Training in Agriculture, Fisheries, Foods and Organic Production (whose Spanish acronym is IFAPA, a ROBIN project partner) and the Spanish National Research Council (whose Spanish acronym is CSIC). There are also other research centres such as ANDALTEC (Plastic Technological Centre), TECNOVA (Research Centre related to agribusiness) and CETAQUA (Water Technology Centre).

From the consumers’ side, there is the Andalusian Union of Consumers.

From the private sector side and from a value chain perspective, due to Andalusia’s strong feedstock position, these are the different feedstocks for which Andalusia has a strong position at European level:

- Horticulture and agri-food
- Olive sector
- Forestry
- Livestock farming
- Algae (using CO₂ and nutrients from industry as feedstock)

The main leadership role is from the Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural (Regional Ministry for agriculture, fishing, water, and rural development), ROBIN partner.

Civil society organizations and /or non-governmental organizations involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy include the Andalusian Union of Consumers. Also, Cooperativas Agroalimentarias de Andalucía is an Association of Andalusian farmers cooperatives. Another association is ASAJA (Andalusian association of young farmers). Moreover, there are Rural Development Groups all over the region such as GDR Los Pedroches.

The ACBS is structured in four strategic lines. The first two respond to strategic objective 1 and the other two respond to strategic objectives 2 and 3, respectively:

- ·Strategic line 1. Sustainable generation and availability of biomass resources
- ·Strategic line 2. Infrastructures and logistics management
- ·Strategic line 3. Industrial processes for the transformation of biomass resources and industrial production capacity of bioproducts and bioenergy
- ·Strategic Line 4. Market development for bioproducts and bioenergy

The role of public authorities in bringing together the QH actors is to coordinate, promote, encourage, and communicate in the process of implementing the circular bioeconomy governance model. Designing accompanying measures for the development of the bioeconomy.

In Andalusia, there is no research centre specifically devoted to bioeconomy or circular bioeconomy as such. However, there is many technology, research, and innovation centres that focus their activities in one of the areas related to bioeconomy.

4.5 The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs)

In the case of **Baden-Wuerttemberg**, the political mandate is the regional and local implementation of the bioeconomy within the Baden-Wuerttemberg's territory. The scope of the strategy is wide, covering rural, urban, and industrial areas. The rural part is covered with measures proposed by the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection, and the ones related with urban and industrial areas are proposed by the Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy Sector.

The monitoring, evaluation and/or use of indicators for the implemented strategy is not detailed in public documents. It is known that the Sustainable Bioeconomy Council is consulted periodically for opinion in some measures and strategic decisions to take. The update of the strategy is expected by end of 2024 and an evaluation is expected till then. The implementation of the strategy has recently assured its continuation after 2024 [33].

A study was funded between 2017/2018 and co-led by the University of Stuttgart and IFEU Heidelberg to develop a concept for a Bioeconomy Development Index. The study was discussed with multiple stakeholders from Baden-Wuerttemberg during the dialogue process (*Plan B*), as well as in a second event organized by the Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy Sector. For the index, 18 key indicators and 9 dimensions were identified. The indicators were selected in basis of an integral sustainability perspective: the UN Sustainability Goals were considered, as well as the Bioeconomy Research Programme in Baden-Wuerttemberg and the German politic strategy in bioeconomy. Recommendations for action for the creation of a monitoring program were finally set [34], [35]. It is not known to which degree these recommendations were considered in the design and implementation of the regional bioeconomy strategy.

In the case of **Central Macedonia**, European funding programmes are the main financial instrument available for the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy. There are currently action plans per sector, i.e., for the environmental and agricultural sectors. However, there are no data publicly available for monitoring actions (including KPIs, deadlines, and no follow-up or evaluation procedures data). The economy-related indicators that are used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy are: Target points, business process, monitoring results and investigation of Deviations. The economy-related indicators that are used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy are: GDP, personnel occupied, wellbeing of Population, employment rate, health status. The environmental indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy are: Gas emissions, Energy produced and Amount of waste recycled and / or reused.

In the case of the **Southern region**, as there is no regional bioeconomy strategy for the Southern Region, The Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy 2022-2023 is Ireland's first national circular economy strategy. The Strategy is a key addition to Government's drive to achieve a 51% reduction in overall greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and to get on a path to reach net-zero emissions by no later than 2050, as per commitments in the Programme for Government [36] and the Climate Act 2021. [37].

The Climate Action Plan 2021 [38] sets out almost 500 actions to support Ireland's journey towards a 51% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and carbon neutrality by 2050. In relation to the bioeconomy, the plan sets out targets such as that opportunities to expand both skills and funding mechanisms will be explored.

As there is no regional bioeconomy strategy in the Southern region, there is a National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy [39], a Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy [40] and regionally there is a Regional, Spatial and Economic Strategy for the Southern Region [41] which has specific Regional Policy Objectives (RPO) relating to the bioeconomy and circular economy in the region and its implementation and promotion. For the RSES, The Regional Development Monitor (RDM) which the Southern Regional Assembly was involved in developing, is to be launched shortly and will be entirely focussed on Indicators. Also, the RSES Implementation Programme and RSES Two Year Monitoring report can be used for identifying indicators.

As Denmark are leading the way in a grass/clover-based bioeconomy there is a link there for Ireland and the Southern Region to emulate a Danish model. The Danish landscape, similar to Ireland and the Southern Region, is dominated by agriculture. The Danish case is an important example of how environmental sustainability has been addressed in an intensively managed country with a high proportion of agricultural land. The Central Denmark Region is home to a unique cluster of knowledge and industry targeting effective production, logistics and conversion of bio-resources to high-value bio-based products.

Nationally, there are similarities with Scotland and there has been collaboration - similar population, and similar primary sectors, industries and residues (grass, tillage, brewing/distillery wastes, dairy wastes, slurries, meat by-products etc.). Initiatives such as Zero Waste Scotland [42], IBioIC [43], Circular North East [44] etc.) would be put forward as front runners in the bioeconomy to emulate.

In the case of **Zilina**, the financial instruments have 40 Mio euros from public funds through at least 2 interventions: 1) Investments - in the amount of 35 Mio euros, of which:

- a. investments in innovative technologies in the field of bioeconomy in the amount of 20 Mio euros,
- b. investments in renewable sources, especially in local energy sources in the amount of 15 Mio euros.

2) Cooperation - in the amount of 5 Mio euros through created operational

groups in the field of bioeconomy (within pilot projects, local cooperation, or relevant short supply chains).

Small projects will be supported under the LEADER initiative. Such projects will make it possible to support the competitiveness and sustainable development of industries, including improvement of environmental protection procedures at the local level.

There is a Draft National Action Plan for Development bioeconomy in the Slovak Republic with the aim of supporting the development of the "green economy" in the future planning period from 2020. It follows from consultations with national and international experts that the green economy sector has a significant development potential and may within a decade to reach the turnover of the

automotive industry, while it will use domestic resources. The national action plan for the development of bioeconomy in Slovakia defines three main areas bioeconomy, namely:

- Efficient agriculture
- Efficient forestry
- Waste Management

Every year there is an evaluation of the implementation of the social and economic development plan of the Žilina Region (PHSR ŽSK) and the Action Plan of the ŽSK Office for the previous year. Filling of specific goals is evaluated using the indicator system report and published in the PHSR Implementation Report ŽSK. Subsequently, proposals for modifying the Action Plan of the ŽSK Office are collected so that they can be approved By the representative office of ŽSK. The first evaluation Report on the implementation of the PHSR ŽSK 2021+ will be prepared for the year 2023, i.e. in 2024.

The report on the implementation of the PHSR ŽSK 2021+ processed once a year must contain the following information:

- Main part – Manager's summary of the implementation of PHSR ŽSK 2021+ and the Action Plan of the Office of ŽSK (overall summary implementation of the PHSR ŽSK 2021+ in the previous period with an indication of the main findings);
- Proposals of key measures for the following year;
- Appendix – Data update and comments on filling in indicators.

Regarding the indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy, the most relevant outcome indicator based on interventions for the field of bioeconomy is the indicator of Rural Development bioeconomy: number of supported enterprises operating in bioeconomy. This indicator will be used for monitoring and evaluation of the benefits of bioeconomy support. Societal indicators include: creation of thematic and cross-sectoral excellent teams from among researchers (from various organizations) and the business sphere in order to implement results more effectively research and innovation into practice, Incentive measures in the field of research and innovation, tax policy, the availability of qualified labor and specifically measures at the national and regional level, including the state level policy e.g. structure and amount of local taxes, mobility support and participation in international projects.

In the case of **Andalusia**, the ACBS will have the financial resources needed to develop the actions proposed. The different administrative centres and Instrumental bodies that have been involved in the design, drafting, and definition of the Strategy will provide their own funds and they will be also responsible for the future implementation of the actions.

On the one hand, the ACBS has an associated action plan which has not yet been implemented, but the following actions have been foreseen in the strategy.

STRATEGIC LINE (SL) 1: SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION AND AVAILABILITY OF BIOMASS RESOURCES.

ACTIONS:

- To identify and quantify the biomass resources by sectors and sub-sectors to achieve their comprehensive use and identify their possible uses.
- To establish and developing the methodology to introduce indicators on the biomass resources and the industrial areas producing CO2 in the statistical Andalusian planning.

- To stimulate and reinforcing sustainability practices and better technical alternatives (equipment and machinery) to obtain, recover and use biomass resources.
- To promote the evaluation of sustainability in the stage of biomass resources generation.
- To establish and develop the methodology to create and inventory and georeferencing the potential users of biomass resources concerning the territorial distribution of resources.

SL 2: INFRASTRUCTURES AND LOGISTIC MANAGEMENT

ACTIONS:

- To identify and promote the best collecting or supply, storage, pre-treatment and use technologies for biomass resources based on efficiency and profitability criteria for the bioproducts or bioenergy value chain.
- To design an investment plan to support, improve and disseminate the existing logistical infrastructures bearing in mind the importance of their location in rural areas.
- To promote the establishment of new centres to prepare and collect biomass resources adapted to the conditions of every area to facilitate their management.

SL 3: INDUSTRIAL BIOMASS PROCESSING PROCESSES AND BIOPRODUCTS AND BIOENERGY INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION CAPACITY

ACTIONS

- To analyse the state of the art of preparation (previous treatments) and processing technologies (conversion technologies) of biomass resources into bioproducts and bioenergy.
- To promote sustainability in the use of biomass resources according to eco-innovation and eco-efficiency criteria: cascade use, circular economy, use of the industrial CO₂, pre-treatment and processing processes in areas near production facilities.
- To develop programmes of structured industrial symbiosis and/or innovative collaborations between companies and industries to create new models to use biomass resource flows and industrial CO₂ resources.
- To stimulate the conduction of feasibility studies (economic, social, and environmental) and business models during the planning and implementation stages of bioindustries and biorefineries, mainly in rural areas.
- To promote the settlement of bioindustries and biorefineries in Andalusia to support the already existing ones and promote the conversion of the biodiesel industry into integrated biorefineries.

SL 4: MARKET DEVELOPMENT FOR BIOPRODUCTS AND BIOENERGY.

ACTIONS:

- To support the undertaking of market studies, business plans, and feasibility studies of bioproducts, bioenergy, and services linked to the circular bioeconomy and monitoring the bioproducts and bioenergy value chains.
- To draft market studies on consumer trends and new uses of bioproducts and bioenergy, as well as a portfolio of their potential consuming areas and/or sectors.
- To promote the marketing and use of bioproducts, bioenergy, and services linked to the circular bioeconomy and create marks for their differentiation in the market.
- To encourage cultural business change needed to appreciate the services offered by the circular bioeconomy to improve sustainability, stimulate the analyses of the life cycle, and calculate the environmental footprints of bioproducts and bioenergy.

PROGRAMME A: SOCIETY COMMUNICATION AND AWARENESS-RAISING ON THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY.

ACTIONS.

- To design and launch a communication plan to develop activities on circular bioeconomy that will include a specific website, fairs, seminars, workshops, meetings, advertising campaigns, and forums, as well as a visibility plan for social networks.
- To design and launch promotion and advertising campaigns (marketing) of bioproducts, bioenergy, services, and processes related to the circular bioeconomy by promoting their marks.

PROGRAMME B: PROMOTING R&D+I+T FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND EXPANSION OF THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY IN ANDALUSIA.

ACTIONS.

- To identify and disseminate the research, innovation, and technological development needs.
- To promote research for the development of bioproducts and bioenergy and the instruments to support innovation and the generation of intellectual and industrial property in their areas, especially through the public procurement of innovative solutions and incubators and social shuttles to encourage entrepreneurship.
- To promote the analysis of by-product valorisation systems from an economic perspective, including valuation of benefits for society, research on the adoption of innovations, and analysis of policy instruments to promote the development of the circular bioeconomy, among others.
- To stimulate the creation of a catalogue of good practices and a portfolio of successful projects, technological innovations, and business ideas for each of the links of the value chains related to the circular bioeconomy.
- To design tools to favour the technology transfer between the different stakeholders in the field of the circular bioeconomy.
- To plan activities and services to promote the transfer of knowledge in the field of the circular bioeconomy (workshops on technological transfer, business missions, sector-based committees, awareness-raising events in aspects related to this matter, advisory services, and mentoring ...)
- To promote the participation of the knowledge agents, research and innovation groups, and businesses in the RDI programmes of the EU and industrial projects, networks, and other events.
- To stimulate the creation of a Focus Group in the field of research related to the circular bioeconomy.
- To introduce the circular bioeconomy and/or its areas of knowledge in the curricular content of compulsory education, vocational training, university relevant qualifications as well as in the training courses for the professionals working on sectors related to it.
- To analyse the state of the art of the Master's education in subjects related to the circular bioeconomy and stimulate the establishment of a specialization Master in circular bioeconomy.

PROGRAMME C: FUNDING ACCESS TO FACILITATE THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY IN ANDALUSIA.

ACTIONS.

- To stimulate a guidance service to analyse, give advice, and communicate the financial instruments available for the circular bioeconomy.

- To stimulate new forms of public support and access to financing for the development and implementation of projects and business ideas in circular bioeconomy, including alternative collaborative funding sources and new public-private financial instruments, as well as the public procurement of innovative solutions.
- To promote initiatives to disseminate the competitive advantages of Andalusia and its experience in diverse sectors as factors of interest to favour foreign investment in projects and business ideas linked to the circular bioeconomy.
- To promote the connection of circular bioeconomy projects and companies with investors' networks or business angels to extend the funding alternatives at national and international levels.

PROGRAMME D: PROMOTING THE COOPERATION, COORDINATION AND MONITORING OF THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY

ACTIONS

- To stimulate the Andalusian Cluster for Circular Bioeconomy.
- To create and implement the Andalusian Observatory for Circular Bioeconomy.
- To identify regulatory areas that could be a barrier or an opportunity for the development of the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia.
- To create an Interdepartmental Commission to promote and monitor the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia.
- To create the Monitoring Committee and the Technical Office for the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy.
- To design the panel of specific indicators to monitor and evaluate the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy and keep it updated.
- To elaborate reports on the situation, monitoring and evaluation of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, and organising specific work groups in matters of particular relevance.

In the ACBS, the associated action plan has not yet been developed, so the follow-up and evaluation procedure has not yet been established.

The ACBS is in the process of being implemented with a framework until 2030. Some economy-, society- and environmental-related indicators used to assess the territorial impact of the circular bioeconomy strategy could be employment generated by the bioeconomy, value-added generated by the bioeconomy, increase in the number of bioindustries, increase in the number of biorefineries, impact of bioeconomy contents in social networks, the impact of bioeconomy contents on websites, domestic consumption of bioproducts and bioenergy, holding of conferences and training activities, the production and consumption of bioenergy in Andalusia, the percentage of valorised residues in the agri-food sector, etc.

ACBS considers:

- European Bioeconomy Strategy and its Action Plan.
- Spanish Bioeconomy Strategy-2030 Horizon.
- Green Deal.
- Farm to Fork strategy.
- The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development with 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In Spain, regions such as Catalanian and Castilla y Leon have strategies dedicated to bioeconomy and mainly in sectors like agriculture and agroindustries. Their actions are of interest to Andalusia.

Flanders (Belgium) stands out as one of the first regions in Europe in adopting a regional bioeconomy strategy in 2013. Andalusia has made an in-depth study of the following regions: Baden-Wuerttemberg (Germany), Pays de la Loire (France), Flanders (Belgium) and Mazovia (Poland) comparing diverse aspects of their policies.

The ACBS is based on political priorities already undertaken by the Andalusian government, such as moving towards a competitive economy based on biological processes, which respect the good use of natural resources, their maintenance, and efficient use. The elaboration of the ACBS included a participatory approach of all actors in the value chain of the different sectors. This way, the best measures and programmes linked to the development of the bioeconomy in Andalusia could be addressed.

Since the Statute of Autonomy for Andalusia came into force, among the competencies held by the Autonomous Community concerning agriculture, livestock production, fishing, agro forestry uses, rural development, and quality schemes, the region has developed competencies that help to achieve the goals set by the ACBS. Some of them are the development of the agricultural, livestock production, fishing, and food-processing sectors, the regulation of the agricultural production processes, organic farming, food sufficiency, the development of technological innovations, rural development, sustainable development, and the promotion of the production and use of biomass. All these competencies must continue to be developed in the future by applying the criteria adopted and raised by the Andalusian Strategy.

The experience gained by Andalusia after being selected by the European Commission as a model demonstrator region to lead the way towards the chemical sustainable production in Europe constitutes another opportunity for the circular bioeconomy in our region. Thanks to this project, Andalusia has received the advisory and technical support of the European Sustainable Chemicals Support Service. It has enabled it to define this new concept of industry and help generate new investment and employment opportunities to bring wealth and make progress in the achievement of a circular economy, the aim of zero residues and the reduction of pollutant emissions. At the same time, the project has strengthened the intersectoral relations between the chemical industries and those involved in the processes that produce the raw material.

All these opportunities take advantage and, simultaneously, underpin the ACBS.

5. Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy in the ROBIN regions

In the case of **Baden-Wuerttemberg**, a SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats) was performed, as part of an extensive assessment of the current research landscape in the region, relevant to bioeconomy. Three research topics were to be funded:

- **Biogas**, that showed potential for the short-term implementation of innovations; this field has a high scientific know-how along all the value chain, is well established and there is general interest for its further progress.
- **Lignocellulose**, that is characterized by many outstanding individual competencies that come with a wide range of know-how that can contribute to further development. This field of research shows a more medium-term implementation character. The perception of the potential of this research field is still not very pronounced in the associated industries and intensive networking is needed.
- **Algae** was selected by the group of experts as the subject area with the longest-term perspective while having the greatest potential for innovation. There is already a high level of scientific competence in Baden-Wuerttemberg along the entire value chain, however coupled with a great need for action (biorefinery). Since it only marginally found its way into the economy, it is the field of research with the greatest need for development.

The SWOT analysis was based on three pillars: i) raw materials from supply side (agri-, wood-based, aquatic, bio-waste, and by-products); ii) products and valorization from demand side (food use, material use, energetic use); and iii) cross-cutting areas covering ecological, societal, ethical, and economic aspects. Since the exercise was done in 2013, no further SWOT related to the bioeconomy strategy and related policies has been published.

A correlation between the identified research fields identified in the SWOT and its transposition in the text of the current regional bioeconomy strategy is found. E.g., measure 16 of the regional bioeconomy strategy (“Further development of the biogas plant inventory”) will develop a concept for the future-oriented, economically efficient, and environmentally friendly expansion of the existing biogas plants (around 1,000 agricultural ones) following the expiry of the guaranteed EEG (*Erneubare Energien Gesetz*) bonuses. The bonus was related to a 20-years long warranty. The measure 14 (“Pilot/demonstration facilities”) is related to the comprehensive processing of biological resources into innovative products, including lignocellulosic crops, side streams and residual materials along the agricultural and forestry value chains. The facilities will be decentralized and in form of modular biorefineries in rural areas. Finally, the measure 18 (also called “Pilot/demonstration facilities”) is related, among others, with substance synthesis and CO₂ recycling via smart fermentation and biocatalysts with microalgae, bacteria, and fungi. The establishment of bio factories as living labs and pilot facilities will serve for the purpose of a bioeconomy in urban and industrial areas.

In the case of **Central Macedonia**, the following table (Table 31) presents the results of the SWOT analysis.

Table 31: SWOT analysis for the circular bioeconomy policy in Central Macedonia, Greece

<h2>Strengths</h2>	<p>There are services from both the government & public sector to continuously increase the knowledge of Circular Bioeconomy</p> <p>There are management systems to enhance knowledge & implementation to increase e.g., recycling</p> <p>Good presence of consulting engineering companies</p> <p>Significant development of waste-to-energy plants e.g., bio-gas plant</p>
<h2>Weaknesses</h2>	<p>Lack of obligatory systems & mechanisms for monitoring, reviewing & evaluating the results of small enterprises that can improve their productivity. Farmers' attitude focuses on their compensations and not to increase their knowledge of their agriculture management.</p> <p>Over consolidated use of several plants resulting to exclusion of others.</p>
<h2>Opportunities</h2>	<p>There is available European funding to help farmers and industries to incorporate and implement new systems/techniques/processes.</p> <p>There is governmental funding. Opening of the market could develop new intra- European trade & business opportunities</p>
<h2>Threats</h2>	<p>Livelihood and daily life problems ate the main concern of the entrepreneurs (farmers, plant owners) than the integration of new technologies & Circular Bioeconomy approaches.</p>

Concrete and specific tools that can be developed in the region to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices from the circular bioeconomy include: A Guide of Best Practice Tools could be developed by public Agencies such as Region of Central Macedonia to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices from circular bioeconomy in priority sectors/value chains in the region as well as Seminars/workshops. Finally, an important lesson learnt from the circular bioeconomy policy so far is that the circular bioeconomy has the potential to minimize the environmental impacts of biomass while simultaneously generating value added bioproducts & bio energy. The societal effect is of great significance and reflects directly to all stakeholders.

In the case of the **Southern region**, the following table (Table 32) presents the results of the SWOT analysis.

Table 32: SWOT analysis for the circular bioeconomy policy in the Southern region, Ireland

<h2>Strengths</h2>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong agri-food sector and availability of Feedstocks <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Agricultural / Marine / Industry side stream • Promising bio-based products emerging <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ More value-added products • Strong Bioeconomy Education & Research sector – MTU, UCC etc • Existing Bio-based industries – Bioatlantis, Nutramara etc
<h2>Weaknesses</h2>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Often the capital expenditure, and lack of scale-up facilities along with the long route to market for some processes and products are prohibitive for companies. • In addition, further work is required to engage suppliers of biomass, and end users, on the potential benefits of the bioeconomy to ensure their participation. • Investment is needed in key Bioeconomy infrastructure particularly new biorefinery infrastructure. • Stakeholders are often operating in silos • Policy constraints • Need for policy development / review in relation to circular bioeconomy
<h2>Opportunities</h2>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rising Costs of synthetic farm inputs e.g.: Fertilisers, proteins, with bio-based alternatives coming to market. • Opportunity to reduce import dependence as Ireland is currently dependent on imported energy, chemicals, plastics, fertilisers, feed and more. • Complete valorisation of existing feedstocks, pushing value up the 'bio-based value pyramid' - Marine Sector – extracting inputs for pharmaceutical sector. • Creating a just transition for agriculture and revitalizing rural and coastal regions with new companies and jobs. • Developing a circular bioeconomy based on sustainable supply chains can aid in the reduction of GHG emissions and help to meet climate targets.
<h2>Threats</h2>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of investment capital for pilot and demonstration level initiatives • Ensuring adequate skills exist to meet the emerging needs • Ensuring that members/stakeholders involved and impacted by the bioeconomy (e.g. public, consumers, farmers) are fully engaged

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ensuring that the biomass is managed and harvested sustainably and the trade-offs of developing a bioeconomy are fully considered • Lack of support for companies innovating and scaling in this space • Lack of support in connecting and support the various actors in their collaborations
--	---

Concrete and specific tools that can be developed in the region to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices from the circular bioeconomy have not yet been developed as there is yet no regional circular bioeconomy strategy. A key action within the Climate Action Plan is supporting regional assemblies in understanding areas of potential growth in the bioeconomy. There are several potential tools which could be used to support this activity. Firstly, understanding the potential of biomass from various sectors, and understanding how this may be used. Several projects including INFORMBIO, MainstreamBIO, Be-Rural, Power4Bio can help inform this work and approaches for mapping of feedstocks, technologies and business cases for developing regional bioeconomies. Peer-learning activities and exchanges of best practices through international and interregional site visits, learning and networking events, can also support in build capacity in regions, examples of this activity can be found in projects like COOPID and Power4Bio. Several opportunities exist to develop identified opportunities, first at lower technology readiness levels (TRL) through established research centres, and later scaling these through pilot and demonstration activities with regional R&D and industry partners. However, supported in infrastructure and investment for scale-up is key. In Europe, the Public-Private-Partnership model of the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (now CBE JU) has played a key role in supporting bioeconomy scale up. Setting appropriate policy, including measurable targets is also of key importance. The important role of clusters in connecting the various value chain stakeholders in the region is already being seen in the Southern Region.

In the case of **Zilina**, the following table (Table 33) presents the results of the SWOT analysis.

Table 33: SWOT analysis for the circular bioeconomy policy in Zilina, Slovakia

Strengths	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • significant production potential of the region in forest land and water resources (historically, geographically, in terms of climatic conditions), • structure and character of agricultural enterprises - concentrated agricultural production, • the multifunctional nature of the forestry that it provides amount of biomass, biomaterials, bioproducts and fillings important ecological functions, inclusion of the majority of forests in the economic category forests with a primary wood production function
Weaknesses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • frequent calamities and the resulting high volume accidental logging inefficient use of biomass (including waste) as raw material

	<p>for further processing the unclear position of agriculture within the national priorities,</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the absence of a regional strategy for the bioeconomy, • inconsistency and fragmentation of policies relevant to the area bioeconomy and the ambiguity of its position and role in development policies, • inconsistency of methodologies for policy making in the area bioeconomy, • lack and unavailability of data for creating a strategy for bioeconomy and its subsequent monitoring and evaluation
<h2>Opportunities</h2>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • development of business activities in the countryside and creation of new ones value chains within the circular bioeconomy obtaining and processing biomass, waste economy, wood processing, etc., • growing demand for biomass causing the need to increase production by increasing yields per hectare (limited options increase in cultivation areas) while simultaneously taking into account environmental criteria and requirements for the protection of life environment, • increasing the contribution of the forestry and timber sector to the green sector of the economy within its potential for increasing employment, • efficient use of resources, mitigating climate change, production of renewable energy, low-carbon economy, • strengthening advice on topics in the field of bioeconomy, • increase in the share of domestic production with higher added value value and with a higher form of processing by use biotechnologies and innovative technologies, • use of digitization and innovative technologies
<h2>Threats</h2>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • bioeconomy solutions will not be from an economic point of view more effective compared to fossil-based products, • competitive use of land for the production of food and fodder for animals and for the production of renewable resources for material use and for energy use, • access to wood raw material – increased competition for wood as a raw material, especially due to the growing demand for renewable energy • departure of executive scientists due to lack of continuity of funding

Measures and tools that can be developed in the region to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices include cooperation with international excellent workplaces and competence centres, support the development of clusters and associations in the bioeconomy as driving mechanisms to support cooperation to change the social paradigm through a strong European support in the area of using wood as ecological, renewable and recyclable raw material, permanently active sustainable forest management, and efficient use of domestic sources of wood raw material.

The lessons learnt from the circular bioeconomy policy so far are that:

- using the creativity and imagination of the public in the creation of policies is important,
- projects, innovations, and solutions both every day and social problems in the field of bioeconomy,
- support of bioeconomy through social networks and involving the public (including young people) in discussions,
- education of farmers in the field of sustainable, low-carbon and circular bioeconomy,
- development of new educational programs and scientific fields related to the bioeconomy (e.g., in the field of biotechnology).

In the case of **Andalusia**, the following table (Table 34) presents the results of the SWOT analysis.

Table 34: SWOT analysis for the circular bioeconomy policy in Andalusia, Spain

<p style="font-size: 24pt; font-weight: bold; color: white;">Strengths</p>	<p><u>Generation and availability of biomass resources</u></p> <p>Great production capacity of biomass resources from agriculture, livestock production, agri-food, forest and fishing sectors.</p> <p>Availability of other flows of biomass resources of interest that can be recovered such as sludge from sewage systems and biowaste produced at local level.</p> <p>Progressive optimization in the management of biomass resources generated by the agricultural and agri-food sectors due to the extensive experience that exists concerning its bioenergetic use.</p> <p>Important concentration of biomass resources with potential use in certain areas.</p> <p>Development of algal production experiences to make the most of CO₂.</p>
	<p><u>Infrastructures and logistics management of biomass resources</u></p> <p>An important concentration of biomass resources in certain areas of the region, a fact that facilitates the logistics of their management.</p> <p>Existence of storage facilities and collection centres for biomass resources in certain productive sectors.</p>

	<p>Availability of logistic infrastructures for certain biomass resources that can be used in other value chains.</p> <p>Existence of biomass transport companies that might deliver to new bio-based industries or biorefineries.</p> <p>Use of the logistic development associated with the bioenergy sector in other value chains of bioproducts derived from the expansion of the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p><u>Industrial processing of biomass resources and capacity of industrial production of bioproducts and bioenergy</u></p> <p>Important agro-industrial business fabric with the capacity to participate in bio-based processes that also have experience in certain technological developments aimed at the efficient use of resources.</p> <p>Continuous development of bioenergy; a fact that has led to the creation of a business fabric that uses biomass for thermal and electrical use and for the production of biofuels.</p> <p>The existence of chemical clusters made up of a diversity of companies that could host new others linked to the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Experience in circular bioeconomy resulting from its selection as a model demonstrator region for sustainable chemistry.</p> <p>Existence of a biotechnological ecosystem that favours the transformation and recovery of the biomass resources of Andalusia.</p> <p><u>Development of markets for bioproducts and bioenergy.</u></p> <p>Existence of a consolidated market for biofuels.</p> <p>The existence of a demand already established for particular bioproducts (plant debris for composting or manure for organic amendments) can boost the demand for bioproducts.</p> <p>Experience of Andalusia in the sustainable chemistry sector, both concerning the bioproducts that can be obtained and their current and/or potential markets, as it has been selected as a demonstrator region.</p> <p>Active involvement of Andalusia in the Bio-Based Industries Consortium (BIC).</p> <p><u>Communication.</u></p> <p>Initiatives related to the circular bioeconomy and publicly known by society; a fact that can be an</p>
--	--

advantage in order to make society aware of its advantages and importance.

Enough information on the potential biomass available in Andalusia.

Bioeconomy cases of success can be showcased to society as an example of the advantages of the circular bioeconomy.

R&D+Innovation and Training.

Adaptation of the Andalusian scientific production to the European priorities proposed for industrial matters; some of them directly related to the circular bioeconomy.

Involvement of Andalusia in international projects related to the circular bioeconomy.

Experience of the Andalusian International Campuses of Excellence (CeIA3 and Andalusia TECH), and of research and technology transfer groups in the sectors of interest for the circular bioeconomy.

Knowledge, experience, human capital, technological capacity and dimension in innovation areas related to the circular bioeconomy, as well as in leading companies.

Critical mass of scientific-technical staff in the field of the circular bioeconomy.

Network of research and training centres and infrastructures on agriculture and agri-food processing as well as technological parks related to sectors with a great potential for the circular bioeconomy.

Presence of important driving poles for productive innovation with implications in circular bioeconomy (agri-food industry, chemical sector, renewable energies).

Promotion of research oriented to the bioeconomy as a priority defined in the Andalusian Innovation Strategy 2020, RIS3 Andalusia, through projects of excellence.

Support policies and funding.

Possibility of submitting applications for funding to the calls of the Joint Undertaking for Bio-Based Industries and those launched by the Social Challenge 2 that falls under H2020 for projects related to research, technological development and innovation in the field of the circular bioeconomy.

Availability of budget on the structural funds (principally ERDF and EAFRD) and European

	<p>investment funds to fund actions to stimulate and promote the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Possibility of funding projects through the Spanish Ministry for Economy and Business (CDTI, INIA...).</p> <p>Existence of cross-cutting policies of the Regional Government of Andalusia that promote and support the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p><u>Inter-administrative cooperation and coordination.</u></p> <p>Development of new relations and collaboration methods and formulas for the development of innovative projects between the institutions and the companies associated with the circular bioeconomy of Andalusia.</p> <p>Possible synergies between the sectors involved (suppliers, transformers and users of residues and bioproducts) in the region.</p> <p>Progressive dissemination of the new model represented by the circular bioeconomy in the different centres of the Regional Ministries of Andalusia.</p> <p>Development of policy and planning tools related to circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Political commitment in all the areas to the bioeconomy and the circular economy, which favours the organisation of events and forums where contacts are established.</p>
<h2>Weaknesses</h2>	<p><u>Generation and availability of biomass resources.</u></p> <p>Limited knowledge on the characteristics of a great variety of biomass resources with potential as raw material for the production of innovative bioproducts.</p> <p>Deficient management of the by-products derived from livestock production.</p> <p>Insufficient management of forest resources.</p> <p>Ignorance of the balance between the potential demand of alternative raw materials to biomass and the availability of the latter.</p> <p><u>Infrastructures and logistics management of biomass resources.</u></p> <p>Seasonal variation of biomass resources and inappropriate collection infrastructures.</p> <p>Existence of logistic centres optimized for a certain value chain owned by their stakeholders.</p> <p><u>Industrial processing of biomass resources and capacity of industrial production of bioproducts and bioenergy.</u></p>

Lack of technological developments specifically adapted to every type of biological resource and industrial process.

Little development of the integrated biorefineries and bio-based industries.

Development of markets for bioproducts and bioenergy.

Limited knowledge on alternative uses of different raw materials and their introduction in alternative value chains in the field of circular bioeconomy.

Lack of detailed analyses concerning the potential applications of by-products and the available waste of biological origin and companies potentially interested in them.

Lack of innovation business culture to face the technological adaptation to new products and manufacturing processes.

Reduced number of medium-large companies that will allow the development of business projects in the medium-long term.

Lack of a clear and recognized regulation of the products of biological origin.

Communication.

Unawareness of what the circular bioeconomy is and what it represents by great part of society.

Weaknesses in the promotion of the products and services that shape the Andalusian productive system and among them, those derived from activities associated with the circular bioeconomy.

R&D+Innovation and Training.

Poor links between scientific production and the market. Lack of patents and real applications of the research on circular bioeconomy.

Difficulty in the definition of strategies related to the circular bioeconomy in the medium-long term successive research programmes according to a complete alignment with the national and European R&D+i policies.

Lack of information, training and skills, networking, cooperation, etc. in circular bioeconomy, in order to produce new innovative actions.

Poor number of spin-off or start-up companies based on the knowledge on circular bioeconomy compared to the size of the Andalusian system.

Insufficient adjustment of the training offer to the needs and specificities of the professional staff working in the agricultural, food- processing,

	<p>environmental, forest and fishing sectors related to the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Lack of joint initiatives between the R&D+i system and the sectors associated with the circular bioeconomy, especially, in relation with the real needs of the above-mentioned sectors.</p> <p><u>Support policies and funding.</u></p> <p>Poor flexibility of the funding instruments existing for Technology-based Businesses (TBB) that do not bear in mind the life cycle of business projects as a whole.</p> <p>Difficulty to fund comprehensive projects due to the incompatibility between funds (divided by competences).</p> <p><u>Inter-administrative cooperation and coordination.</u></p> <p>Unawareness of what the circular bioeconomy implies for certain business areas and the public sector.</p> <p>Lack of facilitating schemes to create alliances between companies, sectors and research bodies in the field of the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Lack of a single resource that gathers the whole regulation and funding opportunities related to the different raw materials, products and processes associated with the circular bioeconomy.</p> <p>Rigid governing models in Public R&D+i Institutions that hinder the development of the circular bioeconomy.</p>
<p>Opportunities</p>	<p><u>Generation and availability of biomass resources.</u></p> <p>Possibility of increasing the competitiveness of the primary and secondary sectors through the development of new bioproducts.</p> <p>Excellent regional weather conditions for the production of biomass.</p> <p>Existence of a biotechnological environment adapted to favour the use of the biomass resources generated.</p> <p>Increase of the volume of residues in dumps.</p> <p>Existence of new management methods for solid urban biowaste.</p> <p>Advantages of the transformation of by- products and waste into resources concerning the saving of greenhouse gases, a guarantee of the sustainable development and contribution to the mitigation of climate change.</p>

Normative changes in the European and/or national legislation in order to favour, stimulate and even force to achieve the full re-use of by-products in the production lines.

Infrastructures and logistics management of biomass resources.

Important transport infrastructure network (roads, railroads, ports).

Possibility of using the logistic centres already existing in mature value chains, in new ones.

The possibility of improving and computerizing the logistic operations by means of the use of ICT.

Industrial processing of biomass resources and capacity of industrial production of bioproducts and bioenergy.

Great potential for the implementation of the use of biomass by applying biorefinery concepts in diverse Andalusian sectors (olive growing, fruits and vegetables...).

Development of bioindustries and biorefineries on a small scale in the Andalusian rural areas.

Possible transformation and/or remodelling of biodiesel production plants into biorefineries.

Growing interest in the use of resources of biological origin and the circular economy by part of the European industry.

Existence of support policies for entrepreneurs and the consolidation of innovative companies.

Existence of technologies for the production and use of biogas from biomass resources.

Increase of the bioenergy demand.

Development of markets for bioproducts and bioenergy.

Existence of a consolidated activity in fields directly linked with new models of sustainable development (renewable energies, healthy food, etc.).

Growing social demand of sustainable products that can lead to the development and expansion of circular bioeconomy.

Importance of sectors such as organic farming, integrated production, animal feed, etc. For potential bioproducts' consumers.

Potential for the production of fertilizers and other products of major added value from biomass resources (sludge from swage systems, biowaste produced at local level).

Incorporation of criteria to stimulate the circular bioeconomy in the Public procurement of Innovative solutions.

Existence of the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU) whose purpose is to support the establishment of circular bioeconomy industries and value chains.

Communication.

Existence of entities that create synergies and of social communication networks on science that can disseminate the advantages offered by circular bioeconomy to society.

R&D+Innovation and Training.

Network of scientific-technological infrastructures that generate important environments of opportunities in the region.

Consolidation of the programme to support research groups that will contribute to the organisation of the research and development work developed by universities and other R&D+i centres of Andalusia.

Experience in the participation and leadership of European R&D+i projects.

Room for improvement in the exploitation of synergies between the different agents of the Science, Technology and Business System.

“Carry-over” effect of the cases of success in the dissemination of processes and good innovative practices.

Territorial specialization strategy oriented to intensive and high added value segments with skilled human capital.

Attraction of research talent from other regions using particular programmes.

Support policies and funding.

Possible synergies with other public funding lines available (national or European funding such as European Investments Bank or Structural Funds).

Collaboration network between some public, private and financial institutions.

Existence of both public and private financial intermediaries (European Investments Bank, European Investment Fund).

Possibility of creating intermediate credit lines (combination of regional public resources with other at national or European level).

	<p>Positive evolution of the foreign investment in the region.</p> <p>Growing interest for sustainable investment.</p> <p>Visibility of the region at European level thanks to other projects.</p> <p><u>Inter-administrative cooperation and coordination.</u></p> <p>Institutional support and commitment to the environment and the territory.</p> <p>Regulatory provisions and planning tools in the field of environment and sustainability.</p> <p>Technological dimension and development of the Andalusian Public Sector to allow it to act as a demand, public procurement of innovative solutions and driver of companies.</p>
<p>Threats</p>	<p><u>Generation and availability of biomass resources.</u></p> <p>Availability of biomass resources at better prices and of major quality in other regions.</p> <p>Reduction of the biomass resources available due to the effects of climate change.</p> <p>Changes in legislation that can harden the requirements to recover or manage biomass resources.</p> <p><u>Infrastructures and logistic management of biomass resources.</u></p> <p>High transport costs of certain flows of low-density biomass resources.</p> <p>Transport costs very dependent on the volatility of the price of fossil fuels.</p> <p>Excessive importance of the transport by road with its consequent impact on GHG emissions.</p> <p>Deficiencies in the connection between the regional Andalusian centres and other international markets (Mediterranean Axis and Trans-European Transport Networks).</p> <p><u>Industrial processing of biomass resources and capacity of industrial production of bioproducts and bioenergy.</u></p> <p>High transport costs of certain flows of low-density biomass resources.</p> <p>Certain legislative developments that hinder and hamper the use of particular by-products and waste.</p> <p>Regulatory changes that may affect the transformation of biomass</p>

Development of markets for bioproducts and bioenergy

Uncertainty concerning the development of the possible markets arisen from the productive areas that must be part of the Andalusian circular bioeconomy.

Difficulties faced by the business sector in general, and of innovative companies, in particular, to access to new markets or to keep the leadership quotas reached in certain areas compared to the international competitors.

Increase of the energy cost and uncertainty in its regulative framework, specially concerning renewable energies.

Competition with cheaper products derived from the fossil energy or with products of other markets regulated by different legislations.

Low production performances of bioproducts.

Communication.

Lack of clarity in the dissemination of the circular bioeconomy concept, what hinders its understanding among the different stakeholders.

R&D+Innovation and Training.

Resources of the R&D+i system slightly efficient to attract and retain the human capital of the Science, Technology and Business System.

Growing international competence in terms of resources, talent, technology and attraction of R&D+i investments.

Relative disconnection between the business structure and the Andalusian knowledge system. Moreover, the limited activity of many components of the latter results in the reduction of the improvement and development potential of the most innovative industry.

Limited number of companies that use the public R&D+i system compared to its size.

Insufficient appreciation of research in general and of researchers in particular, especially by the business fabric.

Incidence of the economic crisis in the number of companies classified as innovative, as well as in the expenditure on innovation.

Existence of barriers for the mobility between the R&D+i staff of the public and private sectors

Support policies and funding.

	<p>Poor involvement of the private sector in R&D+i funding.</p> <p>Limited access to credit to undertake or innovate, aggravated by the current economic situation.</p> <p>Risk of sustainability of the R&D public sector in the current situation due to a lack of alternatives to direct financing.</p> <p>Limitations in the access to traditional loan instruments (loans and credits).</p> <p>Shortage of alternative funding and credit options.</p> <p>Problems to access to private funding by the private sector, especially, SMEs.</p> <p><u>Inter-administrative cooperation and coordination.</u></p> <p>Bureaucratic burdens and excessive administrative procedures that entail important obstacles for entrepreneurship.</p> <p>Administrative difficulties for the implementation and development of projects in the territory (for example, innovative projects).</p>
--	---

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy promote the following measures/tools:

- Identifying the biomass resources produced in Andalusia.
- Improving the availability of biomass resources and sustainable practices in the sectors and producing areas associated with the bioeconomy.
- Improving the knowledge on biomass resources and their sources according to logistic factors.
- Keeping and improving infrastructures and implementing instruments to ensure the supply resources for the operators or the bioindustries considering the sustainability of the value chain.
- Improving the processes to prepare biomass resources and stimulating models to increase the eco-efficiency of their transformation.
- Supporting the creation and promoting the continuity of bioindustries and biorefineries, especially the integrated ones.
- Conducting studies on bioproducts, bioenergy and services linked to the circular bioeconomy.
- Promoting the use and distribution of bioproducts and bioenergy.
- Communicating and promoting the positive externalities of the circular bioeconomy.
- Favouring the adoption of innovation and the transfer of the knowledge related to the circular bioeconomy.
- Supporting collaborative approaches that promote innovation.
- Promoting the introduction of the circular bioeconomy in training programmes, curricular activities and in training for professionals.

- Improving the financing of projects included in the areas related to the circular bioeconomy.
- Favouring foreign investment in the field of the Andalusian circular bioeconomy.
- Facilitating the cooperation and collaboration between stakeholders.
- Clarifying the regulatory and legal framework that affect the activities linked to the circular bioeconomy and stimulating it in plans and programmes of the Andalusian Administration.
- Setting up a Monitoring Committee and a Technical Office for the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy to analyse the impact of its measures in the goals set.

In relation to horticulture highlights:

- There is a good predisposition to implement innovative solutions in this sector that minimize or avoid the generation of waste, such as adoption of alternatives to mulching (compostable and biodegradable).
- There are available alternatives for staking elements or raffias, all of them (compostable, reusable, and biodegradable raffia) obtain a medium-high predisposition to be used and they are more sustainable.
- With reference to the alternatives for energetic valorisation of difficult-to-manage waste tested (valorisation by pyrolysis and valorisation by gasification), the sector has a medium predisposition to adopt these techniques. It is therefore clear that the sector has a need for innovative alternatives for this type of plastic waste.
- With regard to the alternatives for documentary traceability of inorganic waste, the predisposition to adopt the alternatives tested is medium, and producers perceive the physical documentary traceability system as more feasible than using the software, possibly because at the moment there is no solid and developed software linked to the documentary traceability of the residues.
- In relation to the alternatives related to associative models for waste management, the potential for adoption of both alternatives offered in the horticultural sector is medium, although the sector is more inclined to adopt the alternative where companies establish waste management agreements with a single management company than the alternative in which the farmers' association becomes waste manager.
- There is a high potential of adoption of the solutions tested in the horticultural industry. The ones showing a better potential of adoption are those considering the use of rPET (incorporate recycled material (recycled PET) in the packaging while putting into the market a 100% recyclable PET packaging), the use of cardboard trays and bands to substitute the whole packaging.

According to dairy production and industry, the following measures are to be considered:

- Lowering plastic use by packaging light weighting allows reducing fossil sources exploitation and waste streams.
- Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) studies on bioplastic packaging report environmental advantages compared to conventional systems.
- The adoption of non-destructive control systems prevents waste generation at the quality control level.

The lessons learnt from the circular bioeconomy policy in the strategic sector are as follows:

- There are innovative alternatives for the most relevant sectors in Andalusia because they are tested in diverse experiences according to legislation. Besides, the main social, technical, and economic factors have been identified in order to promote the adoption of innovation.
- The research and transfer are promoted through different channels: field trials, workshops, videos on social networks, etc., and whenever possible in productive areas.
- Promote quality certifications related to respect for the environment, specifically the reduction of inorganic waste.
- Promoting the existence of specific managers for each type of waste and improving the network of easily accessible collection points (green points) where waste can be delivered at an affordable cost in the immediate surroundings of the production areas.
- Developing a regulatory framework that includes all types of inorganic waste in a differentiated manner, guaranteeing their correct management through a system of extended responsibility.
- Concerning the factors that promote the adoption of innovation, the horticulture sector feels that the most important one is consumer acceptance in terms of impact on sustainability.
- The food companies (not only horticulture) are very keen on how to valorise their engagement on the sustainability topic.
- Better use of funding schemes existing at the national/regional to finance the necessary investments at the plant level.
- A better involvement of plastic producers/processors and suppliers of packaging is necessary.
- Need for specific training for government staff responsible for authorising circular bioeconomy initiatives.
- Green public procurement to promote the use of circular bioeconomy products.
- Need to promote a venture capital model that facilitates investment in circular bioeconomy initiatives.
- Political recommendation: encourage companies to adopt alternative solutions thanks to regional and national technical and financial support.
- Encourage research and development projects about new alternative solutions.
- Regional support for companies who are willing to put alternative solutions in place.
- Raising awareness of consumers.

6. Circular bioeconomy governance profiles of ROBIN regions

6.1 Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Baden-Wuerttemberg case

6.1.1 Regional and local peculiarities

Baden-Wuerttemberg is the third largest state in Germany, both in terms of area and population. Located in southwestern Germany and being adjacent to three German states, it is centrally located in Europe and shares its borders with three European countries.

The area of intervention of the regional sustainable bioeconomy strategy is the whole federal state. The size is 35,751 km² with a population of about 11 Mio. people and a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of around €536 bn. in 2023 [45], [46].

Stuttgart is the state capital and the largest city, with a population of around 630,000 by 2020. The next largest cities are Mannheim (~310,000 inhabitants), Karlsruhe (~308,000) and Freiburg (~231,000). In addition to the urban centers, Baden-Wuerttemberg has a strong rural area with diverse agriculture, forestry and tourism. 586 of Baden-Wuerttemberg's municipalities have fewer than 5,000 inhabitants. The landscape and nature are diverse with large contiguous forest areas such as the Black and the Swabian Forests, or the Odenwald. Around 40% of Baden-Wuerttemberg's surface area is covered with forest. Regarding water bodies, the lake Constance (total area: 572 km²) plays an important role as drinking water source and recreational use in the region. The main rivers that flow through Baden-Wuerttemberg are the Rhine (437 km), Neckar (367 km) and Danube (251 km) [45].

The most developed value chains related to the bioeconomy are the forestry and agricultural sector related. For both sectors the use of biomass and valorisation of fiber-rich by-products for multiple purposes plays a major role e.g.: biopolymers (e.g., packaging, automotive, textile and paper industry), bio-based building blocks for phytopharma (e.g. natural cosmetics) and biomass for energy /biofuels as the final stage of the cascade use. Some emerging value chains are related with hemp, plant-based proteins (soja, lupins, peas), valorisation of wastewater, industrial CO₂ reuse, insect biorefineries, or municipal modular biorefineries for the valorisation of energy, waste and side streams.

The most relevant biomass feedstocks of Baden Wuerttemberg are wood, lignin, lignocellulose, bio-waste, agricultural by-products (e.g., from harvest or digestates) and insects. An analysis of the baseline situation in Baden-Wuerttemberg shows firstly that is a densely forested state: 38.9% of the state's land area is covered with forest (13,900 km²). Currently, around 4 Mio solid cubic meters per year are already used for energy. This means that the potential for sustainable use of the forest has already been almost fully exploited. There is considerable unexploited utilisation potential in

hardwoods, especially in heavy timber. In addition, residues from the sawmill and wood industry could be also used.

Germany has the goal to produce 28% of energy consumption in the transport sector by renewable energy with help of advanced biofuels. Regarding vegetable oil, operational experience already exists in Baden-Wuerttemberg with craft and cab businesses as well as local transport companies [47].

Related to the bio-waste, 39 out of 44 municipal, peri-urban and rural districts had the option of using separate collection of domestic bio-waste. This collection was carried out with a bio-garbage can in most districts. The quantity of bio-waste collected in 2021 was 640,000 t. Regarding green waste, 310,000 t was used for material and energy use and 729,000 t for biological use [48].

The launch of the “Sustainable bioeconomy strategy” by the Government of Baden-Wuerttemberg [49] in 2019 was a milestone of the relevance of this topic in the policy agenda. The topic already progressed since 2013 via the Bioeconomy Research Programme. The fact that the Green Party (*Grüne*) has been leading the Government in coalition since 2011 represented a solid impulse; the launch of the strategy paved the way to an average good reception of the topic among the regional stakeholders and the general public. At the current time, more awareness-raising is needed at the county and municipal level, but no adverse effects are foreseen in the future. Moreover, 5 regions candidated as *example regions* for the industrial bioeconomy [50] at a national competition in 2022 and are currently being set.

The solid implementation of the strategy has already/ will bring effects at all levels: economic, social and environmental. Although no data on the scale of effect or direct correlation with the GDP is available, the implementation of the strategy should increase the turnover from the bio-based innovations, settle new value chains, bring environmental benefits (e.g. through improvement of the valorisation of bio-waste [13]), as well as establish new examples of social innovation in form of bioeconomy labs / hubs e.g. the urban BioEconomyLab [14] or the Innovation Hub CCUBIO [15].

6.1.2 Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies

Baden-Wuerttemberg was quoted in a European Commission study in 2017 as one of the six top ranking European regions on the bioeconomy maturity index [5]. The “Baden-Wuerttembergs government's sustainable bioeconomy strategy” was published in June 2019 after a participative progress conducted by the state agency BIOPRO Baden-Wuerttemberg in 2017 and 2018. The strategy was driven by two leading ministries, the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection, and the Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy Sector. The genesis of this cross-departmental regional strategy is found in 2013, when the systemic research programme “Die Bioökonomie im System aufstellen” (“Setting up the bioeconomy in the system”) was launched by the Ministry of Science, Research and the Arts. This document represented a first concept for a research strategy in Baden-Wuerttemberg. Nowadays the appointed departments of the four Ministries (the three mentioned above plus the Ministry of Economic Affairs, Labour and Tourism) meet in a regular basis through the organisation of *Jour Fixes*.

The basic objectives of the bioeconomy strategy are the development of biological concepts for the exploitation of renewable or recyclable raw materials, and the development of Baden-Wuerttemberg

as a model region for sustainable and circular economy, as well as, strengthening the role of the rural areas. Other aspects are relevantly considered e.g., impact to climate change, protection of the biodiversity and the promotion of bio-based innovations. The scope of the strategy is wide, covering rural, urban and industrial areas.

The strategy is composed of 6 action areas and 37 measures. The definition of the bioeconomy within the strategy is mainly based in the one defined by the German government's Bioeconomy Council in 2016. It is kept deliberately broad, including agriculture and forestry, the environmental economy sector and all areas that apply life science knowledge. Indeed, that assures its remarkable cross-sector and cross-policy character. The main cross-border element of the strategy is the organisation of the international "Bioeconomy Congress Baden-Wuerttemberg" twice-yearly, as well as participation in EU initiatives and (particularly) in Interreg projects. The Congress is an initiative out of the Bioeconomy Research Programme set in 2013. It is aimed at a regional, national and international audience.

One of the measures of the bioeconomy strategy is setting up a Sustainable Bioeconomy Council, to pool existing expertise and advise the government on the implementation and further development of the strategy. It is further elaborated in the following chapter.

The strategy has an allocation of €50 Mio. for a 5-year period (2020-2025) and includes economic incentives such as public procurement, idea competitions, creation of pilot and demonstration facilities (e.g., modular biorefineries in rural areas) and funding programmes for companies; also, *thematic initiatives* for interdisciplinary, cross-cutting and along the value chain networks are supported. Additionally, €35 Mio. were allocated as part of the measures resulting from the COVID-19 crisis, that were addressed for innovation and investment programmes for the rural areas. Between 2013 and 2019 around €14 Mio. were invested for the Bioeconomy Research Programme. Some of this budget is covered with the European Fund for Regional Development (EFRD) and is topped-up with co-funding by the regional government till up to 60%.

There are several funding programmes launched since the publication of the strategy that will not be detailed here. The bioeconomy is also addressed in several policies and aligned with other strategies or initiatives, from which four are highlighted in this document: "Sustainability Strategy Baden-Wuerttemberg" (2007) [51], "Baden-Wuerttemberg state's strategy for resources efficiency" (2016) [52], "Construction with wood – Offensive in Baden-Wuerttemberg: sustainable construction for the future" (2018) [53] and "Innovation Strategy Baden-Wuerttemberg" (2020) [54].

Moreover, the bioeconomy and the circular economy are explicitly mentioned in the chapter 5.8 ("Innovation for more resource efficiency, circular economy and climate protection") of the Innovation Strategy Baden-Wuerttemberg (Update in 2020) [16]. In this strategy aspects such as the role of the bioeconomy, the adaptation of the automotive industry -one of the key sectors in the region- to the circular economy principles, and the future prospects for a hydrogen-based economy are mentioned or elaborated. Social innovation is mentioned in the document in form of "sharing economy".

The regional bioeconomy strategy has an action area called "Information and dialogue about the sustainable bioeconomy", that aims at expanding information about the bioeconomy and strengthening the social dialogue. Some of the measures such as the participative dialogue, the *bioeconomy experience space* and several information initiatives via print media, digital platforms, trade fairs, conferences and educational institutions are foreseen.

The region has a long tradition in participative governance and -due to the fact that bioeconomy and climate-change are in the policy agenda since long- the acceptance of the general public is high, nonetheless the awareness is low (bioeconomy concept is still difficult to communicate in layman terms). The so-called *Landesgartenschau*, a kind of garden and landscape-planning related open-

air exhibition organised in Baden-Wuerttemberg twice-yearly, are also used as vehicle to communicate on the bioeconomy.

As already mentioned, the regional bioeconomy strategy advocates deliberately for a wide definition of the bioeconomy. Three interdisciplinary areas of action related with networking, education and information are listed in the strategy. The systemic approach of the *thematic initiatives* (measure 26 of the strategy) is also a relevant element on this regard. An example of bio-based solutions integrated to existing systems can be found in a recent co-funded project via European Regional Development Fund called Biowaste to Products (BW₂Pro), in which a modular biorefinery will be installed in the location of the public company Abfallwirtschaft Rems-Murr, so secondary raw materials can be obtained from municipal waste and wastewater treatment plants in a county with 425,000 inhabitants. The project has a 2.5-year duration.

6.1.3 The Quadruple Helix actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system

The regional bioeconomy strategy is backed-up politically by the State Ministry. The conception and drafting of the strategy were driven by two leading ministries in 2019, the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection, and the Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy Sector, both finally featuring as co-publishers. The implementation is based in a cross-departmental work involving also the Ministry of Science, Research and the Arts, and the Ministry of Economic Affairs, Labour and Tourism. Besides that, the Sustainable Bioeconomy Council acts as a board of experts advising, guiding and supporting the strategy process; it is consulted in a periodic basis. This Council is currently composed of 17 experts coming from different sectors (industry, academia and research), including Prof. Dr. Ralf Kindervater, CEO of BIOPRO Baden-Wuerttemberg. Civil and environmental NGOs are not represented in this Council. Nonetheless they participated in the consultation and participative process ran in 2017/2018.

Baden-Wuerttemberg as a region has an extended pool of academia, research, clusters, business support organisations and companies related with the bioeconomy. The universities, universities of applied science and research institutions cover the entire range of research topics that are important for the bioeconomy (e.g., agricultural science, forestry, plastics technology, materials science, textile technology or energy). A relevant example is the University of Hohenheim in Stuttgart, that launched the first bioeconomy degree programme in Europe and has its own Research Faculty of Bioeconomy.

Competence centers related to the bioeconomy are a few e.g., the Technikum Laubholz, which is an independent non-university research institute that develops innovative high-quality applications for hardwood. Another example is the Landwirtschaftliche Technologiezentrum Augustenberg, in which the focus is on the production of protein plants and biomass for material and energetic use. And, finally, the Deutsche Institute für textile+Faserforschung (DITF) is based on material development, including cellulose-based filaments and bio-based fibers and polymers. All these competence centers are related with several ministries in different forms: the first institution was set-up under the auspices of the Ministry of Food and Rural Affairs, the second one is an institution within that Ministry; and the third one includes representatives of the Ministries of Science and Economic Affairs in its the board of trustees.

The very well-established cluster landscape is a major asset for Baden-Württemberg's industry. The state's policy has been dealing with cluster policy for a long time, making it a component of innovation and SME policy. There are 9 clusters and associations whose topics are related to the bioeconomy. There is not a specific bioeconomy cluster in the region, but BIOPRO Baden-Wuerttemberg pools the competences in a cross-sectoral manner following a quadruple helix approach. It facilitates networking among industry, academia, public bodies and the general public. More than setting a regional bioeconomy cluster, BIOPRO advocates for the so-called *bioeconomisation* of the regions. This process involves a systemic approach of the value chain and continuous communication and information activities. BIOPRO is one of the state agencies mandated by the government and act on its behalf, so to speak. State agencies strengthen the innovative power of the region and act as catalysts for the competitiveness of SMEs through the networking of science and industry and the associated knowledge transfer.

The networking through areas, actors and clusters is promoted through an action area of the regional bioeconomy strategy. In an exercise done in May 2022 through the Danube Transnational Programme project GoDanuBio [55], BIOPRO identified that one important missing actor for the *bioeconomisation* of the region are the chambers of commerce. Further work with key productive sectors such as the automotive and machine-building industry are also needed. In this regard, an *example region* on industrial bioeconomy has been launched -among four other locations- in the region of Stuttgart [56].

Baden-Württemberg as a business location is characterized by global players as well as innovative SMEs. More than 90 % of the companies in the state have less than 250 employees. The region has around 452,500 companies in total. Even in rural areas, Baden-Württemberg is home to research-intensive companies whose internal expenditure on research & development is significantly higher than the overall average in Germany. Another important factor is that Baden-Württemberg companies have strong cooperation with companies located in other federal states in the field of bioeconomy. This is due to the fact that the region covers the bio-based value chain very well at its end, but not at the beginning of the chain.

Co-creation activities related to the regional bioeconomy were a fundamental part of the roadmap towards the strategy. In the years 2017 and 2018, BIOPRO commissioned a participative process with more than 300 participants on behalf of the two leading Ministries. The set-up of the Sustainable Bioeconomy Council years ago could be seen as an element of a co-creation process too. In July 2022 at more local level, a co-creation workshop was organised in the Alb-Donau County as a regional activity of the project GoDanuBio. As follow-up, two expert groups for discussing about bioeconomy progress in this county are being founded at the time of writing.

Baden-Wuerttemberg has a long tradition on participative governance, and it is highly valued. In 2013, the participation portal Baden-Württemberg [22] was launched, in which citizens can participate online. An example would be civil society involvement in the area of land readjustment. These are agri-structural reorganisation measures related e.g., to the construction of a new road. This action can fragment land ownership, but it can be reunited during the process to facilitate working conditions in agriculture. A platform [23] provides information about current procedures, and citizens can actively give comments and opinions and participate in workshops or events.

There are several examples as citizens' initiatives and non-profit organizations like associations which lobby for topics as e. g. permaculture, e-mobility and renewable energies. It is interesting to mention that, from a first glance, land use for agriculture and renewable energies (photovoltaic, wind, biomethanol production, etc.) might be considered contradictive but could be merged by combining both in Agri-Photovoltaic projects (Agri-PV) [24]. The special characteristic about citizens' initiatives is that there are events to different topics (among them, rural development), in which citizens'

initiatives can speak directly with representatives of the regional government and local administration in order to present their concerns and ideas.

The views and interests towards the bioeconomy transition lay fundamentally in the sectoral approach of each association or group of interest represented. E.g. in the Rhein-Nektar region there is a food.netz association, that approach the bioeconomy mainly from the perspective of the food systems, while for several NGOs (e.g. NABU Baden-Wuerttemberg), the protection of the biodiversity could be one main priority. On the other hand, clusters and business support organisations could be more sensible to regulation that could affect (negatively) the day-to-day business of the sector they represent. In regard to the general public, there is a wide understanding of greening and climate change issues, but bioeconomy might be still too specific or niche for a general understanding.

In the case of primary producers such as farmers and farmer cooperatives/associations there has been a continuous advance on the positive position toward the bioeconomy since 2017. The introduction of the European Green Deal and the new Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) even reinforced this trend. The main two agricultural sector organisations in Baden-Wuerttemberg are the the Genossenschaftsverband e.V. (BWGV) and the Landesbauerverband in Baden-Wuerttemberg e.V., LBV. “Tank-plate” discussions from the past have got over and now the main topic might be the land use change.

6.1.4 The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs)

The political mandate is the regional and local implementation of the bioeconomy within the Baden-Wuerttemberg’s territory. The scope of the strategy is wide, covering rural, urban and industrial areas. The rural part is covered with measures proposed by the Ministry of Food, Rural Affairs and Consumer Protection, and the ones related with urban and industrial areas are proposed by the Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy Sector.

As explained in the 2nd chapter, the current allocation of funds for the implementation of the regional bioeconomy strategy is €50 Mio. for a period of five years (2020-2024). This allocation is distributed in different funding programmes launched by the two leading Ministries. Some of these funding programmes are directly related with the measures listed in the strategy. The action plan is based in 6 action areas and 37 measures.

Moreover, and as part of the post-pandemic measures, a package of €300 Mio has been allocated to maintain the competitiveness of Baden-Wuerttemberg as a business location. This is an open-topic call, including climate change and sustainability topics, so no bioeconomy-specific. The funds are mainly allocated to companies or joint projects with RTD organisations. Although this package is not *per se* part of the bioeconomy strategy, it could have a positive impact depending on the final projects funded. The bioeconomy-related funding programmes can be addressed by sector e.g., some funding for the revitalisation of the rural areas, or with a wider approach as e.g. the establishment of modular biorefineries or for networking purposes through the *thematic initiatives*.

The monitoring, evaluation and/or use of indicators for the implemented strategy is not detailed in public documents. It is known that the Sustainable Bioeconomy Council is consulted periodically for opinion in some measures and strategic decisions to take. The update of the strategy is expected

by end of 2024 and an evaluation is expected till then. The implementation of the strategy has recently assured its continuation after 2024 [33].

A study was funded between 2017/2018 and co-lead by the University of Stuttgart and IFEU Heidelberg to develop a concept for a Bioeconomy Development Index. The study was discussed with multiple stakeholders from Baden-Wuerttemberg during the dialogue process (*Plan B*), as well as in a second event organised by the Ministry for the Environment, Climate and Energy Sector. For the index, 18 key indicators and 9 dimensions were identified. The indicators were selected in basis of an integral sustainability perspective: the UN Sustainability Goals were considered, as well as the Bioeconomy Research Programme in Baden-Wuerttemberg and the German politic strategy in bioeconomy. Recommendations for action for the creation of a monitoring program were finally set [34], [35]. It is not known to which degree these recommendations were considered in the design and implementation of the regional bioeconomy strategy.

6.1.5 Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT Analysis)

As part of a larger strategic process called "Designing the future with bioeconomy", the Bioeconomy Research Programme launched by the Ministry of Science, Research and the Arts [57] in 2013 was developed by a working group of scientists from a broad spectrum of disciplines relevant to bioeconomy, in cooperation with partners from industry. The programme outlined an extensive assessment of the current research landscape of Baden-Wuerttemberg relevant to bioeconomy, including a SWOT analysis (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities and Threats). It also reasoned and described the three research topics to be funded:

7. The research field of **biogas**, that showed potential for the short-term implementation of innovations; this field has a high scientific know-how along all the value chain, is well established and there is general interest for its further progress.
8. The research field of **lignocellulose** is characterised by a large number of outstanding individual competencies that come with a wide range of know-how that can contribute to further development. Contrary to the biogas research field, the actors and competencies are not yet bundled. Thus, this field of research shows a more medium-term implementation character. The perception of the potential of this research field is still not very pronounced in the associated industries and intensive networking is needed.
9. The research field of **algae** was selected by the group of experts as the subject area with the longest-term perspective while having the greatest potential for innovation. There is already a high level of scientific competence in Baden-Wuerttemberg along the entire value chain, however coupled with a great need for action (biorefinery). Since it only marginally found its way into the economy, it is the field of research with the greatest need for development.

The SWOT exercise was based in three pillars: i) raw materials from supply side (agri-, wood-based, aquatic, bio-waste and by-products); ii) products and valorisation from demand side (food use, material use, energetic use); and iii) cross-cutting areas covering ecological, societal, ethical and economic aspects. Since the exercise done in 2013, no further SWOT related to the bioeconomy strategy and related policies has been published.

A correlation between the identified research fields identified in the SWOT and its transposition in the text of the current regional bioeconomy strategy is found. E.g., measure 16 of the regional

bioeconomy strategy (“Further development of the biogas plant inventory”) will develop a concept for the future-oriented, economically efficient and environmentally friendly expansion of the existing biogas plants (around 1,000 agricultural ones) following the expiry of the guaranteed EEG (*Erneubare Energien Gesetz*) bonuses. The bonus was related to a 20-years long warranty. The measure 14 (“Pilot/demonstration facilities”) is related to the comprehensive processing of biological resources into innovative products, including lignocellulosic crops, side streams and residual materials along the agricultural and forestry value chains. The facilities will be decentralised and in form of modular biorefineries in rural areas. Finally, the measure 18 (also called “Pilot/demonstration facilities”) is related, among others, with substance synthesis and CO₂ recycling via smart fermentation and biocatalysts with microalgae, bacteria and fungi. The establishment of biofactories as living labs and pilot facilities will serve for the purpose of a bioeconomy in urban and industrial areas.

Emerging opportunities (insect biorefineries, plant-based protein, hemp...) were shortly commented in chapter 1.

6.2 Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Central Macedonia case

6.2.1 Regional and local peculiarities

The region where the circular bioeconomy strategy is applied:

Region of Central Macedonia, 1.792.069 inhabitants, 19.146km², 14.5% total area size of Greece

Characterization of the area(s) of intervention (urban, peri-urban, semi-rural, rural, coastal). More than one could apply:

Urban, Peri-urban, Semi-rural & rural.

Priority and potential regional sectors/value chains for the circular bioeconomy (agriculture, livestock, agroindustry, forest, chemical industry, energy, maritime, water, etc.):

1. Agriculture
2. Livestock
3. Agroindustry
4. Chemical industry
5. Energy

Baseline situation of the territory (region), and locally available feedstocks/biomass from the mentioned sectors/value chains (residues, by-products, food waste, plastic, bio-waste, marine debris, etc. from agriculture, agri-food, maritime, bio-waste, etc.):

Data to be collected by the General Division of Agroecology & Veterinary and the General Division of Development & Environment of the Region of Central Macedonia.

Brief assessment of the "territorial sensitivity" of the region for the development of the circular bioeconomy, with consideration of the importance of the circular bioeconomy in the region currently [Territorial (regional) sensitivity to bioeconomy development can be described as the degree to which a territory (region) can potentially be directly or indirectly affected, either adversely or beneficially by an increase of the circular bioeconomy in the territory (region)]:

The territorial sensitivity of the Region of Central Macedonia is extremely high. A sustainable and circular bioeconomy contributes to addressing global challenges e.g. climate change, land & ecosystem degradation, which combined to a growing demand for food, feed & energy, results to new ways of producing & consuming. Thus, industries simultaneously modernize their production systems & protect the environment.

Brief assessment of the "exposure" of the region to the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy, with consideration of the scale of its effect (economic, social, environmental) in the region [Exposure to bioeconomy is the degree to which the bioeconomy is part of the regional economy currently. Describe in economic (e.g. GDP), social (e.g. employment) and environmental terms]:

The circular bioeconomy in the Region of Central Macedonia presently "takes its first steps". The implementation of the circular bioeconomy affects the region to a great extent. Its effect is enormous on positive environmental terms (less emissions of CO₂, less water consumption, soil fertility. Its societal effect is strongly positive because of increased rate of employment especially in agriculture, waste management & energy.

Economically, Circular Bioeconomy will also result to a positive effect as development of the Circular bioeconomy creates a climate that promotes the development, & modernisation of new start – ups and other enterprises.

Overall, Circular bioeconomy is expected to result to a strongly positive effect.

Bridging elements, synergies and platforms between traditional (agri-food, fisheries, livestock etc.) sectors, industry, research, technology and public administration [i.e., who (agents) or what (agencies) may facilitate (bridge) the aforementioned QH actors. It could be formal (legislation) or informal. Please provide specifics]:

Technical Chamber and the Geo-Technical Chamber are the Bridging elements between traditional sectors and public administration.

Consulting agencies bridge the communication between industry, agriculture, research technology and public administration. Employees such as Agricultural Advisors and Environmental Managers within their organizations/enterprises also facilitate through reports, documents required by legislation.

6.2.2 Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies

Description of the level of development of the strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in the region and how they were developed. Analysis whether a circular bioeconomy strategy exists on standalone mode, or as a part of a broader mix of strategies (with links to relevant strategy(-ies) if available):

The Regional Development Fund on behalf of the Region of Central Macedonia participates in the European scheme "Regional Models of circular economy & best available techniques for biological streams" - *BIOREGIO* [17].

BIOREGIO's target is the direction of regional policies to support the best practices of circular economy and it is funded by the inter-region programme INTERREG EUROPE 2014-2020. It is realized locally by the Heat Transfer & Environmental Engineering Laboratory of the *Department of Mechanical Engineers* [18] of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki and the *Regional Development Fund of Central Macedonia* [19]

CESME (Circular Economy for SMEs) aims to the transition from a linear to a circular economy where all outflows from a production activity are reused as inflows to another production activity resulting to greener methods.

Description of the planning instruments, policies, measures, supporting schemes and other interventions available that comprise the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The Regional Development Fund, the Aristotle University, the Region of Central Macedonia, Technical Chamber and the Geo-Technical Chamber promote the circular bioeconomy policy. Acting programmes: BIOREGIO (INTERREG), CESME, HORIZON, LIFE

Cross-sector, cross-policy, and cross-border/inter-region analysis of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

Circular bioeconomy strategy is cross-sector, cross policy and cross border/inter -region., e.g. There are inter region programs between Greece and Bulgaria, and Greece and North Macedonia. Also, it is by definition cross-policy and cross sector strategy as environment, agriculture, energy etc. are the basis for a more positive economically, socially and environmentally future

S3 (smart specialization strategies) implementation in the region:

Yes

Connection between the circular bioeconomy strategy and other related strategies (Sustainable Development Goals, S3, Climate change, etc), with description of interconnections/synergies in terms of common objectives or actions with other regions and/or national strategies or plans objectives:

Circular bioeconomy strategy and other related strategies (Sustainable Development Goals, S3, Climate change are cross – connected. Programmes such as Horizon and LiFE target to a better future keeping in mind the human, the environment as well as the financial situation (direct outcome of Development of enterprises)

Strategic vision/s and objectives of the circular bioeconomy strategy in the territory (region):

The strategic vision/s and objectives of the circular bioeconomy strategy in the Region of Central Macedonia is the direction of regional policies to support the best practices of circular economy (by reduction of environmental impact through management of wastes and reuse/recycle of the feedstocks/biomass to energy creation).

Existence of bio-based solutions integrated to existing systems/processes or independent [i.e., is the bioeconomy sector been developed as an independent sector or are bio-based solutions integrated into existing systems and processes]:

There are bio-based solutions integrated to existing systems/processes and they may be independent.

Brief description of the level of public awareness and acceptance of the circular bioeconomy strategy [Level of awareness among the general population (public) of the region: High/medium/low.]:

Public awareness and acceptance of the circular bioeconomy strategy is characterized as medium since more training & education of the general population is needed.

Brief description of the degree of concern, interest, and knowledge of farmers/producers/businesses (stakeholders) about the circular bioeconomy strategies available, the problem of waste, etc., and the circularity opportunities (marketing, social, etc):

The degree of concern, interest, and knowledge of farmers/producers/businesses (stakeholders) about the circular bioeconomy strategies available, the problem of waste, etc., and the circularity opportunities (marketing, social, etc) is considered to be high. Consulting Agencies, Farm Advisors

via workshops & seminars & on-site training in the field can incorporate Circular Bioeconomy into their Development Plan.

On the public sector side and the Chamber's side, public officers, auditors and Chambers officers may communicate many of Circular Bio economy's aspects through legislation and Best Practice techniques.

6.2.3 The QH actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system

Policy departments in local and regional administrations currently involved in the development and the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main responsible administrations):

Decentralized Administration of Macedonia and Thrace, Hellenic Environmental Inspectorate of MoEE, Directorate of Development & Environment of the Region of Central Macedonia, Division of Agro-economy & Veterinary.

Policy departments in local and regional administrations that should also be involved in the future or have shown interest in being involved (in particular those in charge of economic development, agriculture and rural development, environment and climate, research and innovation):

Departments of Environment & Quality of Life of all local Towns inside the Region of Central Macedonia.

Working groups among administrative departments involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy:

"LIFE" program, Department of European Programs and Synergies, Division of Support Innovation and Entrepreneurship of the Region of Central Macedonia:

E-mail: v.tsanidis@pkm.gov.gr

Specific clusters developed, with brief description of the bioeconomy related clusters operating in the territory:

CERTH. Centre for Research and technology Hellas. Among its areas of expertise, activities in renewable energy sources, solid biofuels production and utilization, energy saving and environmental protection are included. It is involved in several EU funded projects regarding agrobiomass utilization and market uptake of bioenergy, such as AGROinLOG, SECURECHAIN, uP_running, Biomasud Plus and BIOFIT.

Previous co-creation initiatives towards governance models/structures/policies:

Yes

People's attitudes towards co-creation with policy makers:

Hesitantly positive

Existence of a bioeconomy strategy council or similar structure overseeing the policy:

No

Brief description of the main actors (stakeholders) in the territory for the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main partners):

The main actors (stakeholders) in the territory for the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main partners) are farmers, industry owners, universities, public & private sector.

Main leadership role owner, to steer and facilitate the development of circular bioeconomy in the territory:

Public sector.

Existence of civil society organizations (CSOs) and/or non-governmental organizations (NGOs) involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy, with brief description:

Management body of Koronia and Volvi lakes, Management Body of Protected areas of the Thermaikos gulf.

Common priorities of the actors involved in circular bioeconomy activities:

The common priorities of the actors involved in circular bioeconomy activities (consider society, business, knowledge, administration, and capital representatives) are the environmental management and the profit.

Existence of diversity of perspectives and interests among them, with explanation:

Yes, the stakeholders derive from different fields (public or private sector, agriculture, or industry) acquiring different final objectives.

Role of public authorities in bringing together the QH actors:

Public officers, auditors and Chambers officers may communicate many of Circular Bio economy's aspects through legislation and Best Practice techniques and familiarise farmers/producers/businesses (stakeholders) about the circular bioeconomy strategies available, the problem of waste, etc., and the circularity opportunities convincing them to incorporate Circular Bioeconomy into their Development Plan.

Intermediary organizations that operate as bridges/links between clusters/sectors:

Technical and Geo technical Chamber

Existence of specialized technology, research and innovation centers within the bioeconomy governance system, analysis of their interconnectivity and their role:

CERTH. Centre for Research and technology Hellas and Universities are connected through personnel, financial resources, and know-how.

6.2.4 The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs)

Monitoring, consulting, implementation, evaluation.

Financial instruments available for the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

European funding programs

There are action plans by sector e.g. environmental sector, agriculture sector.

Brief description of the short-/mid-/long-term actions and their monitoring system (including KPIs, deadlines)

No available data. (to be collected)

Brief description of the follow-up and evaluation procedure of the action plan's performance

No available data. (to be collected)

Economy-related indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The economy-related indicators that are used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy are: Target points, business process, monitoring results and investigation of Deviations.

Societal indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The economy-related indicators that are used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy are: GDP, personnel occupied, wellbeing of Population, employment rate, health status.

Environmental indicators are used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

Gas emissions

Energy produced.

Amount of waste recycled and / or reused.

No Existing initiatives from front-runners and/or regions with the same bioeconomy profile/approach to emulate/follow:

Flexibility of the circular bioeconomy strategy in your territory to accommodate the needs of the territory:

The stakeholders (society, industry & agricultural sector) are skeptical but at the same time rather receptive and appear willing to incorporate new bioeconomy approaches and innovative know-how e.g. green technologies.

6.2.5 Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT Analysis)

Main strengths for implementing the circular bioeconomy in the region:

1. There are services from both the government & public sector to continuously increase the knowledge of Circular Bioeconomy
2. There are management systems to enhance knowledge & implementation to increase e.g. recycling
3. Good presence of consulting engineering companies
4. Significant development of waste-to-energy plants e.g. bio-gas plant

Main weaknesses for applying the circular bioeconomy in the region:

1. Lack of obligatory systems & mechanisms for monitoring, reviewing & evaluating the results of small enterprises that can improve their productivity. Farmers; attitude focuses on their compensations and not to increase their knowledge of their agriculture management.
2. Over consolidated use of several plants resulting to exclusion of others.

Main opportunities for implementing the circular bioeconomy in the region:

1. There is available European funding to help farmers and industries to incorporate and implement new systems/techniques/processes.
2. There is governmental funding.
3. Opening of the market could develop new intra- European trade & business opportunities

Main threats for applying the circular bioeconomy in the region:

1. Livelihood and daily life problems are the main concern of the entrepreneurs (farmers, plant owners) than the integration of new technologies & Circular Bioeconomy approaches.

Concrete and main specific potential measures/tools that can be developed in the region/sector to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices from circular bioeconomy in priority sectors/value chains in the region:

1. A Guide of Best Practice Tools could be developed by public Agencies such as Region of Central Macedonia to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices from circular bioeconomy in priority sectors/value chains in the region.
2. Seminars/workshops

Lessons learnt from the circular bioeconomy policy so far:

Circular bioeconomy has the potential to minimize the environmental impacts of biomass while simultaneously generating value added bioproducts & bio energy.

The societal effect is of great significance and reflects directly to all stakeholders.

6.3 Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Southern region of Ireland case

6.3.1 Regional and local peculiarities

The region where the circular bioeconomy strategy is applied:

The Southern Region of Ireland has an area of 29,590 km², which represents over 42% of Irish state territory. The population is approximately 1.7 Mio according to the 2022 census results, representing one third of the state's population, and is growing at a steady rate that is projected to continue, reaching almost 2 Mio by 2040 according to the Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy for the region. Three out of Ireland's five cities, Cork, Limerick and Waterford, are in the Region along with a network of large towns. In 2020, it was classified as a 'more developed region' according to the EU cohesion policy, the Southern Region ranks 22nd out of all European regions in terms of regional GDP and 2nd at the national level, with a GDP of 147.2 billion euros that accounts for 41.3% of Ireland's GDP1 (Eurostat, 2019). The region has also the highest GDP per capita nationally, which was estimated at 88.5 thousand euros in 2019 (CSO, 2020).

The regional economy relies heavily on a range of multi-national companies that specialise in areas such as:

- Agri-food, bioeconomy and biomaterials
- Electronics and medical technology
- Pharmaceuticals
- Green technology

Characterization of the area(s) of intervention (urban, peri-urban, semi-rural, rural, coastal). More than one could apply:

The Region has a strong urban structure, but it remains largely a rural region with contrasting rural landscapes that range from the Atlantic seaboard to rich productive lands and river valleys. The region includes the three metropolitan city areas of Cork, Waterford and Limerick-Shannon, fourteen key towns, a network of towns and villages and an extensive rural hinterland.

Priority and potential regional sectors/value chains for the circular bioeconomy (agriculture, livestock, agroindustry, forest, chemical industry, energy, maritime, water, etc):

There is an abundance of renewable feedstock in the region, such as seaweed, manure, food waste and biomass which can be converted into biofuels, chemicals, and construction materials and which have the potential to be utilised in agriculture, agroindustry, energy, and chemical industry.

Baseline situation of the territory (region), and locally available feedstocks/biomass from the mentioned sectors/value chains (residues, by-products, food waste, plastic, bio-waste, marine debris, etc. from agriculture, agri-food, maritime, bio-waste, etc.):

Agri-Food. Abundance of renewable feedstock in the region, such as seaweed, manure, grass, food waste, peat, and biomass. The most abundant biomass feedstocks that can be found in the region include grasses, cattle manure and slurry, cheese industry waste, meat and bone meals, cattle industry waste, pig and chicken manure and cereal straws. There are smaller arisings of energy crops, spent mushroom compost and horticultural residues. Forestry harvest and residues can be also found like woodchips and sawmill residues. Aquatic biomass such macroalgae and seaweed is available in coastal regions, while urban waste such as organic food waste is generated in dwellings, towns, and cities.

Brief assessment of the "territorial sensitivity" of the region for the development of the circular bioeconomy, with consideration of the importance of the circular bioeconomy in the region currently

The Southern Region of Ireland has significant strengths in the circular bioeconomy which if understood and managed correctly present an area of opportunity and growth for the region as well as providing a pathway to achieving Ireland's climate action targets. Due to extensive natural and infrastructure resources, the Southern Region has huge potential to inform and lead the way in the bioeconomy in Ireland, while supporting a key Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy (RSES) objective to transition to a low carbon economy.

The Region has a wealth of environmental assets with rich biodiversity. This includes Special Areas of Conservations (SACs and Special Protection Areas (SPAs) which form part of the Region's Natura 2000 Network along with other areas subject to environmental designation.

The Regional, Spatial and Economy Strategy for the Southern Region (RSES) [58] was subject to rigorous environmental assessment in line with EU Directives and national legislation and includes documents which cover the Region on Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA), an Appropriate Assessment (AA) and also a Strategic Flood Risk Appraisal (SFRA). These documents comprise are important documents which should be referred to in the development of any future policy on the bioeconomy.

At the project level, all applications for development consents for projects emanating from any policies that may give rise to likely significant effects on the environment will need to be accompanied by one or more of the following, as relevant:

- Ecological Impact Assessment Report (EclA);

- Environmental Report; • Environmental Impact Assessment Report - if necessary, under the relevant legislation;
- Natura Impact Statement - if necessary, under the relevant legislation

The protection of water resources from pollution is also a significant issue for consideration with statutory protection under the Water Framework Directive. Protection of water resources is supported by the River Basin Management Plan and monitoring of Water Quality by the EPA.

Brief assessment of the "exposure" of the region to the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy, with consideration of the scale of its effect (economic, social, environmental) in the region
There is not a dedicated regional bioeconomy strategy for the Southern Region. However, there is a National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy [39] which was compiled by the Government of Ireland in 2018. There is also the Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy [40] which is supported by the Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy for the Southern Region [58] and the Southern Region Waste Management Plan 2015-2021 [59]. In addition, Action 363 of the Climate Action Plan 2021 [38] states that support will be given to Regional Assemblies to identify areas of potential growth in the bioeconomy. One of the benefits of the implementation of Bioeconomy statements and strategies that relate and reference the bioeconomy for the Southern Region is that the region is already home to a vast amount of biological raw materials and infrastructure resources along with world renowned research institutes in the circular bioeconomy sector. There is a strong collaboration between the industry and academia which fosters cutting edge advancements with the potential for a globally competitive and sustainable bioeconomy. There is a willingness to learn in the region that creates a good atmosphere for cross-sectorial partnership towards sustainable development. The Southern Region is moving towards becoming a UNESCO Learning Region. The Southern Regional Assembly's 'Towards a Learning Region' [60] identifies 19 actions which will move the region towards establishing a Learning Region. One of these actions is to ensure more students and workers across all sectors participate in educational courses and skills development that support the transition to a Low Carbon and Circular Economy.

Bridging elements, synergies, and platforms between traditional (agri-food, fisheries, livestock etc.) sectors, industry, research, technology and public administration

The National Bioeconomy Campus at Lisheen, Tipperary in the Southern Region is an example of a facilitator/bridge between traditional and non-traditional QH actors. This National Campus was developed through the Irish Bioeconomy Foundation (IBF) bringing together relevant stakeholders, including local government, universities, private enterprise and is supported through Enterprise Ireland. At this campus IBF supports collaboration between food companies and other organisations to identifying sustainable bio-based opportunities by deploying biorefining technologies based on renewable biological resources. This former lead and zinc mine, has been transformed into a bioeconomy innovation hub supporting pilot, demonstration and commercial operations which enables QH actors across industry, entrepreneurship, agriculture, and research to scale technologies that convert Ireland's natural resources to products of high value for use in a wide variety of sectors including food ingredients, feed ingredients, pharmaceuticals, natural chemicals, biodegradable plastics and more.

6.3.2 Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies

Description of the level of development of the strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in the region and how they were developed. Analysis whether a circular bioeconomy strategy exists on standalone mode, or as a part of a broader mix of strategies (with links to relevant strategy(-ies) if available):

- There is no specific regional bioeconomy strategy for the Southern Region of Ireland, however there are several both national and regional strategies that are informing regional bioeconomy development including Regional Policy Objectives contained in the RSES for the Southern Region.
- *The National Bioeconomy Statement (NPS)* [39] is part of a broader bioeconomy strategy for the whole of the country. First published in 2018, the NPS was introduced with the purpose of capitalising on the Bioeconomy's future potential.
- *The Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy* [40] is Ireland's first circular economy strategy and a key component of the government's plans for a circular economy to contribute to net-zero emissions by no later than 2050. Its primary objective is to provide a national policy framework to reduce Ireland's circularity gap and includes instruments that address the economic, regulatory and social barriers to achieving this objective. It also promote the development of the Irish circular bioeconomy.
- *The Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy for the Southern Region (RSES)* [41] is a strategic development framework for the future development of the regions three main rural and urban areas. This framework aims to protect and enhance the environment and successfully combat climate change. The bioeconomy is identified as a sector offering significant development opportunities and a key instrument in the transition to a low carbon economy.
- *Renewable Fuels for Transport Policy Statement 2021 –2023* sets out a roadmap for the supply and use of renewable fuels in transport energy in meeting targets set out in the Climate Action Plan 2021 and European obligations for renewable energy supply and use in transport.
- The South East Energy Agency, with collaboration from the Southern Regional Assembly, are currently finalising a South East Bioenergy Implementation Plan.

Description of the planning instruments, policies, measures, supporting schemes and other interventions available that comprise the circular bioeconomy strategy:

- The NPS is built upon the following core policy objectives:
 - Research, Innovation & Skills,
 - Enhancement of markets and competitiveness,
 - Policy co-ordination and stakeholder engagement.
- The Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy:
 - Aligns itself to policy objectives of the NPS
 - Outlines the importance of setting up a National Bioeconomy Forum and the High-Level Implementation Group
 - Notes that one of the primary objectives of the bioeconomy is to aid Irelands transition to a carbon neutral and circular economy while emphasizing the importance of a “coherent, horizontal approach to policymaking across sectors”.
- The Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy for the Southern Region:
 - The Strategy planning and economic strategy is underpinned by strong National policy in the National Planning Framework, which sets the context for the RSES through 10 National Strategic Outcomes, several of which apply to the development of the bioeconomy within the 3 urban regions: Compact Growth, Strengthened Rural Economies and Communities, Transition to Sustainable Energy and Sustainable Management of Water and other Environmental Resources.
- Renewable Fuels for Transport Policy Statement 2021 –2023:
 - Support Ireland's commitment to reduce greenhouse gas emissions.

- Meet and exceed the renewable energy targets set out in RED II and future ambition under the EU Fit for 55 proposals.
- To ensure a shift towards non-crop fuels and more robust sustainability criteria.
- Establish a framework of obligations to support these objectives.

Cross-sector, cross-policy, and cross-border/inter-region analysis of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

- Cross Sectoral
 - NPS & The Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy – recognise that the bioeconomy consists of farming and the agri-food businesses, marine-based industries, forestry, waste management, energy suppliers, and pharma and biotechnology products.
 - The Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy for the Southern Region also identifies the importance that the bioeconomy plays within different industries across rural and urban areas.
- Cross-Policy
 - The NPS outlines that the *Action Plan for Rural Development (2017)* [20] “underlines how the bioeconomy can contribute to decarbonisation, sustainable growth and job creation in the agricultural, industrial and technological sectors in rural areas” and is also recognised in the *Action plan for jobs (2017)* [21].
 - The Bioeconomy Interdepartmental Group (2016) outlined in the NPS is chaired by An Taoiseach and is comprised of seven governmental departments which reflects the need for policy coherence across governmental departments.
- Cross-border / inter-region
 - The NPS has no cross-border references, however the government along with its Northern Irish counterparts, have established an annual All-Island Biobased Industries Day with support from Intertrade Ireland. The event is now in its fourth year.
 - However, as the NPS and the Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy are national strategies, they are interregional.
 - The RSES report outlines policy objectives for the 3 areas of the Cork metropolitan area, Limerick-Shannon area, and Waterford metropolitan area.

S3 (smart specialization strategies) implementation in the region:

- National Smart Specialisation Strategy for Innovation 2022-2027, introduced in July '22 this updated strategy aims to promote a regional approach to research, development, and innovation challenges, providing “a bridge between regional and national innovation strategy building”
- The Bioeconomy is mentioned throughout within the areas of Bioeconomy/Renewable Energy (including Climate Action/ Sustainability).
- National Smart Specialisation Strategy for Innovation 2022-2027 [61].
- The Southern Regional Assembly regional *report* [62] on Smart Specialisation through an extensive SWOT analysis identified the bioeconomy as a key sector for the region with further priority areas identified to direct resources towards. The Southern Regional Assembly will continue to work with the national department in the development of smart specialisation strategies.

Connection between the circular bioeconomy strategy and other related strategies (Sustainable Development Goals, S3, Climate change, etc), with description of interconnections/synergies in terms of common objectives or actions with other regions and/or national strategies or plans objectives:

- In addition to Ireland's NPS, published in 2018, the country will introduce its first Bioeconomy Action Plan covering the 2023-2025 period which has been outlined in the Climate Action Plan 2021 Action List. The Bioeconomy and the opportunities that it creates is also recognised as an important opportunity within the Action Plans for Rural Development and Jobs also published in 2018.
- Sustainability Development Goals (SDGs): Whilst documents like the NPS do not mention them directly it is recognised that an array of bioeconomy activities supports around half of SDGs. Goals like 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth, 9: Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure and 12: Responsible Consumption and Production do align with the aims of existing national and regional strategies on the bioeconomy. The National Implementation Plan for the Sustainable Development Goals 2022-2024. Published October '22, is structured around five strategic objectives:
 - Embed SDG framework across all government policy.
 - Integrate SDG into local authorities to support localisation of SDGs.
 - Greater partnerships for the SDGs.
 - Incorporate the principle of Leave No One Behind into Ireland's Agenda 2030 implementation.
 - Strong reporting mechanisms.

As a result of these objectives, it is expected to see a higher prominence of the SDGs in future strategies particularly at a regional level.

- S3: *National Smart Specialisation Strategy for Innovation 2022-2027* [61], The Bioeconomy is mentioned throughout within the areas of Bioeconomy/Renewable Energy (including Climate Action/ Sustainability).
- Climate Action Plan – Annex of Actions: Action 363 - Support Regional Assemblies to identify areas of potential growth in the bioeconomy. This action outlines the need to involve Irish regional assemblies in the policy development process, specifically identifying the Southern Regional Assembly to be invited to participate in the Bioeconomy Forum and identifying the Southern Regional Assembly as a stakeholder in other points within this action.

Strategic vision/s and objectives of the circular bioeconomy strategy in the territory (region):

- The NPS sets out four strategic policy objectives:
 - Sustainable economy & Society: Developing the Irish Bioeconomy will be the basis for the entire economy to be more sustainable and encourage a greater ethos of circularity.
 - Decarbonisation of the economy: Greenhouse gases can be reduced by developing the bioeconomy, new and innovative processes and practices will encourage efficiency in sectors with high emissions like Agriculture and Forestry. Replacing high embedded carbon products with biobased alternative and developing bioprocessing and biorefining will also play a large part in reducing emissions.
 - Jobs & Competitiveness: Bioeconomy inputs are sourced nationally opening the possibilities for future employment as these bio-based industries develop. With unpredictability arising from international pressures like the war in Ukraine and Brexit, the bioeconomy offers an opportunity replace imported fossil-based inputs.

- Regional prosperity: Many bio-based industries are regionally based, and a developed bioeconomy will help reduce regional decline. Involving regional assemblies in the policy making process will help further the effectiveness of development of regional bioeconomy's.

Existence of bio-based solutions integrated to existing systems/processes or independent:

- The NPS outlines “the bioeconomy extends from farming and the agri-food businesses, marine-based industries, forestry, waste management, energy suppliers, and pharma and bio-technology products” and this is reflective of the developing bioeconomy within Ireland. As the region has flourishing industry in all these sectors bio-based solutions are being developed within these through collaboration with academia, government and others.
- However naturally the development of the bioeconomy is skewed towards certain sectors and within the Southern Region farming and agri-food are to the forefront. The marine sector has also seen investment and development with a focus on complete valorisation of feedstocks in recent times.
- At the same time, research projects are also exploring the development of new sustainable crops which may form part of Ireland's future bioeconomy. This can be seen through projects such as U-Protein, Protein-I and the development of the Irish Hemp Cooperative.

Brief description of the level of public awareness and acceptance of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

- Within the current sphere of bioeconomy stakeholders, bioeconomy awareness is high, and several educational programmes and activities are underway nationally and within the region to promote awareness among new actors. However, outside of this sphere, it is still a developing sector. Recent studies show that important regional stakeholders such as consumers, public and primary producers still have a relatively lack a deep awareness of the bioeconomy, despite holding relatively positive impressions of the concept.

Brief description of the degree of concern, interest, and knowledge of farmers/producers/businesses (stakeholders) about the circular bioeconomy strategies available, the problem of waste, etc., and the circularity opportunities (marketing, social, etc):

- There is limited information available to reflect the degree of concern, interest and knowledge of stakeholders surrounding circular bioeconomy strategies, the problem of waste and the circularity opportunities available.
- Anecdotally primary producers do have a strong concern that bio-based alternatives etc are cost prohibitive and the degree of investment and time required results in them not being a viable alternative.

6.3.3 The QH actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system

Policy departments in local and regional administrations currently involved in the development and the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main responsible administrations):

There is no specific regional Bioeconomy strategy for the Southern Region of Ireland, however there is a broader statement for the whole of the country.

National Policy Statement in the Bioeconomy [39] (National):

- Department of the Taoiseach (Irish prime minister)
- Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine
- Department of Environment, Climate and Communications
- Department of Enterprise Trade and Employment
- Department of Rural and Community Development
- Department of Transport
- Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media (The Gaeltacht is the term used to refer to those areas of Ireland where the Irish language (Gaeilge) is still spoken as a community language)
- Department of Education

Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy [40] (National):

- Department of Environment, Climate and Communications

Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy for the Southern Region [58] (Regional):

- Southern Regional Assembly's Regional Planning and EU Programmes Division (Southern Regional Assembly lead the implementation of the RSES)
- Department of Enterprise, Trade and Employment
- Department of Education (Contributed to the production of the RSES)
- Department of Foreign Affairs (Contributed to the production of the RSES)
- Department of Rural and Community Development (Contributed to the production of the RSES)
- Department of Transport (Contributed to the production of the RSES)
- Department of Tourism, Culture, Arts, Gaeltacht, Sport and Media
- Relevant departments in Local Authorities across the region. Expertise would usually be located in 'Environment' Departments /Sections but Planning and Economic Development Departments would also be involved.

Policy departments in local and regional administrations that should also be involved in the future or have shown interest in being involved (in particular those in charge of economic development, agriculture and rural development, environment and climate, research and innovation):

- **Local Authorities (Carlow, Kilkenny, Wexford, Cork, Kerry, Limerick, Clare, Tipperary, Waterford)** Environment, Planning, Community/Social & Finance. In most Local Authorities the Environment/ Planning and Economic Development Departments would be the departments most likely to be involved.
- **Regional Assemblies (Southern Regional Assembly)-** Regional Planning and EU Programmes
- **Atlantic Seaboard South Climate Action Regional Office CARO-** Local Authority Climate Action

- **Southern Region Waste Management Office**
- **Enterprise Ireland-** Funding and Research and Innovation
- **Irish Water**
- **Environmental Protection Agency EPA-** Climate change, Waste
- **Sustainable Energy Authority Ireland-** Low Carbon Heating and Cooling Technologies,
- **Teagasc-** Animal and Grassland Research and Innovation, Crops, Environment and Land Use, Food, Rural Economy and Development
- **Science Foundation Ireland-** Climate research, Bioeconomy research
- **South East Energy Agency**
- **Tipperary Energy Agency**

Working groups among administrative departments involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy:

- The NPS established the Bioeconomy Implementation Group which is co-chaired by DECC and DAFM.
- The National Bioeconomy Forum was established in 2021 to promote, support and advocate for the sustainable development of the bioeconomy in Ireland in line with the progression of a circular economy, climate action and a climate-neutral, sustainable and innovative agri-food sector.
- Southeast Energy Agency: The agency published a Bioenergy Roadmap (July 2022), part of which is developing regional stakeholder groups to drive policy change.

Specific clusters developed, with brief description of the bioeconomy related clusters operating in the territory:

Circular Bioeconomy Cluster Southwest (*CircBio*) [30]

A first-of-a-kind regional bioeconomy cluster, established by the CircBio Research Group at MTU with a goal to develop and promote bioeconomy in the South-west region, with a focus on marine, agriculture, and waste-to-value thematic areas. The cluster has the aim of unlocking and accelerating business opportunities and new value chains across these sectors. The cluster fosters collaboration through events and workshops, site visits and project matchmaking, linking industry partners to R&D expertise in the region. They also support members with funding opportunities, communications and marketing, and education and training.

Irish Bioeconomy Foundation (*IBF*) [31]

IBFs is a national bioeconomy foundation based at Lisheen Co. Tipperary with the mission to promote the conversion of Ireland's natural land & sea resources to high value products for the development of a sustainable bioeconomy that is globally competitive and creates local development. The foundation facilitates the agrifood, forestry, marine, energy sectors to create synergies enabling innovative projects at a global, regional and local level. Operating on a national level, but are located within the Southern Region, and their activities influence bioeconomy development within the region.

Previous co-creation initiatives towards governance models/structures/policies:

Members and staff of the Southern Regional Assembly (and Members who served in the 2014 to 2019 Assembly), Local Authorities, Government Departments, Public Bodies, Agencies, Community Groups, businesses and stakeholders contributed to the production of the RSES in a co-creation, Quadruple Helix approach. The RSES Implementation Programme has seen further examples through the Learning Region initiative, Smart Mobility, etc. In terms of Bioeconomy RPOs in RSES chapter 4 and Bioenergy and Circular economy RPOs in Chapter 5, would have

been drafted by the Regional Planning team with no wider co-creation process - except that the entire document was subject to three public consultation phases

People's attitudes towards co-creation with policy makers:

No studies regarding people's attitudes towards co-creation with policy makers in the region are available. However, public consultation in the development of sustainable government policy is the norm, and this was also the case in the development of the national bioeconomy policy statement. In addition, part of the role of Ireland's National Bioeconomy Forum is to help inform the development of bioeconomy policy with input from different stakeholders, and to date it has been an effective mechanism.

Existence of a bioeconomy strategy council or similar structure overseeing the policy:

At a national level: The NPS established an implementation group, chaired in conjunction by the Department of Agriculture, Food and Marine and the Department of Environment, Climate and Communications to report and to act on progression of the NPS. There is also the National Bioeconomy Forum was established to promote, support and advocate for the sustainable development.

Brief description of the main actors (stakeholders) in the territory for the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main partners):

The main actors (stakeholders) in the Southern Region when it comes to the bioeconomy and the implementation and creation of a regional bioeconomy strategy are

- Munster Technological University (MTU),
- Teagasc,
- Circular Bioeconomy Research Group
- Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
- Teagasc
- South East Energy Agency
- Tipperary Energy Agency
- Irish BioEnergy Association
- University of Limerick
- University College Cork
- South East Technological University
- MarEI
- Shannon ABC Gateway,
- Irish Bioeconomy Foundation,
- Circular Bioeconomy Cluster South West,
- Bioeconomy Forum,
- Bioeconomy Implementation Group,
- Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine,
- BiOrbic,
- Science Foundation Ireland,
- Environmental Protection Agency (EPA),
- Enterprise Ireland,
- Department of Environment, Climate and Communications

- Southern Regional Assembly.
- Local Authorities within the Region
- Local Enterprise Offices
- Industrial Development Agency Ireland
- Regional Enterprise bodies

Main leadership role owner, to steer and facilitate the development of circular bioeconomy in the territory:

The Bioeconomy is very active and well connected throughout the region and to a national level. A network analysis map published for Bioeconomy Week 2022 shows this interconnectivity and the influence and leadership potential of the actors within the region and nationally which would also be active down to a regional level.

Within the Region:

- Academia & Research: Munster Technological University & Circular Bioeconomy Research Group, Shannon ABC, MaREI, University of Limerick
- Bioeconomy Development: Circular Bioeconomy Cluster Southwest & Irish Bioeconomy Foundation

Regional & National Level:

- State/Semi State: Teagasc, Science Foundation Ireland, Environmental Protection Agency, and the Southern Regional Assembly.
- [*Ireland's Bioeconomy*](#) [63].

Existence of civil society organizations (CSOs) and/or non-governmental organizations (NGOs) involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy, with brief description:

No dedicated regional bioeconomy strategy.

National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy [39]- Irish Bioeconomy Foundation

Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy [40] - Community Resources Network Ireland, Irish Environmental Network, VOICE (Voice of Irish Concern for the Environment), Ellen MacArthur foundation

Regional, Spatial and Economic Strategy for the Southern Region [58] - National Bioeconomy Hub, Tipperary Energy Agency, South East Energy Agency, Irish Bioeconomy Foundation, Public Participation Network (PPN), LEADER programme

Common priorities of the actors involved in circular bioeconomy activities (consider society, business, knowledge, administration and capital representatives):

There is a mixture of priorities. Often in the case of agri-food industry a key objective is around find solutions to become more sustainable, and also to add value to primary/secondary feedstocks. Ireland's dairy sector, for example, has a strong track record to adding value to different milk streams and by-products and the bioeconomy can help advance this work. At the same time, many of these sectors are under pressure to reduce emissions and waste streams, and the bioeconomy offers opportunities to meet these challenges.

For many companies looking to develop or implement processes, a priority is accessing funding for scale up. In the case of bio-based technologies, particularly for first mover companies, the CAPEX required is high with often long routes to market for new products, making access to finance on the journey a challenge.

For primary producers, there is often a priority on ensuring that their farms remain profitable, in spite of the increasing pressures, including environmental pressures resulting from a 25% GHG reduction target by 2030, as well as economic pressures from increasing input prices.

For consumers, some recent studies suggest that Irish consumers have a positive impression of bio-based products, however their level of knowledge about these products and how to identify them remains low, and a relatively low percentage of Irish consumers would pay more for bio-based alternatives, so affordability of products is still key.

Existence of diversity of perspectives and interests among them, with explanation:

There can be many competing interests among the stakeholders. Even in terms of sourcing biomass, it can still be challenge to understand which biomass may harvested without having a negative impact on things like biodiversity and eco-systems services. The development of new value chains can also bring competing interests as each stakeholder will have specific needs. For example – primary producers need to get a fair return for their biomass or residual stream to help maintain the profitability for their farms, often technology developers will require the biomass to be as affordable as possible in order to have a viable process, and meanwhile consumers expect to buy affordable products which are also sustainable. With all of these different priorities, it is sometimes difficult to reconcile these competing interests to develop new value chains and enterprises.

Role of public authorities in bringing together the QH actors:

The Southern Regional Assembly is part of the regional tier of government in Ireland. Part of the local government sector, the assembly forges links between the EU, and national and local levels through regional, spatial and economic planning for the Southern Region. The Southern Regional Assembly interact with a wide variety of the QH actors of Government Departments, agencies, local authorities, and stakeholders from the private and the third sectors at local, regional, national and EU level. Therefore, the Southern Regional Assembly's role in leading the implementation of the Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy's and its objectives to transition to a low carbon economy and to support the National Policy Statement on the bioeconomy will allow for the bringing together of QH actors to achieve this through regional planning and EU projects and programmes. SRA being tasked with assisting in the writing of the Regional Renewable Energy Strategy.

Intermediary organizations that operate as bridges/links between clusters/sectors:

There are several clusters operating in the region.

Circular Bioeconomy Cluster South-West based in Tralee, aims is to develop and promote the circular bioeconomy in the South-West region. The cluster brings together industry, enterprises, government and research centres to deliver unique and co-created initiatives to benefit member companies.

Irish Bioeconomy Foundation (IBF) operates on a national level but is located within the Southern Region, where the IBF facilitates the agri-food, forestry, marine and energy sectors to create synergies enabling innovative bioeconomy projects at a global, regional and local level.

In addition, the South East Energy Agency and the Tipperary Energy Agency bridge the gap between climate targets and real-world results by taking the engineering & financial actions necessary to deliver on Ireland’s Climate Action Plan.

Existence of specialized technology, research and innovation centers within the bioeconomy governance system, analysis of their interconnectivity and their role:

There are several research groups work in the bioeconomy, with a presence in the region.

BiOrbic is a national collaboration of researchers, based across UCD, Teagasc, TCD, University of Limerick, MTU and University of Galway, focused on the development of a sustainable, circular bioeconomy. Whilst it is a nationally focused organisation, it’s actives feed into the development of the bioeconomy within the Southern Region. BiOrbic has strong collaborative activities with an array of bioeconomy stakeholders with the region.

The Circular Bioeconomy Research Group (CIRCBIO) based at Shannon ABC in MTU, has a multidisciplinary team working on various bioeconomy educational and research activities in the region. CircBio leads in areas biorefining including a focus on grass and seaweed feedstocks.

SFI MaEI Centre, headquarter at UCC and based across a number of institutes provides leading expertise in the area of biomethane and other renewable energies.

Bernal Insitute at University of Limerick is leading research into the area of composites and biomaterials.

6.3.4 The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs)

Financial instruments available for the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

Although there is no regional bioeconomy strategy for the Southern Region, The Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy 2022-2023 is Ireland’s first national circular economy strategy. The Strategy is a key addition to Government’s drive to achieve a 51% reduction in overall greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and to get on a path to reach net-zero emissions by no later than 2050, as per commitments in the *Programme for Government* and the *Climate Act 2021*.

Table 35: Financial instruments for the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy

Name of financial instrument/support	Awarding/supporting body	Form of support	Additional details
<u>Support Scheme for Renewable Heat [64]</u>	Government funded/ South East Energy Agency. Ongoing Operational Support.	Support Scheme Tariff/ Financial Instrument	Government funded initiative designed to increase the energy generated from renewable sources in the heat sector. The scheme is open to commercial, industrial, agricultural, district heating, public sector

			and other non-domestic heat users.
<u>Small-Scale Generation Support Scheme (SSG) in Ireland</u> [1]	Department of Environment, Climate and Communications	Tariff based support/ Financial instrument	DECC developing a support scheme for Small-Scale Generation (SSG) which will fill the gap in tariff-based supports and which aims to provide an easier route to market for community projects while also enabling farmers, businesses and others to maximise their participation in the energy transition.
<u>Biofuels Obligation Scheme</u> [65]	National Oil Reserves Agency Department of Environment, Climate and Communications	Obligation Scheme/ Financial Instrument	The BOS places an obligation on suppliers of mineral oil to ensure that 14.942% (by volume) of the motor fuel (generally gasoline and motor diesel) they place on the market in Ireland is produced from renewable sources, e.g. bioethanol and biodiesel.
<u>Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine Competitive Research Call</u> [66]	Department of Agriculture, Food and the Marine	Research call fund	A growing number of bioeconomy research projects such as <u>INFORMBIO</u> [67] and <u>NXTGENWOOD</u> [68] have been funded.
<u>Science Foundation Ireland funding</u> [69]	Provides grants for researchers from around the world who wish to relocate to Ireland and those already based in Ireland, for outstanding investigators, for conferences and symposia, and for collaboration with industry.	Funding/ grants	Funded BiOrbic Bioeconomy SFI Research Centre (also part funded by Industry)
<u>Springboard funding</u> [70]	Springboard/Higher Education Authority	Funding	Springboard have part funded the MSc in Bioeconomy Business run by MTU & UCD, while the HEA

			have funded the IKC3 projects.
<u>Project Ireland 2040 fund</u> [71]	Government of Ireland	Funding	Project Ireland 2040 fund including the Climate Action Fund has funded the Renewable Gas Forum Ireland <u>GRAZE project</u> [72] in the region
<u>LEADER Programme Funding</u> [73]	EU/ Department of Rural and Community Development	Funding	Funded Bioeconomy projects/initiatives. This <u>booklet</u> [74] showcases 10 Bioeconomy projects/initiatives supported by the LEADER Programme 2014-2020 throughout Ireland and within the region.
<u>EIP-AGRI</u> [75]	National Rural Network/ EU	Funding	Two projects funded through EIP-AGRI that work to implement the bioeconomy in the region are <u>Biomass to Biochar for Farm Bioeconomy</u> [76] which was focused on the mid-west-region of Ireland and <u>Biorefinery Glass-Small-Scale-Farmer led Green Biorefineries</u> [77] which was focused on the southwest of Ireland
<u>The National Waste Prevention Programme (NWPP)</u> [78]	Government of Ireland and Environmental Protection Agency	Funding	Supported national-level programmes to prevent waste and drive the circular economy. Provides funding programmes to develop novel solutions for the circular economy in priority areas such as food waste, construction and demolition, plastics, agriculture, resources and raw materials and waste prevention.
<u>EPA 'Green Enterprise: Innovation for a Circular Economy' annual funding programme.</u> [79]	EPA	Funding	Supports the demonstration of sustainable circular economy solutions and keeping products and materials in use for longer.

<u>The 'Circular Economy Innovation Grant Scheme (CEIGS) [80]</u>	Government of Ireland initiative	Grant scheme	Provides support to projects which work in the Circular Economy space.
<u>CIRCULÉIRE [81]</u>	Irish Manufacturing Research and the Department of the Environment, Climate and Communications (DECC), the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and EIT Climate-KIC	Innovation fund	Operate a 1.5 Mio euros ringfences innovation fund for manufacturing industry members.
Relevant funding EU	EU	Funding	Horizon Europe, EU LIFE Programme, Interreg Europe. Horizon Europe part funded <u>AgriChemWhey</u> [82] (which is also part funded by industry (Glanbia) in public private partnership). <u>Farm4More project</u> [83] is co-funded by Department of Environment, Climate and Communication and the EU Commission through LIFE.
<u>Enterprise Ireland's Green Transition Fund [84]</u>	Enterprise Ireland, EU	Funding	The Green Transition Fund will accelerate the decarbonisation of Irish enterprise. EI funded the Circular Bioeconomy Cluster South-West in the Southern Region. EI's REDF also funded the Bioconnect Centre and the Irish Bioeconomy Foundation Bioeconomy Piloting Facility.
<u>European Circular Bioeconomy Fund [85]</u>	EU	Funding	Funds and partners with ambitious and visionary entrepreneurs and investors to accelerate late-stage companies with first recurring revenues and strong market traction in the European circular bioeconomy.

<u>Community Climate Action Programme Fund [86]</u>	Department of Environment, Climate and Communication/ Pobal	Funding	Supports projects and initiatives that facilitate community climate action through education, capacity building and learning by doing. The programme is being run by Pobal, on behalf of the department
---	---	---------	---

There is no dedicated regional bioeconomy action plan. A national bioeconomy action plan is due to be published covering the 2023-2025 period.

National example- *The Climate Action Plan 2021* [38] sets out almost 500 actions to support Ireland's journey towards a 51% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2030 and carbon neutrality by 2050. In relation to the bioeconomy, the plan sets out targets such as that opportunities to expand both skills and funding mechanisms will be explored. Furthermore, on a national level there is also a *National Mitigation Plan* [87], *National Renewable Energy Action Plan* [88], *Offshore Renewable Energy Plan* [89], *National Energy Efficiency Action Plan* [90], *Action Plan for Rural Development* [20], *Bioenergy Action Plan* [91].

Regional example- *The Southern Region Waste Management Plan 2015-2021* [59] (being replaced by the National Waste Management Plan for a Circular Economy which is currently being prepared). The plan puts in place policy objectives and actions which align with European and national waste policy and support Ireland's move to an economy defined by higher resource efficiency and productivity. The plan is focused on recognising the important role the waste sector has to play in helping Ireland's households, businesses and industry in the transition towards a more resource efficient and circular economy. The waste management plan is a statutory document prepared by the local authorities of the region. In addition, on a regional level there is the *South-West Regional Enterprise Plan to 2024* [92] and the *South-East Regional Enterprise Plan to 2024* [93]. These plans have actions to encourage entrepreneurship and enhance the region's start up ecosystem. Ensure that the green economy becomes an engine for future job creation and economic growth in the region. Drive forward the agri-tech and food sectors and enhance company capability in the region by providing expert specialised training, a virtual testing facility, collaboration and learning spaces, testbed opportunities, business centres, state-of-the-art tech-based solutions under the four central pillars of sustainability, digitalisation, skills development and economic growth. Embrace the enterprise opportunities presented by climate action and to develop strategies to ensure that the region's progress to a low-carbon and digital society is a Just Transition. **Maximise the potential of digital enterprises and innovation hubs to support digitalisation, business growth, climate action and smart working. Embrace the opportunities of climate action in the marine, circular bioeconomy, tourism and energy sectors.**

Brief description of the short-/mid-/long-term actions and their monitoring system (including KPIs, deadlines)

The Climate Action Plan 2021 Bioeconomy/Circular economy Actions listed:

The main actions relating to the circular bioeconomy in CAP 2021 are:

- Publishing of a Whole-of Government Circular Economy Strategy,

- Enacting the Circular Economy Bill
- Establish a Circular Economy Innovation Scheme
- Strengthen the regulatory and enforcement frameworks for the waste collection and management system
- Reduce demand for virgin raw materials and support re-use,
- Continue to drive the rollout of *CIRCULÉIRE* [101], the national circular economy platform
- The Bioeconomy will be reflected across circular economy strategies and policies where relevant, and regulatory barriers will be examined
- Funding mechanisms for bioeconomy innovation at demonstration level will be explored
- Opportunities to increase skills in the bioeconomy will be explored
- Develop a policy statement on mineral exploration and mining that supports the sustainable supply of minerals required to transition to a climate neutral economy
- Develop a Food Waste Prevention Roadmap that sets out a series of actions to deliver the reductions necessary to halve our food waste by 2030 and promote our transition to a circular economy
- Education, training and skill gaps currently existed on the bioeconomy in Ireland will be identified and potential funding mechanisms for demonstration actions within the bioeconomy will be identified.
- **Support will be given to Regional Assemblies to identify areas of potential growth in the bioeconomy in their regions.**

The Climate Action Plan 2021 Bioeconomy Monitoring and measures listed to deliver targets:

- Monitor finalising the first Whole-of-Government Circular Economy Strategy
- Bringing the Circular Economy Bill 2021 through the Oireachtas. The High-Level National Bioeconomy Implementation Group will report to Government on the implementation of the National Bioeconomy Policy Statement by early 2022.
- The High-Level National Bioeconomy Implementation Group will set out a three-year action plan for the bioeconomy in 2022.
- The National Bioeconomy Forum will provide recommendations and advice to aid the advancement of the bioeconomy.
- National Bioeconomy Implementation Group will report to Government and develop a detailed Bioeconomy Action Plan in 2022.
- The Bioeconomy Forum will contribute to the development of actions in future iterations of key policies and strategies.

The Southern Region Waste Management Plan 2015-2021 circular bioeconomy Actions listed:

- Engage with and facilitate enterprises in the development of repair and preparing for reuse activities.
- Engage with the Community Reuse Network Ireland (CRNI) and other similar networks to develop a network of reuse/upcycling activities and promotional events.
- Produce a code of practice for local authority authorised facilities to maximise the quantity and quality of material produced.
- Liaise with and support Economic Development Departments of local authorities in the identification of enterprises and potential clusters of enterprises for the development of secondary material markets.
- Prepare resource efficiency criteria for local authority waste related contracts.

- Implement a systematic engagement with local or regional local authority procurement officers and the Office of Government Procurement (OGP) to ensure the inclusion of resource efficiency criteria in contracts.
- Encourage SMEs (including micro enterprises) and industry to realise the environmental and economic benefits of resource efficiency.

The Southern Region Waste Management Plan 2015-2021 monitoring:

Monitoring and reporting of the plan's implementation is a continuous process that requires regular review and refinement. This ensures that the implementation programme continues to be relevant, as well as assessing progress towards meeting targets. In order to ensure effective implementation, all waste data must be quantified, used consistently and reported in order to assess progress towards meeting EU targets. In addition to the policy action indicators, a series of primary and secondary statistical indicators known as key performance indicators (KPIs) have been developed.

Brief description of the follow-up and evaluation procedure of the action plan's performance:

Climate Action Plan 2021:

The Climate Action Delivery Board will ensure that each department and public body is held to account for the delivery of actions set out in the Climate Action Plan. The Board will also review key strategic projects and areas of work. *The first progress report* [94] was published in June 2022 and highlighted climate action progress achieved in both quarters, while also emphasising the need to address barriers to implementation.

The Southern Region Waste Management Plan:

There will be an annual review of performance by the regional waste office. The regional office recognises the need for the ongoing input of stakeholders to the implementation of this plan. It is proposed to provide stakeholders with an opportunity to provide feedback on the implementation of the plan, and to bring forward new proposals or innovations as they arise.

Economy-related indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

There is no dedicated circular bioeconomy strategy for the Southern Region, however, there is a *National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy* [39], a *Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy* [40] and regionally there is a *Regional, Spatial and Economic Strategy for the Southern Region* [41] which has specific Regional Policy Objectives (RPO) relating to the bioeconomy and circular economy in the region and its implementation and promotion. For the RSES, The Regional Development Monitor (RDM) which the Southern Regional Assembly was involved in developing, is to be launched shortly and will be entirely focussed on Indicators.

Also, the RSES Implementation Programme and RSES Two Year Monitoring report can be used for identifying indicators.

Regional, Spatial and Economic Strategy (RSES) for Southern Region economy related regional policy objectives and indicators:

- Development of the rural economy through supporting a sustainable and economically efficient agricultural and food sector, together with the bioeconomy.
- Transition towards low carbon economy and circular economy through mechanisms such as the Climate Action Competitive Fund.
- Development of enterprises that create and employ green technologies.
- Development of social enterprises and the circular economy within local communities to benefit environmental protection, employment generation and community development.

- The sustainable development of the Lisheen Bioeconomy Hub site into a significant economic and employment driver with the potential to significantly contribute towards meeting Ireland's climate change targets as a strategic site of European significance.
- Investment in research relating to the circular bioeconomy in the Southern Region (EUROS)
- Jobs created in SMEs relating to products or services in the circular bioeconomy in the Southern Region
- Grant supports and private investment in projects.

Societal indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

Regional, Spatial and Economic Strategy (RSES) for Southern Region societal regional policy objectives and indicators:

- Development of the rural economy through supporting a sustainable and economically efficient agricultural and food sector, together with the bioeconomy.
- Local authorities including objectives in statutory land use plans promoting energy conservation, energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources
- Development of social enterprises and the circular economy within local communities to benefit environmental protection, employment generation and community development.

Environmental indicators are used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

Regional, Spatial and Economic Strategy (RSES) for Southern Region environmental regional policy objectives and indicators:

- Development of the rural economy through supporting a sustainable and economically efficient agricultural and food sector, together with the bioeconomy.
- Transition to a low carbon future and the transition towards low carbon economy and circular economy
- Development of enterprises that create and employ green technologies
- Local authorities ensuring that the development of green industry and technologies incorporates careful consideration of potential environmental impacts at project level including the capacity of receiving environment and existing infrastructure to serve new industries.
- Local authorities including objectives in statutory land use plans promoting energy conservation, energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources
- The sustainable development of the Lisheen Bioeconomy Hub site into a significant economic and employment driver with the potential to significantly contribute towards meeting Ireland's climate change targets as a strategic site of European significance.
- Development of social enterprises and the circular economy within local communities to benefit environmental protection, employment generation and community development.
- Develop a Regional Decarbonisation Plan to provide a framework for action on decarbonisation across all sectors. The Plan shall include existing and future targets for each sector. Implementation mechanisms and monitoring structures shall be established with stakeholders, including the Climate Action Regional Offices, following the adoption of the RSES to identify the scope and role of the Plan.
- Support the National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy (2018)
- Support the preparation of a Bio-energy Implementation Plan for the Southern Region in conjunction with the Local Authorities and the Regional Waste Management office

Existing initiatives from front-runners and/or regions with the same bioeconomy profile/approach to emulate/follow:

As Denmark are leading the way in a grass/clover-based bioeconomy there is a link there for Ireland and the Southern Region to emulate a Danish model. The Danish landscape, similar to Ireland and the Southern Region, is dominated by agriculture. The Danish case is an important example of how environmental sustainability has been addressed in an intensively managed country with a high proportion of agricultural land. The Central Denmark Region is home to a unique cluster of knowledge and industry targeting effective production, logistics and conversion of bio-resources to high-value bio-based products.

Nationally, there are similarities with Scotland and there has been collaboration - similar population, and similar primary sectors, industries and residues (grass, tillage, brewing/distillery wastes, dairy wastes, slurries, meat by-products etc.). Initiatives such as Zero Waste Scotland [42], IBioIC [43], Circular North East [44] etc.) would be put forward as front runners in the bioeconomy to emulate.

Flexibility of the circular bioeconomy strategy in your territory to accommodate the needs of the territory:

There is no regional circular bioeconomy strategy in place in the Southern Region, so there is a clear gap for a regional focused strategy that accommodates and is flexible the bioeconomy needs of the region. However, The Regional Spatial and Economic Strategy for the Southern Region (RSES) [95] has a regional planning objective to facilitate the development of the rural economy through supporting a sustainable and economically efficient agricultural and food sector, together with the bioeconomy, subject to required environmental assessment processes where necessary and balanced with the importance of maintaining and protecting the natural landscape. Therefore, the RSES recognises and works towards accommodating the needs of the region when it comes to the bioeconomy with a balanced and sustainable approach.

When looking at national strategies in place, we do see regional references. For example, in the Government of Ireland's Climate Action Plan 2021 [38] Action 363 states that support will be given to Regional Assemblies (including the Southern Regional Assembly) to identify areas of potential growth in the bioeconomy. The National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy [39] recognises the potential for the bioeconomy to boost employment not only nationally, but also regionally. One of the key objectives of the statement is regional prosperity, and that by helping the bioeconomy to grow regionally it can assist in halting rural decline.

6.3.5 Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy

Main strengths for implementing the circular bioeconomy in the region:

- Strong agri-food sector and availability of Feedstocks
 - Agricultural / Marine / Industry side stream
- Promising bio-based products emerging
 - More value-added products
- Strong Bioeconomy Education & Research sector – MTU, UCC etc
- Existing Biobased industries – Bioatlantis, Nutramara etc

Main weaknesses for applying the circular bioeconomy in the region:

- Often the capital expenditure, and lack of scale-up facilities along with the long route to market for some processes and products are prohibitive for companies.

- In addition, further work is required to engage suppliers of biomass, and end users, on the potential benefits of the bioeconomy to ensure their participation.
- Investment is needed in key Bioeconomy infrastructure particularly new biorefinery infrastructure.
- Stakeholders are often operating in silo's
- Policy constraints
- Need for policy development / review in relation to circular bioeconomy

Main opportunities for implementing the circular bioeconomy in the region:

- Rising Costs of synthetic farm inputs e.g.: Fertilisers, proteins, with bio-based alternatives coming to market.
- Opportunity to reduce import dependence as Ireland is currently dependent on imported energy, chemicals, plastics, fertilisers, feed and more.
- Complete valorisation of existing feedstocks, pushing value up the 'biobased value pyramid' - Marine Sector – extracting inputs for pharmaceutical sector.
- Creating a just transition for agriculture and revitalizing rural and coastal regions with new companies and jobs.
- Developing a circular bioeconomy based on sustainable supply chains can aid in the reduction of GHG emissions and help to meet climate targets.

Main threats for applying the circular bioeconomy in the region:

- Lack of investment capital for pilot and demonstration level initiatives
- Ensuring adequate skills exist to meet the emerging needs
- Ensuring that members/stakeholders involved and impacted by the bioeconomy (e.g. public, consumers, farmers) are fully engaged
- Ensuring that the biomass is managed and harvested sustainably and the trade-offs of developing a bioeconomy are fully considered
- Lack of support for companies innovating and scaling in this space
- Lack of support in connecting and support the various actors in their collaborations

Concrete and main specific potential measures/tools that can be developed in the region/sector to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices from circular bioeconomy in priority sectors/value chains in the region:

A key action within the Climate Action Plan is supporting regional assemblies in understanding areas of potential growth in the bioeconomy. There are several potential tools which could be used to support this activity. Firstly, understanding the potential of biomass from various sectors, and understanding how this may be used. Several projects including INFORMBIO, MainstreamBIO, Be-Rural, Power4Bio can help inform this work and approaches for mapping of feedstocks, technologies and business cases for developing regional bioeconomies. Peer-learning activities and exchanges of best practices through international and interregional site visits, learning and networking events, can also support in build capacity in regions, examples of this activity can be found in projects like COOPID and Power4Bio. Several opportunities exist to develop identified opportunities, first at lower technology readiness levels (TRL) through established research centres, and later scaling these through pilot and demonstration activities with regional R&D and industry partners. However, supported in infrastructure and investment for scale-up is key. In Europe, the Public-Private-Partnership model of the Biobased Industries Joint Undertaking (now CBE JU) has played a key role in supporting bioeconomy scale up. Setting appropriate policy, including measurable targets is also of key importance. The important role of clusters in connecting the various value chain stakeholders in the region is already being seen in the Southern Region.

Lessons learnt from the circular bioeconomy policy so far:

In the region we do not have a circular bioeconomy or bioeconomy policy strategy so this represents a gap.

At national level, some lessons to date include realising the bioeconomy is a very diverse sector, and that trades off within the bioeconomy occur and need to be fully analysed. In addition, policy coherence across the various departments is required but is difficult to achieve, as there is a need to balance different needs. This is also true of the bioeconomy overall, where many stakeholders have often competing needs (i.e. primary producers need a return for their residues, but industry want low cost biomass and consumers want affordable products). We also see that need for definitive and measurable actions and targets as a critical component of policy development.

6.4 Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Zilina region case

6.4.1 Regional and local peculiarities

The region where the circular bioeconomy strategy is applied:

The Žilina self-governing region is situated in the north-western part of Slovakia and is the third largest region in the Slovak Republic. It borders the Czech Republic in the west and Poland in the north. It also shares the borders with three other Slovak regions – Trenčín, Banská Bystrica and Prešov. It includes 5 subregions (Horné Považie, Kysuce, Liptov, Orava and Turiec) and 11 districts (Bytča, Čadca, Dolný Kubín, Kysucké Nové Mesto, Liptovský Mikuláš, Martin, Námestovo, Ružomberok, Turčianske Teplice, Tvrdošín and Žilina). The Žilina Region is the third largest region of the Slovak Republic by area and occupies 13.9% of the state's area.

Total area: 6809 km²

Number of inhabitants: 690 434

Population density (per km²): 101.4

Seat of the ŽSR: Žilina

Number of district towns: 11

Number of towns: 8

Number of villages: 296"

Characterization of the area(s) of intervention (urban, peri-urban, semi-rural, rural, coastal). More than one could apply:

urban, peri-urban, semi-rural, rural

Priority and potential regional sectors/value chains for the circular bioeconomy (agriculture, livestock, agroindustry, forest, chemical industry, energy, maritime, water, etc):

The region has a long tradition in mechanical engineering (railway equipment, bearings, special machinery and tools), which was followed by the automotive industry. The leader of the regional economic growth is the South Korean car producer KIA Motors that has realized the largest foreign

investment in the region. Forestry plays an important role as woodlands cover 50 % of the region. Due to the rich wood resources, wood processing, pulp and papermaking industries are well-established in the region. The territory is abundant of mineral springs, several of them with healing effects, what significantly contributes to the development of spa and wellness services as well as beverage sector. Another fast-growing and promising field of economy is tourism.

Baseline situation of the territory (region), and locally available feedstocks/biomass from the mentioned sectors/value chains (residues, by-products, food waste, plastic, bio-waste, marine debris, etc. from agriculture, agri-food, maritime, bio-waste, etc.):

Since agricultural plant and animal production is not very widespread in the Žilina Region, therefore, the energy potential is mainly represented by wood biomass. The Žilina region is characterized by very significant stocks of wood biomass, which also depends on the number of woodworking companies producing waste wood biomass (offcuts, sawdust, wood chips) suitable for energy purposes.

Brief assessment of the "territorial sensitivity" of the region for the development of the circular bioeconomy, with consideration of the importance of the circular bioeconomy in the region currently [Territorial (regional) sensitivity to bioeconomy development can be described as the degree to which a territory (region) can potentially be directly or indirectly affected, either adversely or beneficially by an increase of the circular bioeconomy in the territory (region)]:

Diversification of activities of agricultural and forestry entities related to the introduction of circular bioeconomy, coobtaining and processing biomass, waste_economy, wood processing, etc.

Brief assessment of the "exposure" of the region to the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy, with consideration of the scale of its effect (economic, social, environmental) in the region [Exposure to bioeconomy is the degree to which the bioeconomy is part of the regional economy currently. Describe in economic (e.g. GDP), social (e.g. employment) and environmental terms]:

With a few exceptions, the volumes of wood salvaged from natural losses (salvage fellings) consistently represent more than half of total fellings (actual logging) and have continuously increased since 2000, in line with planned logging that increases on average by 4% annually. The use of renewable resources in Žilina region is estimated to be very small compared to its potential.

Bridging elements, synergies and platforms between traditional (agri-food, fisheries, livestock etc.) sectors, industry, research, technology and public administration [i.e., who (agents) or what (agencies) may facilitate (bridge) the aforementioned QH actors. It could be formal (legislation) or informal. Please provide specifics]:

A key role in the coordination of the implementation of the bioeconomy in the Žilina Region within the ŽSK Office is represented by the Regional Department_development.

6.4.2 Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies

Description of the level of development of the strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in the region and how they were developed. Analysis whether a circular bioeconomy strategy exists on standalone mode, or as a part of a broader mix of strategies (with links to relevant strategy(-ies) if available):

In accordance with the Social and economic development plan 2021+, the Žilina Region plans to implement the principles of bioeconomy and prepare to achieve the goals of the European Union.

Implementation of bioeconomy principles in the region

Involvement of the region in innovative projects in the field of bioeconomy

Incorporation of bioeconomy principles into regional public procurement

Support for building a network of product reuse centers in the region.

Description of the planning instruments, policies, measures, supporting schemes and other interventions available that comprise the circular bioeconomy strategy:

Strategy for bioeconomy in Slovakia

Contribution of Slovak Bioeconomy to the Strategic Plan 2021-2027

Connection between the circular bioeconomy strategy and other related strategies (Sustainable Development Goals, S3, Climate change, etc), with description of interconnections/synergies in terms of common objectives or actions with other regions and/or national strategies or plans objectives:

In accordance with the Social and economic development plan 2021+, the Žilina Region plans to implement the principles of bioeconomy and prepare to achieve the goals of the European Union.

Implementation of bioeconomy principles in the region

Involvement of the region in innovative projects in the field of bioeconomy

Incorporation of bioeconomy principles into regional public procurement

Support for building a network of product reuse centers in the region.

Strategic vision/s and objectives of the circular bioeconomy strategy in the territory (region):

In accordance with the Social and economic development plan 2021+, the Žilina Region plans to implement the principles of bioeconomy and prepare to achieve the goals of the European Union.

Implementation of bioeconomy principles in the region

Involvement of the region in innovative projects in the field of bioeconomy

Incorporation of bioeconomy principles into regional public procurement

Support for building a network of product reuse centers in the region.

Existence of bio-based solutions integrated to existing systems/processes or independent [i.e., is the bioeconomy sector been developed as an independent sector or are bio-based solutions integrated into existing systems and processes]:

NO

Brief description of the level of public awareness and acceptance of the circular bioeconomy strategy [Level of awareness among the general population (public) of the region:

High/medium/low.]:

Low level of information and public awareness on the advantages of biological products compared to fossil products, bioeconomy – hardly comprehensible terminology for public.

Brief description of the degree of concern, interest, and knowledge of farmers/producers/businesses (stakeholders) about the circular bioeconomy strategies available, the problem of waste, etc., and the circularity opportunities (marketing, social, etc):

Growing interest of society (especially the young generation) in topics close to bioeconomy.

6.4.3 The QH actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system

Policy departments in local and regional administrations currently involved in the development and the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main responsible administrations):

A key role in the coordination of the implementation of the bioeconomy in the Žilina Region within the ŽSK Office is represented by the Regional Department development.

Policy departments in local and regional administrations that should also be involved in the future or have shown interest in being involved (in particular those in charge of economic development, agriculture and rural development, environment and climate, research and innovation):

Department of the environment.

Working groups among administrative departments involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy:

NO

Specific clusters developed, with brief description of the bioeconomy related clusters operating in the territory:

Bioeconomy Cluster (BEC) is an association of legal entities founded in December 2015 with the aim of promoting cooperation in the field of innovation and mutual exchange of information between cluster members, who are primarily representatives of the business sphere (companies in the agricultural and food sector), representatives of research, development and education. representatives of regional and local governments and, last but not least, representatives of the third sector.

Previous co-creation initiatives towards governance models/structures/policies:

NO

People's attitudes towards co-creation with policy makers:

Growing interest of society (especially the young generation) in topics close to bioeconomy

Existence of a bioeconomy strategy council or similar structure overseeing the policy:

NO

Brief description of the main actors (stakeholders) in the territory for the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main partners):

A key role in the coordination of the implementation of the bioeconomy in the Žilina Region within the ŽSK Office is represented by the Regional Department.

Main leadership role owner, to steer and facilitate the development of circular bioeconomy in the territory:

The Regional Department of the Žilina self-governing region plays a key role in coordinating the implementation of bioeconomy in the Žilina region.

Existence of civil society organizations (CSOs) and/or non-governmental organizations (NGOs) involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy, with brief description:

NO

Common priorities of the actors involved in circular bioeconomy activities (consider society, business, knowledge, administration and capital representatives):

Agriculture and rural areas play an important role in development bioeconomy, because agriculture and forestry represent a large part of biomass production. For this reason, there is a need to support investments in production and use of biomass, which at the same time supports natural values and becomes economically attractive for entrepreneurs in the countryside.

Existence of diversity of perspectives and interests among them, with explanation:

There are several integrated within the RIS3 domain "Healthy food and environment". development trends in the sectors of agriculture, forestry and logging, which were designed based on the identification of areas of common interest of companies and research and development organizations, and which create synergies with the proposed focus investment activities mentioned above. These integrated development trends domains include:

1. Sustainable and competitive primary agricultural and forestry production resources
2. Production of safe, health-supporting foods with high nutritional value and added value value
3. New technologies of mechanical, chemical and energy processing of agricultural and forest biomass into products with high added value
4. Complex technologies and systems for reducing the negative impacts of agriculture activities on the environment, protection and sustainable use of land and water in changing climatic conditions.

Role of public authorities in bringing together the QH actors:

In accordance with the Social and economic development plan 2021+, the Žilina Region plans to implement the principles of bioeconomy and prepare to achieve the goals of the European Union.

Intermediary organizations that operate as bridges/links between clusters/sectors:

NO

Existence of specialized technology, research and innovation centers within the bioeconomy governance system, analysis of their interconnectivity and their role:

At the level of the Slovak Republic: human capacities - high-quality individual researchers (in various organizations),

- the research infrastructure relevant to the bioeconomy is AgroBioTech research center,
- know-how, tradition and experience with innovations and implementation new technologies scientific research base,
- the scientific research base of the forestry sector is established in the international research space,
- significant research results achieved in the field of bioenergetics, including demonstration biogasstation.

6.4.4 The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs)

Financial instruments available for the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

To support the bioeconomy 2021 -2027 in the Slovak Republic, it is proposed to allocate 40 EUR million from public funds through at least 2 interventions:

1) Investments - in the amount of 35 mil. EUR, of which:

- a. investments in innovative technologies in the field of bioeconomy in the amount of 20 mil. EUR,
- b. investments in renewable sources, especially in local energy sources in the amount of 15 mil. EUR.

2) Cooperation - in the amount of 5 mil. EUR through created operational

groups in the field of bioeconomy (within pilot projects, local cooperation, or relevant short supply chains).

Small projects will be supported under the LEADER initiative. Such projects will make it possible to support the competitiveness and sustainable development of industries, including improvement of environmental protection procedures at the local level.

Are there actions plans, by sector, stream or product/service:

Draft National Action Plan for Development bioeconomy in the Slovak Republic with the aim of supporting the development of the "green economy" in the future

planning period from 2020. It follows from consultations with national and international experts that the green economy sector has a significant development potential and may within a decade to reach the turnover of the automotive industry, while it will use domestic resources. The national action plan for the development of bioeconomy in Slovakia defines three main areas bioeconomy, namely:

- Efficient agriculture

including land care and irrigation development, food production and development food industry and the production of second-generation biofuels.

- Efficient forestry

including forest protection, efficient mining technologies, circular and cascading wood processing with high added value and obtaining energy from wood biomass.

- Waste Management

including energy processing of waste and minimization of landfills"

Brief description of the short-/mid-/long-term actions and their monitoring system (including KPIs, deadlines):

Every year there is an evaluation of the implementation of the social and economic development plan of the Žilina Region (PHSR ŽSK) and the Action Plan of the ŽSK Office for the previous year. Filling of specific goals is evaluated using the indicator system report and published in the PHSR Implementation Report

ŽSK. Subsequently, proposals for modifying the Action Plan of the ŽSK Office are collected so that they can be approved By the representative office of ŽSK. The first evaluation Report on the implementation of the PHSR ŽSK 2021+ will be prepared for the year 2023, i.e. j. in 2024.

Brief description of the follow-up and evaluation procedure of the action plan's performance:

The report on the implementation of the PHSR ŽSK 2021+ processed once a year must contain the following information:

- Main part – Manager's summary of the implementation of PHSR ŽSK 2021+ and the Action Plan of the Office of ŽSK (overall summary implementation of the PHSR ŽSK 2021+ in the previous period with an indication of the main findings);
- Proposals of key measures for the following year;
- Appendix – Data update and comments on filling in indicators.

Economy-related indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The most relevant outcome indicator based on interventions for the field of bioeconomy, the indicator is Rural Development bioeconomy: number of supported enterprises operating in bioeconomy. This indicator will be used for monitoring and evaluation of the benefits of bioeconomy support.

Societal indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

Growing interest of society (especially the young generation) in topics close to bioeconomy. Creation of thematic and cross-sectoral excellent teams from among researchers (from various organizations) and the business sphere in order to implement results more effectively research and innovation into practice, Incentive measures in the field of research and innovation, tax policy, the availability of qualified labor and specifically measures at the national and regional level, including the state level policy e.g. structure and amount of local taxes, mobility support and participation in international projects.

Environmental indicators are used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The number of projects that are aimed at supporting adaptation to impacts of climate change in the Žilina region.

Existing initiatives from front-runners and/or regions with the same bioeconomy profile/approach to emulate/follow:

The Self-governing Region of Trenčín (TSR) is aware of environmental issues and even in spite of its low competencies in this area it has proceeded to the implementation of the Green regional administration project since 2015. It aims to decrease the negative impacts on the environment from its own operations, including from the operation of the facilities within the competencies of the region. Its target is also to increase the environmental awareness of citizens of the TSR."

Flexibility of the circular bioeconomy strategy in your territory to accommodate the needs of the territory:

In accordance with the Social and economic development plan 2021+, the Žilina Region plans to implement the principles of bioeconomy and prepare to achieve the goals of the European Union.

Implementation of bioeconomy principles in the region

Involvement of the region in innovative projects in the field of bioeconomy

Incorporation of bioeconomy principles into regional public procurement

Support for building a network of product reuse centers in the region.

6.4.5 Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT Analysis)

Main strengths for implementing the circular bioeconomy in the region:

Significant production potential of the region in forest land and water resources (historically, geographically, in terms of climatic conditions),

structure and character of agricultural enterprises - concentrated agricultural production,

the multifunctional nature of the forestry that it provides amount of biomass, biomaterials, bioproducts and fillings important ecological functions, inclusion of the majority of forests in the economic category forests with a primary wood production function.

Main weaknesses for applying the circular bioeconomy in the region:

Frequent calamities and the resulting high volume accidental logging inefficient use of biomass (including waste) as raw material for further processing the unclear position of agriculture within the national priorities,

the absence of a regional strategy for the bioeconomy,

inconsistency and fragmentation of policies relevant to the area bioeconomy and the ambiguity of its position and role in development policies,

inconsistency of methodologies for policy making in the area bioeconomy,

lack and unavailability of data for creating a strategy for bioeconomy and its subsequent monitoring and evaluation.

Main opportunities for implementing the circular bioeconomy in the region:

Development of business activities in the countryside and creation of new ones value chains within the circular bioeconomy obtaining and processing biomass, waste economy, wood processing, etc., growing demand for biomass causing the need to increase production by increasing yields per hectare (limited options increase in cultivation areas) while simultaneously taking into account environmental criteria and requirements for the protection of life environment,

increasing the contribution of the forestry and timber sector to the green sector of the economy within its potential for increasing employment,

efficient use of resources, mitigating climate change, production of renewable energy, low-carbon economy,

strengthening advice on topics in the field of bioeconomy,

increase in the share of domestic production with higher added value value and with a higher form of processing by use biotechnologies and innovative technologies,

use of digitization and innovative technologies.

Main threats for applying the circular bioeconomy in the region:

Bioeconomy solutions will not be from an economic point of view more effective compared to fossil-based products,

- competitive use of land for the production of food and fodder for animals and for the production of renewable resources for material use and for energy use,
- access to wood raw material – increased competition for wood as a raw material, especially due to the growing demand for renewable energy

departure of executive scientists due to lack of continuity of funding.

Concrete and main specific potential measures/tools that can be developed in the region/sector to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices from circular bioeconomy in priority sectors/value chains in the region:

Cooperation with international excellent workplaces and competence centers,

support the development of clusters and associations in the bioeconomy as driving mechanisms to support cooperation to change the social paradigm through a strong European support in the area of using wood as ecological, renewable and recyclable raw material, permanently active sustainable forest management, efficient use domestic sources of wood raw material.

Lessons learnt from the circular bioeconomy policy so far:

Using the creativity and imagination of the public in the creation of policies,

projects, innovations and solutions both everyday and social problems in the field of bioeconomy,

- support of bioeconomy through social networks and involving the general public (including young people) in discussions,
- education of farmers in the field of sustainable, low-carbon and circular bioeconomy,

- development of new educational programs and scientific fields related to the bioeconomy (e.g. in the field of biotechnology).

6.5 Circular bioeconomy policy mix: the Andalusia case

6.5.1 Regional and local peculiarities

The region where the circular bioeconomy strategy is applied:

The bioeconomy strategy is implemented in the whole Andalusian region. It is the most populated Spanish region and the second largest. The region has eight provinces of Almería, Cádiz, Córdoba, Granada, Huelva, Jaén, Málaga, and Seville.

Andalusia surface area is 87.597 km², representing 17% of the Spanish area, and 2% of the EU27 area. It has around 8.500.000 inhabitants (17,9% of total inhabitants of Spain), of which 1.995.165 are in rural areas. Andalusia has a population density (97 people per square kilometre) a little bit higher than in Spain (94 people per km²).

Agricultural activities are the main source of employment in half of the Andalusian municipalities. Fruits and vegetable production predominate in the area such as tomatoes, cucumbers, peppers, onions, watermelons, lettuces, etc. These agricultural products are typically produced following intensive practices in greenhouses. There are extensive vineyards and citrus and berries farms.

The Utilised Agricultural Area (UAA) in Andalusia is 4.399.491 hectares and accounts for 19.9% of the total UAA of Spain. Moreover, Andalusia is the first region in the final agricultural production in Spain. This way, agriculture is a key economic, environmental, and social sector in Andalusia. The most important tree crop is olive.

The Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita in Andalusia is 19.991 € (datum 2021-IECA) compared with 25.500 € in Spain and 32.300 in EU27.

Characterization of the area(s) of intervention (urban, peri-urban, semi-rural, rural, coastal). More than one could apply:

The area intervention in Andalusia is mixed: urban, peri-urban, semi-rural, rural, and coastal. The following areas stand out: meadows, pastures, countryside, olive growing, low part of the Guadalquivir River, coastline, Betic mountain range, and capital cities.

Priority and potential regional sectors/value chains for the circular bioeconomy (agriculture, livestock, agroindustry, forest, chemical industry, energy, maritime, water, etc)

The potential sectors for the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia are as follows:

- Agriculture.
- Livestock.
- Forestry and silviculture.
- Fishing and aquaculture.

- Agri-food industry: olive sector industry.
- Food, drinks, and tobacco industry.
- Bio-based textile industry.
- Wood and furniture industry.
- Paper industry.
- Bio-based chemical, pharmaceutical, plastics and rubber industries.
- Bioelectricity production.

The value chains for the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia are:

- Sustainable production and availability of biomass resources.
- Industrial Biomass processing and bioproducts and bioenergy industrial production (biorefineries, bioindustries, integrated biorefineries).
- Market development for bioproducts and bioenergy.

Baseline situation of the territory (region), and locally available feedstocks/biomass from the mentioned sectors/value chains (residues, by-products, food waste, plastic, bio-waste, marine debris, etc. from agriculture, agri-food, maritime, bio-waste, etc.):

The following are resources to obtain bioproducts and bioenergy:

- Residual biomass from crops (plant debris from arable crops).
- Biomass from pruning waste.
- Livestock waste and by-products: purines, manures, and parts of animals not intended for human consumption.
- Discards and by-products from the fishing industry.
- Forest biomass.
- By-products of the agri-food industry.
- Algal biomass: industrial CO₂ is included as a resource for algal biomass production.
- Biowaste (at the local level and other organic waste).
- Sludge and effluents from sewage systems.

Brief assessment of the "territorial sensitivity" of the region for the development of the circular bioeconomy, with consideration of the importance of the circular bioeconomy in the region currently
The importance of the bioeconomy has been estimated in Andalusia using the same information sources used by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) and applying as biological quota the ones calculated for the estimation of the indicators for Spain.

The Andalusian bioeconomy accounts for around 345.000 jobs in the region in 2017. It is found that the weight of the agricultural sector in the employment generated by the bioeconomy in Andalusia, was even greater than for the EU or Spain, reaching 77.5% in 2017.

In Andalusia, the value added of the bioeconomy was 13.711 Mio euros worth in 2017, and the agriculture sector is also the one that contributes the most (76.2%), together with the food,

beverages, and tobacco industries (17.4%). The agriculture contribution to the added value is thus much higher than at the state and European levels.

In Andalusia, the gross value added of bioeconomy per capita amounts in 2017 to almost 39.700 euros per person employed in the sector.

In Andalusia, turnover amounted to 35.276 Mio euros in 2017, denoting in the sectoral distribution the predominance of the agro-industrial sector, followed by the agricultural sector, as occurs in the European Union and Spain.

Brief assessment of the "exposure" of the region to the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy, with consideration of the scale of its effect (economic, social, environmental) in the region

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy is in the process of being implemented with a framework until 2030. When the implementation of ABCS starts, an interim report will analyse the impact of the Strategy on the region's bioeconomy.

Bridging elements, synergies and platforms between traditional (agri-food, fisheries, livestock etc.) sectors, industry, research, technology and public administration

The launch of the Andalusian Cluster of Circular Bioeconomy is planned as part of the actions proposed in the EABC. The Cluster will involve all the interested actors of the quadruple helix traditional sectors (agri-food, fisheries, livestock, etc.), industry, research, technology, and public administration.

Linked to the agri-food industry, the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Observatory (HortObserTIC) has been created, as a platform to foster the circular bioeconomy in the horticulture sector. Another operational group is OLEOVALORIZA, which is focused on circular agro-innovation and aimed to achieve an integrated waste valorisation for a sustainable olive sector.

Furthermore, the Andalusian Regional Ministry, and other regional organisations, have developed the Andalusia Agrotech Digital Innovation Hub. Andalusia Agrotech DIH is a digital ecosystem where the needs of a diverse and dynamic agri-food sector, the technological services of technology, information, and communication (ICT) companies, the innovation capacity of knowledge centres, and public programs of support from the public administration.

On the other hand, the Regional Ministry is also the leading region of the S3P Partnership on Traceability and Big Data in the agrifood value chain in which the regional node participates CTA and IFAPA.

Also, the Technological Corporation of Andalusia (CTA) is a multisectoral innovation cluster that covers biotech and agrifood areas and promotes technology transfer from academia to the private sector. From CTA side, and through the participation in European Commission funded projects (H2020, HEurope and BBI-JU), interaction and connection with all stakeholders is pursued and triggered. Some examples of these projects are ICT-BIOCHAIN, BIOSWITCH, urBIOfuture, BioBEC, Scale-up and BIOTRANSFORM among others. It is worth highlight the project A3Bio (regional funding), devoted to mapping and assessing regional capacities related to services in the bioeconomy field.

Furthermore, the Campus of International Excellence in Agrifood ceiA3 is the result of the integration of the Universities of Almería, Cádiz, Huelva, and Jaén, led by the University of Córdoba. It has developed a Master's in Circular Bioeconomy and Sustainability. Besides, ceiA3 is a member of the Management Committee of the Spanish Bioeconomy Observatory.

6.5.2 Positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies

Description of the level of development of the strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in the region and how they were developed. Analysis whether a circular bioeconomy strategy exists on standalone mode, or as a part of a broader mix of strategies

In July 2016, the Regional Government of Andalusia decided to launch the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy (ACBS) to contribute to the sustainable growth and competitiveness of the region. This sets Andalusia as one of the first regions in Spain to foresee the opportunities that the bioeconomy has to offer.

The ACBS was developed by the Regional Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock, Fisheries and Sustainable Development (CAGPDS by its name in Spanish) and approved by the Andalusian Government on September 18th, 2018.

With the support of EU funding, the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy project promotes sustainable growth and regional development by fostering the production of renewable and biological products and processes.

The targeted sectors include agriculture, forestry, fishing, food, and paper production, as well as part of the chemical, biotechnology, and energy industries.

The strategy works with a timeframe for 2030 and has resources worth around 1400 Mio euros, aimed at specific actions that have been developed with the collaboration of more than 50 external experts from the sectors of interest.

Andalusian circular bioeconomy strategy [96]

Andalusian sustainable development strategy [97]

Description of the planning instruments, policies, measures, supporting schemes and other interventions available that comprise the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The strategy will be implemented through a set of four instrumental programs of a transversal nature: communication and awareness, promotion of R+D+i and education, access to financing, and cooperation and collaboration. In total, 17 measures and 39 actions have been defined.

Aside from this, the government has promoted the creation of rural development working groups aiming to boost the agri-food sector in rural areas. Concerning regulation, the regional government will soon pass the regional Law for the Circular Economy. Also, in 2021, the "Andalusian Overall Plan for Waste. Towards a Circular Economy in 2030 Horizon" (PIRec 2030) was approved.

Cross-sector, cross-policy, and cross-border/inter-region analysis of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The focus of the ACBS is the development of activities among three segments of the bioeconomy value chain: the production of biomass, the technical processing, and the consumer markets. In addition, the general aim is to involve all actors of the fourfold approach: knowledge centres, administrations, companies, and citizens.

S3 (smart specialization strategies) implementation in the region:

On 18 December 2012, the Andalusian Governing Council agreed to begin work on the drafting of the Andalusian Innovation Strategy, RIS3Andalusia 2020, which was finally approved by the Agreement of 15 February 2015.

The Andalusian Regional Government carried out the mid-term evaluation of its Innovation Strategy 2020, RIS3Andalusia, between March and June 2019 through the Andalusian Agency for Innovation and Development, the IDEA Agency, acting as the Technical Secretariat for the Strategy design and Implementation. It considers the first phase of the implementation period (2014-2018) with the final objective to guide the decision-making process for the rest of the implementation framework.

RIS3Andalusia had a positive influence in the formulation of different regional strategies, plans, and programmes where key Smart Specialisation components were adopted. Notably, both Entrepreneurial Discovery Process and the RIS3 governance were integrated into specific development strategies in the fields of ICT, Energy, Bioeconomy, and Health). Most of them have developed a participatory approach that follows the RIS3 perspective, involved regional actors and stakeholders as part of their governance scheme, and endorsed the 8 regional specialisation priorities. Moreover, the Andalusian Industrial Strategy (EIA2020) is a relevant example, with the creation of dedicated working groups to ensure the integration of RIS3 priorities in its strategy implementation. Besides, the Andalusian Plan for R&D&I (PAIDI2020) has also endorsed the RIS3 priorities that serve as the basis for all the activities it supports.

However, the mid-term review also indicates a low integration of the RIS3 Andalusia priorities in the decision-making processes of managing entities. Several bottlenecks have been identified related to the i) administrative structure and governmental changes; ii) limited institutional support and members' participation mainly due to the low number of sessions held during the period 2015-2018; iii) the Andalusian Knowledge Agents have a reduced knowledge of RIS3Andalusia.

Connection between the circular bioeconomy strategy and other related strategies (Sustainable Development Goals, S3, Climate change, etc), with description of interconnections/synergies in terms of common objectives or actions with other regions and/or national strategies or plans objectives:

The Structural Funds and Investment Funds of Andalusia (2014-2020) have already favoured the development of policies related to the bioeconomy in terms of innovation, business development, research, and training. Both the EAFRD Operative Programme of Andalusia and the Rural Development Programme of Andalusia 2014-2020 (RDP) contain key priority elements for the bioeconomy such as improved efficiency in the use of resources or the transition to a low carbon economy. In the same way, the underlying principles of the Operative Programme for the European Maritime and Fisheries Fund 2014-2020, are helping fishermen in the transition towards more sustainable fishing, helping the coastal communities to diversify their economies, financing projects to create jobs and improve the quality of life in the European coastal areas.

Other horizontal strategic plans of the Regional Government of Andalusia are the Agenda for Employment, the Economic Plan of Andalusia 2014-2020, the Strategy for Competitiveness, the Andalusia Innovation Strategy 2020-RIS3 Andalusia and the Andalusian Plan for Research, Development and, Innovation-Spanish (PAIDI) 2020. In addition, other more specific plans are the Andalusian Industrial Strategy 2014-2020, the Andalusian Energetic Strategy 2020, the Andalusian Strategy against Climate Change, the Andalusian Plan for Environment Horizon 2017 and the Law for Agriculture and Livestock production of Andalusia integrate the bioeconomy as a model which

can respond to the challenges to be faced.

At the national level, Spanish Strategy for Bioeconomy Horizon 2030, approved in 2016, is based on the science-economy-society triangle. The public sector is responsible for promoting, stimulating, and coordinating the strategy.

Strategic vision/s and objectives of the circular bioeconomy strategy in the territory (region):

Vision: Building a diversified and sustainable region in which the circular bioeconomy is the cornerstone for development combined with the improvement of human welfare and social equity, thus generating opportunities for quality jobs for citizens, with greater resilience to current changes and transformations and future trends, adapted to climate change that will gradually reduce its dependence on external resources

The strategy focuses on the regional bioeconomy areas less developed and aims to support the implementation of specific actions that facilitate its take-off and consolidation in the medium-long term. The relevant sectors for the bioeconomy include agriculture, forestry, fishing, food, and paper production, as well as part of the chemical, biotechnology, and energy industries. The time horizon of the strategy is 2030.

The main objective of the ACBS is to contribute to sustainable growth and development in Andalusia by carrying out actions toward the production of renewable and biological products and processes. Three strategic objectives can be pointed out:

- Increase the availability of sustainable biomass for its use through innovative treatments.
- Increase the number of bio-industries and biorefineries in Andalusia.
- Increase markets and the consumption of bioproducts and bioenergy in Andalusia.

Existence of bio-based solutions integrated to existing systems/processes or independent

There is a need for technological developments specifically adapted to every type of biological resource and industrial process and the need to make progress on the development of integrated biorefineries.

The experience gained by Andalusia after being selected by the European Commission as a model demonstrator region to lead the way towards a chemical sustainable production in Europe constitutes another opportunity for the circular bioeconomy in our region. Thanks to this project, Andalusia has received the advisory and technical support of the European Sustainable Chemicals Support Service. This has enabled it to define this new concept of industry and help to generate new investment and employment opportunities to bring wealth and make progress in the achievement of a circular economy, the aim of zero residues, and the reduction of pollutant emissions. At the same time, the project has strengthened the intersectoral relations between the chemical industries and those which are involved in the processes that produce raw materials.

Brief description of the level of public awareness and acceptance of the circular bioeconomy strategy [Level of awareness among the general population (public) of the region]:

The ACBS points out that there is some misinformation from the citizenship side about what bioeconomy means and what it implies. There are also weaknesses in the promotion of products and services related to bioeconomy fields.

To make the implementation of bioproducts on the markets come true, a system allowing their identification by final consumers has to be established. The standardization of bioproducts seems to be a key element for their recognition by society.

Brief description of the degree of concern, interest, and knowledge of farmers/producers/businesses (stakeholders) about the circular bioeconomy strategies available, the problem of waste, etc., and the circularity opportunities (marketing, social, etc):

The ACBS points out that there is limited knowledge of alternative uses of different raw materials and their introduction in alternative value chains in the field of circular bioeconomy.

6.5.3 The QH actors, operating principles, and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system

Policy departments in local and regional administrations currently involved in the development and the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main responsible administrations):

The Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural (Regional Ministry for Agriculture, Fishing, Water and Rural Development) from the Junta de Andalucía (Andalusian Government) is the policy department in the regional administration in charge of implementing the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy that was issued in 2018 by the regional government.

Policy departments in local and regional administrations that should also be involved in the future or have shown interest in being involved (in particular those in charge of economic development, agriculture and rural development, environment and climate, research and innovation):

Other policy departments in the region are linked to the bioeconomy field. The Consejería de Sostenibilidad, Medio Ambiente y Economía Azul (Regional Ministry for sustainability, environment and blue economy) is the one in charge of circular economy issues and has pushed for regulation for a circular economy that has been approved at the regional level recently. Moreover, the Consejería de Política Industrial y Energía (Regional Ministry for industrial policy and energy) would be also related to bioeconomy due to bioenergy production. Aside from regional ministries, there are public agencies whose activity might be related to circular bioeconomy as well. These are Agencia de Gestión Agraria y Pesquera de Andalucía (Agency for farming and fish management), Agencia Andaluza de la Energía (Andalusian Agency for Energy), and Agencia de Medio Ambiente y Agua (Agency for environment and water).

Working groups among administrative departments involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy:

It involves a multidisciplinary group that includes different fields related to the Bioeconomy: agriculture, fisheries, forestry, R&D&I, industry, academia, environment, etc.

Specific clusters developed, with brief description of the bioeconomy related clusters operating in the territory:

The Andalusian Bioeconomy Cluster is planned to be developed in the framework of the 2030 strategy (the aim of participating in ROBIN is to further shape, launch, and start the operation of the cluster). There is also the Technological Corporation of Andalusia (ROBIN partner), a multi-sectoral Andalusian cluster of private companies that includes biotechnology among its seven sectors.

Previous co-creation initiatives towards governance models/structures/policies:

In the frame of the BBI-JU funded project "ICT-BIOCHAIN", a co-creation event was conducted among QH stakeholders to identify the main challenges, needs, and ideas for the development of a Digital Innovation Hub (DIH) devoted to biomass mobilisation through the digitalisation of logistics.

People's attitudes towards co-creation with policy makers:

The experience in the ICT-BIOCHAIN project was very positive with high participation of QH stakeholders. A summary of the whole experience can be found in "**Digital Innovation Hubs as a Tool for Boosting Biomass Valorisation in Regional Bioeconomies: Andalusian and South-East Irish Case Studies**" [32].

Existence of a bioeconomy strategy council or similar structure overseeing the policy:

One of the actions foreseen in the Strategy provides for the creation of a Monitoring Committee, which will periodically evaluate the degree of compliance with the strategic lines and measures of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy through the monitoring and control of a series of indicators.

Brief description of the main actors (stakeholders) in the territory for the circular bioeconomy strategy (Main partners):

From the academia side, The Agrifood Campus of International Excellence comprising the universities of Jaén, Córdoba, Huelva, Cádiz, and Almería has projects in the field of the valorisation of agriculture by-products, biorefineries, and algae (e.g. the FP7 MIRACLE project - a multi-product integrated algae refinery). Other important institutions for academic training relevant to Bioeconomy are the Andalusian Institute for Research and Training in Agriculture, Fisheries, Foods and Organic Production (whose Spanish acronym is IFAPA, a ROBIN project partner) and the Spanish National Research Council (whose Spanish acronym is CSIC). There are also other research centres such as ANDALTEC (Plastic Technological Centre), TECNOVA (Research Centre related to agribusiness) and CETAQUA (Water Technology Centre).

From the consumers' side, there is the Andalusian Union of Consumers.

From the private sector side and from a value chain perspective, due to Andalusia's strong feedstock position, these are the different feedstocks for which Andalusia has a strong position at European level:

- Horticulture and agri-food
- Olive sector
- Forestry
- Livestock farming
- Algae (using CO₂ and nutrients from industry as feedstock)

Main leadership role owner, to steer and facilitate the development of circular bioeconomy in the territory:

The main leadership role is from the Consejería de Agricultura, Pesca, Agua y Desarrollo Rural (Regional Ministry for agriculture, fishing, water and rural development), ROBIN partner.

Existence of civil society organizations (CSOs) and/or non-governmental organizations (NGOs) involved in the circular bioeconomy strategy, with brief description:

Andalusian Union of Consumers. Also, Cooperativas Agroalimentarias de Andalucía is an Association of Andalusian farmers cooperatives. Another association is ASAJA (Andalusian association of young farmers). Moreover, there are Rural Development Groups all over the region such as GDR Los Pedroches.

Common priorities of the actors involved in circular bioeconomy activities (consider society, business, knowledge, administration and capital representatives):

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy is structured in four strategic lines. The first two respond to strategic objective 1 and the other two respond to strategic objectives 2 and 3, respectively;

- Strategic line 1. Sustainable generation and availability of biomass resources
- Strategic line 2. Infrastructures and logistics management
- Strategic line 3. Industrial processes for the transformation of biomass resources and industrial production capacity of bioproducts and bioenergy
- Strategic Line 4. Market development for bioproducts and bioenergy

Existence of diversity of perspectives and interests among them, with explanation:

The interest is that the economic activity of the sectors converges to the development of the circular bioeconomy of the region.

Role of public authorities in bringing together the QH actors:

To coordinate, promote, encourage and communicate in the process of implementing the circular bioeconomy governance model. Designing accompanying measures for the development of the bioeconomy.

Intermediary organizations that operate as bridges/links between clusters/sectors:

So far, a leading role for any actor has been identified.

Existence of specialized technology, research and innovation centers within the bioeconomy governance system, analysis of their interconnectivity and their role:

In Andalusia, there is no research centre specifically devoted to bioeconomy or circular bioeconomy as such. However, there is a large number of technology, research, and innovation centres that focus their activities in one of the areas related to bioeconomy. These are:

- Fundación Citoliva - [Centro de Innovación y Tecnología del Olivar y del Aceite](#) [98],
- Fundación Centro Tecnológico Acuicultura de Andalucía- [CTAQUA](#) [99],

- Fundación Centro de las Nuevas Tecnologías del Agua- [CENTA](#) [100],
- Fundación Centro de Innovación y Tecnología del Residuo- CITRA,
- Centro Tecnológico para el Desarrollo Sostenible en Doñana-[DOÑANA-21](#) [101],
- Otros centros tecnológicos y de apoyo a la innovación tecnológica Huelva,
- Centro Tecnológico [CIDAF](#) [102],
- Centro Investigación y Calidad Agroalimentaria del Valle de Los Pedroches – [CICAP](#) [103],
- Centro de Innovación y Tecnología de la Pesca y Transformación de Productos Pesqueros-[GARUM](#) [104],
- Centro de Excelencia en Investigación sobre Aceite de Oliva y Salud – [CEAS](#) [105],
- Centro de Excelencia en Investigación de Medicamentos Innovadores en Andalucía – [MEDINA](#) [106],
- Campus de Excelencia Internacional Agroalimentario ([ceiA3](#)) [107],

Their role is to develop activities linked to science, technology, and innovation in their respective working fields, operating through public funding and private services, supporting this way the needs from Andalusian companies.

6.5.4 The policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs)

Financial instruments available for the implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy will have the financial resources needed to develop the actions proposed. The different Administrative centres and Instrumental bodies that have been involved in the design, drafting, and definition of the Strategy will provide their own funds and they will be also responsible for the future implementation of the actions. These funds will be complemented with other financing resources, mainly:

- Availability of budget on the structural funds (principally European Regional Development Fund (ERDF) and European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development (EAFRD)) and European investment funds to fund actions to stimulate and promote the circular bioeconomy.
- Possibility of funding projects through the Spanish Ministry for Economy and Business (CDTI, INIA, ...).
- Existence of cross-cutting policies of the Regional Government of Andalusia that promote and support the circular bioeconomy.
- Possibility of creating intermediate credit lines (combination of regional public resources with others at the national or European level).
- Possible synergies with other public funding lines available (national or European funding such as European Investments Bank or Structural Funds).
- Private funds from different entities that want to invest in the bioeconomy.

Are there actions plans, by sector, stream or product/service:

On the one hand, the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy has an associated action plan which has not yet been implemented.

On the other hand, some examples which can be highlighted concerning the bioeconomy are:

- Strategic Plan to improve the competitiveness of the agricultural, livestock, fisheries, and agro-industrial sector and the rural development in Andalusia (2020-2022).
- Plan in the framework of the REINWASTE Project, linked to zero inorganic waste-looking solutions for the agri-food sector.

Brief description of the short-/mid-/long-term actions and their monitoring system (including KPIs, deadlines):

The Andalusian circular bioeconomy strategy includes actions for every strategic line and programme. The associated indicators and their time frame will be established in the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy update.

The included actions in ACBS are described below:

STRATEGIC LINE (SL) 1: SUSTAINABLE PRODUCTION AND AVAILABILITY OF BIOMASS RESOURCES.

ACTIONS:

- To identify and quantify the biomass resources by sectors and sub-sectors to achieve their comprehensive use and identify their possible uses.
- To establish and developing the methodology to introduce indicators on the biomass resources and the industrial areas producing CO₂ in the statistical Andalusian planning.
- To stimulate and reinforcing sustainability practices and better technical alternatives (equipment and machinery) to obtain, recover and use biomass resources.
- To promote the evaluation of sustainability in the stage of biomass resources generation.
- To establish and develop the methodology to create and inventory and georeferencing the potential users of biomass resources concerning the territorial distribution of resources.

SL 2: INFRASTRUCTURES AND LOGISTIC MANAGEMENT

ACTIONS:

- To identify and promote the best collecting or supply, storage, pre-treatment and use technologies for biomass resources based on efficiency and profitability criteria for the bioproducts or bioenergy value chain.
- To design an investment plan to support, improve and disseminate the existing logistical infrastructures bearing in mind the importance of their location in rural areas.
- To promote the establishment of new centres to prepare and collect biomass resources adapted to the conditions of every area to facilitate their management.

SL 3: INDUSTRIAL BIOMASS PROCESSING PROCESSES AND BIOPRODUCTS AND BIOENERGY INDUSTRIAL PRODUCTION CAPACITY

ACTIONS

- To analyse the state of the art of preparation (previous treatments) and processing technologies (conversion technologies) of biomass resources into bioproducts and bioenergy.
- To promote sustainability in the use of biomass resources according to eco-innovation and eco-efficiency criteria: cascade use, circular economy, use of the industrial CO₂, pre-treatment and processing processes in areas near production facilities.
- To develop programmes of structured industrial symbiosis and/or innovative collaborations between companies and industries to create new models to use biomass resource flows and industrial CO₂ resources.
- To stimulate the conduction of feasibility studies (economic, social, and environmental) and business models during the planning and implementation stages of bioindustries and biorefineries, mainly in rural areas.
- To promote the settlement of bioindustries and biorefineries in Andalusia to support the already existing ones and promote the conversion of the biodiesel industry into integrated biorefineries.

SL 4: MARKET DEVELOPMENT FOR BIOPRODUCTS AND BIOENERGY.

ACTIONS:

- To support the conduction of market studies, business plans, and feasibility studies of bioproducts, bioenergy, and services linked to the circular bioeconomy and monitoring the bioproducts and bioenergy value chains.
- To draft market studies on consumer trends and new uses of bioproducts and bioenergy, as well as a portfolio of their potential consuming areas and/or sectors.
- To promote the marketing and use of bioproducts, bioenergy, and services linked to the circular bioeconomy and create marks for their differentiation in the market.
- To encourage cultural business change needed to appreciate the services offered by the circular bioeconomy to improve sustainability, stimulate the analyses of the life cycle, and calculate the environmental footprints of bioproducts and bioenergy.

PROGRAMME A: SOCIETY COMMUNICATION AND AWARENESS-RAISING ON THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY.

ACTIONS.

- To design and launch a communication plan to develop activities on circular bioeconomy that will include a specific website, fairs, seminars, workshops, meetings, advertising campaigns, and forums, as well as a visibility plan for social networks.
- To design and launch promotion and advertising campaigns (marketing) of bioproducts, bioenergy, services, and processes related to the circular bioeconomy by promoting their marks.

PROGRAMME B: PROMOTING R&D+I+T FOR THE DEVELOPMENT AND EXPANSION OF THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY IN ANDALUSIA.

ACTIONS.

- To identify and disseminate the research, innovation, and technological development needs.
- To promote research for the development of bioproducts and bioenergy and the instruments to support innovation and the generation of intellectual and industrial property in their areas,

especially through the public procurement of innovative solutions and incubators and social shuttles to encourage entrepreneurship

- To promote the analysis of by-product valorisation systems from an economic perspective, including valuation of benefits for society, research on the adoption of innovations, and analysis of policy instruments to promote the development of the circular bioeconomy, among others.
- To stimulate the creation of a catalogue of good practices and a portfolio of successful projects, technological innovations, and business ideas for each of the links of the value chains related to the circular bioeconomy.
- To design tools to favour the technology transfer between the different stakeholders in the field of the circular bioeconomy.
- To plan activities and services to promote the transfer of knowledge in the field of the circular bioeconomy (workshops on technological transfer, business missions, sector-based committees, awareness-raising events in aspects related to this matter, advisory services, and mentoring ...)
- To promote the participation of the knowledge agents, research and innovation groups, and businesses in the R&D+i+T programmes of the EU and industrial projects, networks, and other events.
- To stimulate the creation of a Focus Group in the field of research related to the circular bioeconomy
- To introduce the circular bioeconomy and/or its areas of knowledge in the curricular content of compulsory education, vocational training, university relevant qualifications as well as in the training courses for the professionals working on sectors related to it.
- To analyse the state of the art of the Master's education in subjects related to the circular bioeconomy and stimulate the establishment of a specialization Master in circular bioeconomy.

PROGRAMME C: FUNDING ACCESS TO FACILITATE THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY IN ANDALUSIA.

ACTIONS.

- To stimulate a guidance service to analyse, give advice, and communicate the financial instruments available for the circular bioeconomy.
- To stimulate new forms of public support and access to financing for the development and implementation of projects and business ideas in circular bioeconomy, including alternative collaborative funding sources and new public-private financial instruments, as well as the public procurement of innovative solutions.
- To promote initiatives to disseminate the competitive advantages of Andalusia and its experience in diverse sectors as factors of interest to favour foreign investment in projects and business ideas linked to the circular bioeconomy.
- To promote the connection of circular bioeconomy projects and companies with investors' networks or business angels to extend the funding alternatives at national and international levels.

PROGRAMME D: PROMOTING THE COOPERATION, COORDINATION AND MONITORING OF THE CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY

ACTIONS

- To stimulate the Andalusian Cluster for Circular Bioeconomy.
- To create and implement the Andalusian Observatory for Circular Bioeconomy.
- To identify regulatory areas that could be a barrier or an opportunity for the development of the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia.
- To create an Interdepartmental Commission to promote and monitor the circular bioeconomy in Andalusia.
- To create the Monitoring Committee and the Technical Office for the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy.
- To design the panel of specific indicators to monitor and evaluate the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy and keep it updated.
- To elaborate reports on the situation, monitoring and evaluation of the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, and organising specific work groups in matters of particular relevance.

Brief description of the follow-up and evaluation procedure of the action plan's performance

In the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy, the associated action plan has not yet been developed, so the follow-up and evaluation procedure has not yet been established.

Economy-related indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy is in the process of being implemented with a framework until 2030. Some economy-related indicators used to assess the territorial impact of the circular bioeconomy strategy could be employment generated by the bioeconomy, value-added generated by the bioeconomy, increase in the number of bioindustries, increase in the number of biorefineries, etc.

Societal indicators used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy is in the process of being implemented with a framework until 2030. Some societal indicators used to assess the territorial impact of the circular bioeconomy strategy could be the impact of bioeconomy contents in social networks, the impact of bioeconomy contents on websites, domestic consumption of bioproducts and bioenergy, holding of conferences and training activities, etc.

Environmental indicators are used to assess territorial impacts of the circular bioeconomy strategy:

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy is in the process of being implemented with a framework until 2030. Some environmental indicators used to assess the territorial impact of the circular bioeconomy strategy could be the production and consumption of bioenergy in Andalusia, the percentage of valorised residues in the agri-food sector, etc.

Existing initiatives from front-runners and/or regions with the same bioeconomy profile/approach to emulate/follow:

Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy considers:

- European Bioeconomy Strategy and its Action Plan.
- Spanish Bioeconomy Strategy-2030 Horizon.
- Green Deal.
- Farm to Fork strategy.
- The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development with 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

In Spain, regions such as Catalanian and Castilla y Leon have strategies dedicated to bioeconomy and mainly in sectors like agriculture and agroindustries. Their actions are of interest to Andalusia.

Flanders (Belgium) stands out as one of the first regions in Europe in adopting a regional bioeconomy strategy in 2013. Andalusia has made an in-depth study of the following regions: Baden-Wuerttemberg (Denmark), Pays de la Loire (France), Flanders (Belgium) and Mazovia (Poland) comparing diverse aspects of their policies.

Flexibility of the circular bioeconomy strategy in your territory to accommodate the needs of the territory:

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy is based on political priorities already undertaken by the Andalusian government, such as moving towards a competitive economy based on biological processes, which respect the good use of natural resources, their maintenance, and efficient use. The elaboration of the ACBS included a participatory approach of all actors in the value chain of the different sectors. This way, the best measures and programmes linked to the development of the bioeconomy in Andalusia could be addressed.

Since the Statute of Autonomy for Andalusia came into force, among the competencies held by the Autonomous Community concerning agriculture, livestock production, fishing, agro forestry uses, rural development, and quality schemes, the region has developed competencies that help to achieve the goals set by the ACBS. Some of them are the development of the agricultural, livestock production, fishing, and food-processing sectors, the regulation of the agricultural production processes, organic farming, food sufficiency, the development of technological innovations, rural development, sustainable development, and the promotion of the production and use of biomass. All these competencies must continue to be developed in the future by applying the criteria adopted and raised by the Andalusian Strategy.

The experience gained by Andalusia after being selected by the European Commission as a model demonstrator region to lead the way towards the chemical sustainable production in Europe constitutes another opportunity for the circular bioeconomy in our region. Thanks to this project, Andalusia has received the advisory and technical support of the European Sustainable Chemicals Support Service. It has enabled it to define this new concept of industry and help generate new investment and employment opportunities to bring wealth and make progress in the achievement of a circular economy, the aim of zero residues and the reduction of pollutant emissions. At the same time, the project has strengthened the intersectoral relations between the chemical industries and those involved in the processes that produce the raw material.

All these opportunities take advantage and, simultaneously, underpin the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy.

6.5.5 Challenges and opportunities for the circular bioeconomy policy (SWOT Analysis)

Main strengths for implementing the circular bioeconomy in the region:

The main strengths, according to the defined dimensions, are as follows:

Generation and availability of biomass resources

Great production capacity of biomass resources from agriculture, livestock production, agri-food, forest and fishing sectors.

Availability of other flows of biomass resources of interest that can be recovered such as sludge from sewage systems and biowaste produced at local level.

Progressive optimization in the management of biomass resources generated by the agricultural and agri-food sectors due to the extensive experience that exists concerning its bioenergetic use.

Important concentration of biomass resources with potential use in certain areas.

Development of algal production experiences to make the most of CO₂.

Infrastructures and logistics management of biomass resources

An important concentration of biomass resources in certain areas of the region, a fact that facilitates the logistics of their management.

Existence of storage facilities and collection centres for biomass resources in certain productive sectors.

Availability of logistic infrastructures for certain biomass resources that can be used in other value chains.

Existence of biomass transport companies that might deliver to new bio-based industries or biorefineries.

Use of the logistic development associated with the bioenergy sector in other value chains of bioproducts derived from the expansion of the circular bioeconomy.

Industrial processing of biomass resources and capacity of industrial production of bioproducts and bioenergy

Important agro-industrial business fabric with the capacity to participate in bio-based processes that also have experience in certain technological developments aimed at the efficient use of resources.

Continuous development of bioenergy; a fact that has led to the creation of a business fabric that uses biomass for thermal and electrical use and for the production of biofuels.

The existence of chemical clusters made up of a diversity of companies that could host new others linked to the circular bioeconomy.

Experience in circular bioeconomy resulting from its selection as a model demonstrator region for sustainable chemistry.

Existence of a biotechnological ecosystem that favours the transformation and recovery of the biomass resources of Andalusia.

Development of markets for bioproducts and bioenergy.

Existence of a consolidated market for biofuels.

The existence of a demand already established for particular bioproducts (plant debris for composting or manure for organic amendments) can boost the demand for bioproducts.

Experience of Andalusia in the sustainable chemistry sector, both concerning the bioproducts that can be obtained and their current and/or potential markets, as it has been selected as a demonstrator region.

Active involvement of Andalusia in the Bio-Based Industries Consortium (BIC).

Communication.

Initiatives related to the circular bioeconomy and publicly known by society; a fact that can be an advantage in order to make society aware of its advantages and importance.

Enough information on the potential biomass available in Andalusia.

Bioeconomy cases of success can be showcased to society as an example of the advantages of the circular bioeconomy.

R&D+Innovation and Training.

Adaptation of the Andalusian scientific production to the European priorities proposed for industrial matters; some of them directly related to the circular bioeconomy.

Involvement of Andalusia in international projects related to the circular bioeconomy.

Experience of the Andalusian International Campuses of Excellence (CeIA3 and Andalusia TECH), and of research and technology transfer groups in the sectors of interest for the circular bioeconomy.

Knowledge, experience, human capital, technological capacity and dimension in innovation areas related to the circular bioeconomy, as well as in leading companies.

Critical mass of scientific-technical staff in the field of the circular bioeconomy.

Network of research and training centres and infrastructures on agriculture and agri-food processing as well as technological parks related to sectors with a great potential for the circular bioeconomy.

Presence of important driving poles for productive innovation with implications in circular bioeconomy (agri-food industry, chemical sector, renewable energies).

Promotion of research oriented to the bioeconomy as a priority defined in the Andalusian Innovation Strategy 2020, RIS3 Andalusia, through projects of excellence.

Support policies and funding.

Possibility of submitting applications for funding to the calls of the Joint Undertaking for Bio-Based Industries and those launched by the Social Challenge 2 that falls under H2020 for projects related to research, technological development and innovation in the field of the circular bioeconomy.

Availability of budget on the structural funds (principally ERDF and EAFRD) and European investment funds to fund actions to stimulate and promote the circular bioeconomy.

Possibility of funding projects through the Spanish Ministry for Economy and Business (CDTI, INIA...).

Existence of cross-cutting policies of the Regional Government of Andalusia that promote and support the circular bioeconomy.

Inter-administrative cooperation and coordination.

Development of new relations and collaboration methods and formulas for the development of innovative projects between the institutions and the companies associated with the circular bioeconomy of Andalusia.

Possible synergies between the sectors involved (suppliers, transformers and users of residues and bioproducts) in the region.

Progressive dissemination of the new model represented by the circular bioeconomy in the different centres of the Regional Ministries of Andalusia.

Development of policy and planning tools related to circular bioeconomy.

Political commitment in all the areas to the bioeconomy and the circular economy, which favours the organisation of events and forums where contacts are established.

Main weaknesses for applying the circular bioeconomy in the region:

The main weaknesses according to defined dimensions are as follow:

Generation and availability of biomass resources.

Limited knowledge on the characteristics of a great variety of biomass resources with potential as raw material for the production of innovative bioproducts.

Deficient management of the by-products derived from livestock production.

Insufficient management of forest resources.

Ignorance of the balance between the potential demand of alternative raw materials to biomass and the availability of the latter.

Infrastructures and logistics management of biomass resources.

Seasonal variation of biomass resources and inappropriate collection infrastructures.

Existence of logistic centres optimized for a certain value chain owned by their stakeholders.

Industrial processing of biomass resources and capacity of industrial production of bioproducts and bioenergy.

Lack of technological developments specifically adapted to every type of biological resource and industrial process.

Little development of the integrated biorefineries and bio-based industries.

Development of markets for bioproducts and bioenergy.

Limited knowledge on alternative uses of different raw materials and their introduction in alternative value chains in the field of circular bioeconomy.

Lack of detailed analyses concerning the potential applications of by-products and the available waste of biological origin and companies potentially interested in them.

Lack of innovation business culture to face the technological adaptation to new products and manufacturing processes.

Reduced number of medium-large companies that will allow the development of business projects in the medium-long term.

Lack of a clear and recognized regulation of the products of biological origin.

Communication.

Unawareness of what the circular bioeconomy is and what it represents by great part of society.

Weaknesses in the promotion of the products and services that shape the Andalusian productive system and among them, those derived from activities associated with the circular bioeconomy.

R&D+Innovation and Training.

Poor links between scientific production and the market. Lack of patents and real applications of the research on circular bioeconomy.

Difficulty in the definition of strategies related to the circular bioeconomy in the medium-long term successive research programmes according to a complete alignment with the national and European R&D+i policies.

Lack of information, training and skills, networking, cooperation, etc. in circular bioeconomy, in order to produce new innovative actions.

Poor number of spin-off or start-up companies based on the knowledge on circular bioeconomy compared to the size of the Andalusian system.

Insufficient adjustment of the training offer to the needs and specificities of the professional staff working in the agricultural, food- processing, environmental, forest and fishing sectors related to the circular bioeconomy.

Lack of joint initiatives between the R&D+i system and the sectors associated with the circular bioeconomy, especially, in relation with the real needs of the above-mentioned sectors.

Support policies and funding.

Poor flexibility of the funding instruments existing for Technology-based Businesses (TBB) that do not bear in mind the life cycle of business projects as a whole.

Difficulty to fund comprehensive projects due to the incompatibility between funds (divided by competences).

Inter-administrative cooperation and coordination.

Unawareness of what the circular bioeconomy implies for certain business areas and the public sector.

Lack of facilitating schemes to create alliances between companies, sectors and research bodies in the field of the circular bioeconomy.

Lack of a single resource that gathers the whole regulation and funding opportunities related to the different raw materials, products and processes associated with the circular bioeconomy.

Rigid governing models in Public R&D+i Institutions that hinder the development of the circular bioeconomy.

Main opportunities for implementing the circular bioeconomy in the region:

The main opportunities according to defined dimensions are as follow:

Generation and availability of biomass resources.

Possibility of increasing the competitiveness of the primary and secondary sectors through the development of new bioproducts.

Excellent regional weather conditions for the production of biomass.

Existence of a biotechnological environment adapted to favour the use of the biomass resources generated.

Increase of the volume of residues in dumps.

Existence of new management methods for solid urban biowaste.

Advantages of the transformation of by- products and waste into resources concerning the saving of greenhouse gases, a guarantee of the sustainable development and contribution to the mitigation of climate change.

Normative changes in the European and/or national legislation in order to favour, stimulate and even force to achieve the full re-use of by- products in the production lines.

Infrastructures and logistics management of biomass resources.

Important transport infrastructure network (roads, railroads, ports).

Possibility of using the logistic centres already existing in mature value chains, in new ones.

The possibility of improving and computerizing the logistic operations by means of the use of ICT.

Industrial processing of biomass resources and capacity of industrial production of bioproducts and bioenergy.

Great potential for the implementation of the use of biomass by applying biorefinery concepts in diverse Andalusian sectors (olive growing, fruits and vegetables...).

Development of bioindustries and biorefineries on a small scale in the Andalusian rural areas.

Possible transformation and/or remodelling of biodiesel production plants into biorefineries.

Growing interest in the use of resources of biological origin and the circular economy by part of the European industry.

Existence of support policies for entrepreneurs and the consolidation of innovative companies.

Existence of technologies for the production and use of biogas from biomass resources.

Increase of the bioenergy demand.

Development of markets for bioproducts and bioenergy.

Existence of a consolidated activity in fields directly linked with new models of sustainable development (renewable energies, healthy food, etc.).

Growing social demand of sustainable products that can lead to the development and expansion of circular bioeconomy.

Importance of sectors such as organic farming, integrated production, animal feed, etc. For potential bioproducts' consumers.

Potential for the production of fertilizers and other products of major added value from biomass resources (sludge from swage systems, biowaste produced at local level).

Incorporation of criteria to stimulate the circular bioeconomy in the Public procurement of Innovative solutions.

Existence of the Bio-Based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU) whose purpose is to support the establishment of circular bioeconomy industries and value chains.

Communication.

Existence of entities that create synergies and of social communication networks on science that can disseminate the advantages offered by circular bioeconomy to society.

R&D+Innovation and Training.

Network of scientific-technological infrastructures that generate important environments of opportunities in the region.

Consolidation of the programme to support research groups that will contribute to the organisation of the research and development work developed by universities and other R&D+i centres of Andalusia.

Experience in the participation and leadership of European R&D+i projects.

Room for improvement in the exploitation of synergies between the different agents of the Science, Technology and Business System.

“Carry-over” effect of the cases of success in the dissemination of processes and good innovative practices.

Territorial specialization strategy oriented to intensive and high added value segments with skilled human capital.

Attraction of research talent from other regions using particular programmes.

Support policies and funding.

Possible synergies with other public funding lines available (national or European funding such as European Investments Bank or Structural Funds).

Collaboration network between some public, private and financial institutions.

Existence of both public and private financial intermediaries (European Investments Bank, European Investment Fund).

Possibility of creating intermediate credit lines (combination of regional public resources with other at national or European level).

Positive evolution of the foreign investment in the region.

Growing interest for sustainable investment.

Visibility of the region at European level thanks to other projects.

Inter-administrative cooperation and coordination.

Institutional support and commitment to the environment and the territory.

Regulatory provisions and planning tools in the field of environment and sustainability.

Technological dimension and development of the Andalusian Public Sector to allow it to act as a demand, public procurement of innovative solutions and companies driver.

Main threats for applying the circular bioeconomy in the region:

The main threats according to defined dimensions are as follow:

Generation and availability of biomass resources.

Availability of biomass resources at better prices and of major quality in other regions.

Reduction of the biomass resources available due to the effects of climate change.

Changes in legislation that can harden the requirements to recover or manage biomass resources.

Infrastructures and logistic management of biomass resources.

High transport costs of certain flows of low-density biomass resources.

Transport costs very dependent on the volatility of the price of fossil fuels.

Excessive importance of the transport by road with its consequent impact on GHG emissions.

Deficiencies in the connection between the regional Andalusian centres and other international markets (Mediterranean Axis and Trans-European Transport Networks).

Industrial processing of biomass resources and capacity of industrial production of bioproducts and bioenergy.

High transport costs of certain flows of low-density biomass resources.

Certain legislative developments that hinder and hamper the use of particular by-products and waste.

Regulatory changes that may affect the transformation of biomass

Development of markets for bioproducts and bioenergy

Uncertainty concerning the development of the possible markets arisen from the productive areas that must be part of the Andalusian circular bioeconomy.

Difficulties faced by the business sector in general, and of innovative companies, in particular, to access to new markets or to keep the leadership quotas reached in certain areas compared to the international competitors.

Increase of the energy cost and uncertainty in its regulative framework, specially concerning renewable energies.

Competition with cheaper products derived from the fossil energy or with products of other markets regulated by different legislations.

Low production performances of bioproducts.

Communication.

Lack of clarity in the dissemination of the circular bioeconomy concept, what hinders its understanding among the different stakeholders.

R&D+Innovation and Training.

Resources of the R&D+i system slightly efficient to attract and retain the human capital of the Science, Technology and Business System.

Growing international competence in terms of resources, talent, technology and attraction of R&D+i investments.

Relative disconnection between the business structure and the Andalusian knowledge system.

Moreover, the limited activity of many components of the latter results in the reduction of the improvement and development potential of the most innovative industry.

Limited number of companies that use the public R&D+i system compared to its size.

Insufficient appreciation of research in general and of researchers in particular, especially by the business fabric.

Incidence of the economic crisis in the number of companies classified as innovative, as well as in the expenditure on innovation.

Existence of barriers for the mobility between the R&D+i staff of the public and private sectors

Support policies and funding.

Poor involvement of the private sector in R&D+i funding.

Limited access to credit to undertake or innovate, aggravated by the current economic situation.

Risk of sustainability of the R&D public sector in the current situation due to a lack of alternatives to direct financing.

Limitations in the access to traditional loan instruments (loans and credits).

Shortage of alternative funding and credit options.

Problems to access to private funding by the private sector, especially, SMEs.

Inter-administrative cooperation and coordination.

Bureaucratic burdens and excessive administrative procedures that entail important obstacles for entrepreneurship.

Administrative difficulties for the implementation and development of projects in the territory (for example, innovative projects).

Concrete and main specific potential measures/tools that can be developed in the region/sector to promote and encourage the adoption of good practices from circular bioeconomy in priority sectors/value chains in the region:

The Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy promote the following measures/tools:

- Identifying the biomass resources produced in Andalusia.
- Improving the availability of biomass resources and sustainable practices in the sectors and producing areas associated with the bioeconomy.
- Improving the knowledge on biomass resources and their sources according to logistic factors.

- Keeping and improving infrastructures and implementing instruments to ensure the supply resources for the operators or the bioindustries considering the sustainability of the value chain.
- Improving the processes to prepare biomass resources and stimulating models to increase the eco-efficiency of their transformation.
- Supporting the creation and promoting the continuity of bioindustries and biorefineries, especially the integrated ones.
- Conducting studies on bioproducts, bioenergy and services linked to the circular bioeconomy.
- Promoting the use and distribution of bioproducts and bioenergy.
- Communicating and promoting the positive externalities of the circular bioeconomy.
- Favouring the adoption of innovation and the transfer of the knowledge related to the circular bioeconomy.
- Supporting collaborative approaches that promote innovation.
- Promoting the introduction of the circular bioeconomy in training programmes, curricular activities and in training for professionals.
- Improving the financing of projects included in the areas related to the circular bioeconomy.
- Favouring foreign investment in the field of the Andalusian circular bioeconomy.
- Facilitating the cooperation and collaboration between stakeholders.
- Clarifying the regulatory and legal framework that affect the activities linked to the circular bioeconomy and stimulating it in plans and programmes of the Andalusian Administration.
- Setting up a Monitoring Committee and a Technical Office for the Andalusian Circular Bioeconomy Strategy to analyse the impact of its measures in the goals set.

In relation to horticulture highlights:

- There is a good predisposition to implement innovative solutions in this sector that minimize or avoid the generation of waste, such as adoption of alternatives to mulching (compostable and biodegradable).
- There are available alternatives for staking elements or raffias, all of them (compostable, reusable, and biodegradable raffia) obtain a medium-high predisposition to be used and they are more sustainable.
- With reference to the alternatives for energetic valorisation of difficult-to-manage waste tested (valorisation by pyrolysis and valorisation by gasification), the sector has a medium predisposition to adopt these techniques. It is therefore clear that the sector has a need for innovative alternatives for this type of plastic waste.
- With regard to the alternatives for documentary traceability of inorganic waste, the predisposition to adopt the alternatives tested is medium, and producers perceive the physical documentary traceability system as more feasible than using the software, possibly because at the moment there is no solid and developed software linked to the documentary traceability of the residues.
- In relation to the alternatives related to associative models for waste management, the potential for adoption of both alternatives offered in the horticultural sector is medium, although the sector is more inclined to adopt the alternative where companies establish waste management agreements with a single management company than the alternative in which the farmers' association becomes waste manager.
- There is a high potential of adoption of the solutions tested in the horticultural industry. The ones showing a better potential of adoption are those considering the use of rPET (incorporate recycled material (recycled PET) in the packaging while putting into the market a 100% recyclable PET packaging), the use of cardboard trays and bands to substitute the whole packaging.

According to dairy production and industry, the following measures are to be considered:

- Lowering plastic use by packaging light weighting allows reducing fossil sources exploitation and waste streams.
- LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) studies on bioplastic packaging report environmental advantages compared to conventional systems.
- The adoption of non-destructive control systems prevents waste generation at the quality control level.

Lessons learnt from the circular bioeconomy policy so far:

The lessons learnt from the circular bioeconomy policy in the strategic sector are as follows:

- There are innovative alternatives for the most relevant sectors in Andalusia because they are tested in diverse experiences according to legislation. Besides, the main social, technical, and economic factors have been identified in order to promote the adoption of innovation.
- The research and transfer are promoted through different channels: field trials, workshops, videos on social networks, etc., and whenever possible in productive areas.
- Promote quality certifications related to respect for the environment, specifically the reduction of inorganic waste.
- Promoting the existence of specific managers for each type of waste and improving the network of easily accessible collection points (green points) where waste can be delivered at an affordable cost in the immediate surroundings of the production areas.
- Developing a regulatory framework that includes all types of inorganic waste in a differentiated manner, guaranteeing their correct management through a system of extended responsibility.
- Concerning the factors that promote the adoption of innovation, the horticulture sector feels that the most important one is consumer acceptance in terms of impact on sustainability.
- The food companies (not only horticulture) are very keen on how to valorise their engagement on the sustainability topic.
- Better use of funding schemes existing at the national/regional to finance the necessary investments at the plant level.
- A better involvement of plastic producers/processors and suppliers of packaging is necessary.
- Need for specific training for government staff responsible for authorising circular bioeconomy initiatives.
- Green public procurement to promote the use of circular bioeconomy products.
- Need to promote a venture capital model that facilitates investment in circular bioeconomy initiatives.
- Political recommendation: encourage companies to adopt alternative solutions thanks to regional and national technical and financial support.
- Encourage research and development projects about new alternative solutions.
- Regional support for companies who are willing to put alternative solutions in place.
- Raising awareness of consumers.

7. Conclusions

The objective of this deliverable is the analysis of the circular bioeconomy policy mix in the five selected ROBIN regions within Germany, Greece, Ireland, Slovakia and Spain. Specific aspects that are analyzed include: i) regional and local peculiarities, ii) the positioning of circularity and bioeconomy within regional policies, iii) the Quadruple Helix (QH) actors, operating principles and working relationships within the bioeconomy governance system, iv) the policy cycle components of the bioeconomy strategies, including policy monitoring system (and KPIs) and v) challenges and opportunities for circular bioeconomy policy. The regions represent a diverse territorial group, expressive of the heterogeneity of the EU, as well as a diversity of level of implementation of circular bioeconomy policies.

The identified regional and local specificities of the current document will feed in the development/update of successful bioeconomy governance models for each ROBIN region (under WP2 “Co-creating the regional governance models and structures”). The information collected and presented in the context of the current document will ensure that the ROBIN bioeconomy regional action plans which will be developed in the next stages of the project will be well-tailored to the local needs and challenges and will ensure the participation of all relevant stakeholders who have already been engaged and participate in the MARCs of each region. Furthermore, all the valuable information and insights collected will support the formulation of the requirements of the ROBIN tools and toolbox and their development and testing (under WP2 “Co-creating the regional governance models and structures” and WP3 “Setting up and operating the regional governance models and structures”) that will support ROBIN regions in implementing their governance models and structures. It is also worth mentioning that within the development of the current report and for the collection of all the information presented, 5 regional MARCs were set up, bringing together 47 stakeholders from the ROBIN regions (Andalusia: 12, Baden Wutterberg: 8, Region of Central Macedonia: 8, Southern Region of Ireland: 11, Zilina: 8) and 21 interviews were implemented.

The ROBIN regions represent a diverse representation of EU territories in terms of regional and local peculiarities, although there are commonalities in the bioeconomy sectors and products, and the bioeconomy value chains. There are differences in terms of the regions’ implementation of the circular bioeconomy strategy and in terms of the circular bioeconomy governance model.

In the ROBIN pilot regions, only Baden-Wuerttemberg has an already implemented bioeconomy strategy while the rest of the regions are on their way towards developing their regional bioeconomy strategy. It is interesting that all regions presented similar challenges related to the four different categories of barriers (institutional, implementation, financial, and other).

Barriers such as the lack of an official governmental framework to streamline the way to bioeconomy, and the lack of data and monitoring processes related to institutional challenges were present in all regions. Implementation barriers related to the lack of knowledge on what bioeconomy is and the lack of communication of the term bioeconomy and its benefits to the public were also present.

The financial barriers were evident in every pilot region, with the lack of funding for bioeconomy initiatives standing as the main hindering factor to the uptake of a regional governance model focused on bioeconomy. In the Zilina region of Slovakia, the Andalusian region of Spain, and the Region of Central Macedonia of Greece, the bureaucratic burden was a discouraging factor to set up and further develop a regional bioeconomy strategy.

Overall, the findings from the literature review were confirmed in the regional profiles, in terms of barriers, benefits and opportunities for the uptake of regional bioeconomy governance models, however new aspects were also introduced such as the environmental benefits of bioeconomy applications (e.g., low footprint, climate change mitigation), human development (e.g., new jobs) and

awareness raising (e.g., engagement of all stakeholder groups). Also, it is evident that there is a need of a streamlined framework to pave the way to regional bioeconomy governance models, and the term bioeconomy and its benefits need to be communicated effectively to wider audiences.

8. Bibliography

- [1] Robson, C., McCartan, K. (2016). *Real World Research. Fourth Edition.* John Wiley & Sons Ltd
- [2] Kiresiewa, Z., Gerdes, H., Hasenheit, M. (2019). *Biobridges Framework and good practices for multi-stakeholder and cross-sector interconnections. Deliverable 2.2 for the Biobridges Project (Grant Agreement No. 792236)*
- [3] Haarich, S., Kirchmayr-Novak, S. (2022). *Bioeconomy strategy development in EU regions, Sanchez Lopez, J., Borzacchiello, M.T. and Avraamides, M. editors, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. ISBN 978-92-76-49341-9, doi:10.2760/065902, JRC128740*
- [4] European Commission (2022). *EU Bioeconomy Strategy Progress Report, European Bioeconomy Policy: Stocktaking and future developments. Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg. ISBN 978-92-76-50201-2 doi:10.2777/997651*
- [5] *Spatial Foresight, SWECO, ÖIR, t33, Nordregio, Berman Group, Infyde (2017). Bioeconomy development in EU regions. Mapping of EU Member States'/regions' Research and Innovation plans & Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3) on Bioeconomy for 2014-2020*
- [6] Dietz, T., Börner, J., Förster, J., von Braun, J. (2018). *Governance of the Bioeconomy: A Global Comparative Study of National Bioeconomy Strategies. Sustainability 10(9), 3190. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10093190>*
- [7] Salvador, R., Barros, M. V., Donner, M., Brito, P., Halog, A., & De Francisco, A. C. (2022). *How to advance regional circular bioeconomy systems? Identifying barriers, challenges, drivers, and opportunities. Sustainable Production and Consumption 32, 248–269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2022.04.025>*
- [8] Overbeek, G., de Bakker, E., Beekman, V., Davies, S., Kiresiewa, Z., Delbrück, S., Ribeiro, B., Stoyanov, M., Vale, M. (2016). *BioSTEP Review of bioeconomy strategies at regional and national levels. Deliverable 2.3 for the BioSTEP project (Grant Agreement No. 652682)*
- [9] Elbersen, B., Coninx, I., Hatvani, N., Houtkamp, J., Koos, A., Kulmány, I., Mateffy, K., Van Den Oever, M., Vásáry, V. (2020). *An overview of suitable policy instruments to support bio-based business models. Deliverable 4.2 for the POWER4BIO Project (Grant Agreement No. 818351)*
- [10] Bryman, A. (2012). *Social Research Methods. Fourth edition, Oxford University Press*

- [11] Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) *Using thematic analysis in psychology. Qualitative Research in Psychology* 3:2, 77-101. DOI: 10.1191/1478088706qp063oa
- [12] Morrissey, K, O'donoghue, C., Farrell, N. (2014). *The Local Impact of the Marine Sector in Ireland: A Spatial Microsimulation Analysis. Spatial Economic Analysis* 9:1, 31-50. DOI: 10.1080/17421772.2013.835439
- [13] "Biotonne richtig nutzen! Leitfaden für große Wohnanlagen: Ministerium für Umwelt, Klima und Energiewirtschaft Baden-Württemberg," [Online]. Available: <https://um.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/presse-service/publikation/did/biotonne-richtig-nutzen-leitfaden-fuer-grosse-wohnanlagen>
- [14] "Urban BioEconomyLab – Transformation model and living laboratory for a systemic sustainable approach of an urban and industrial bioeconomy in Baden-Württemberg," [Online]. Available: <https://www.igb.fraunhofer.de/en/reference-projects/urban-bioeconomylab.html>
- [15] "Innovation Hub CCUBIO | Umwelttechnik BW," [Online]. Available: <https://www.umwelttechnik-bw.de/de/ccubio>
- [16] "Innovationsstrategie Baden-Württemberg (Fortschreibung 2020)," [Online]. Available: https://www.baden-wuerttemberg.de/fileadmin/redaktion/dateien/PDF/200204_Innovationsstrategie_BW_Fortschreibung_2020.pdf
- [17] "BIOGEGIO Interreg Europe," [Online]. Available: <https://www.interregeurope.eu/bioregio/>
- [18] "Sustainability Engineering Laboratory," [Online]. Available: <http://aix.meng.auth.gr/>
- [19] "Regional development fund Central Macedonia," [Online]. Available: <http://www.rdfcm.gr/>
- [20] "Action Plan for Rural Development," [Online]. Available: <https://assets.gov.ie/10916/951861650a4142b3a5bd0b4339f19509.pdf>
- [21] "Action Plan for Jobs 2017," [Online]. Available: <https://enterprise.gov.ie/en/publications/action-plan-for-jobs-2017.html>
- [22] "Beteiligungsportal Baden-Württemberg," [Ηλεκτρονικό]. Available: <https://beteiligungsportal.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/startseite/>
- [23] "State Office for Geoinformation and Rural Development," [Online]. Available: <https://fno-verfahren.lgl-bw.de/FISInternet/>
- [24] "State supports five model systems for agricultural photovoltaics," [Online]. Available: <https://www.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/service/presse/pressemitteilung/pid/land-foerdert-fuenf-modellanlagen-zur-agri-photovoltaik/>

- [25] "AGRO in LOG," [Online]. Available: <http://agroinlog-h2020.eu/en/home/>
- [26] "Secure Chain," [Online]. Available: <http://www.securechain.eu/>
- [27] "uP_running," [Online]. Available: <http://www.up-running.eu/>
- [28] "BIOMASUD PLUS," [Online]. Available: http://biomasudplus.eu/en_GB/
- [29] "BIOFIT," [Online]. Available: <https://www.biofit-h2020.eu/>
- [30] "Circular BIOECONOMY Cluster South-West," [Online]. Available: <https://cbcsw.ie/>
- [31] "Irish Bioeconomy Foundation Growing Ireland's Bioeconomy Together," [Online]. Available: <https://bioeconomyfoundation.com/>
- [32] Macias Aragonés M, de la Viña Nieto G, Nieto Fajardo M, Páez Rodríguez D, Gaffey J, Attard J, McMahon H, Doody P, Anda Ugarte J, Pérez-Camacho MN, Cuenca Martín MS, Giráldez Morales AJ, Martinelli FG. Digital Innovation Hubs as a Tool for Boosting Biomass Valorisation in Regional Bioeconomies: Andalusian and South-East Irish Case Studies. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*. 2020; 6(4):115. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc6040115>
- [33] "Baden-Württemberg.de," [Online]. Available: <https://www.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/service/presse/pressemitteilung/pid/landesstrategie-zur-biooekonomie-wird-fortgesetzt>
- [34] "Conception of a bioeconomy development index for Baden-Württemberg - indicators for monitoring and marking the development status (BÖE index)," [Online]. Available: <https://pudi.lubw.de/projektdetailseite/-/project/125076>
- [35] "Concept for a bioeconomy index for Baden- Württemberg," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ier.uni-stuttgart.de/forschung/projekte/abgeschlossen/boeeindex/>
- [36] "Programme for Government: Our Shared Future," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/7e05d-programme-for-government-our-shared-future/>
- [37] "Climate Action and Low Carbon Development (Amendment) Act 2021," [Online]. Available: <https://www.irishstatutebook.ie/eli/2021/act/32/enacted/en/html>
- [38] "Climate Action Plan 2021," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/6223e-climate-action-plan-2021/>
- [39] "National Policy Statement on the Bioeconomy," [Online]. Available: <https://assets.gov.ie/2244/241018115730-41d795e366bf4000a6bc0b69a136bda4.pdf>
- [40] "Whole of Government Circular Economy Strategy 2022 – 2023 'Living More, Using Less'," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/b542d-whole-of-government-circular-economy-strategy-2022-2023-living-more-using-less/>

- [41] "Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy," [Online]. Available: <https://www.southernassembly.ie/regional-planning/rses#:~:text=The%20RSES%20provides%20a%20long,%E2%80%93%20Cork%2C%20Limerick%2DShannon%20and>
- [42] "Zero Waste Scotland," [Online]. Available: <https://www.zerowastescotland.org.uk/>
- [43] "Industrial Biotechnology Innovation Centre," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ibioic.com/>
- [44] "Aberdeen & Grampian Chamber of Commerce," [Online]. Available: <https://www.agcc.co.uk/circular-north-east>
- [45] "Land und Leute: Baden-Württemberg.de," [Online]. Available: <https://www.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/unser-land/land-und-leute>
- [46] "Gross domestic product of Baden-Württemberg from 1970 to 2021," [Online]. Available: <https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/5003/umfrage/entwicklung-des-bruttoinlandsprodukts-von-baden-wuerttemberg-seit-1970/>
- [47] "Biomasse: Ministerium für Umwelt, Klima und Energiewirtschaft Baden-Württemberg," [Online]. Available: <https://um.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/energie/erneuerbare-energien/bioenergie/biomasse/>
- [48] "Abfallbilanz 2021. Ressourcen aus unserer kommunalen Kreislaufwirtschaft," [Online]. Available: https://um.baden-wuerttemberg.de/fileadmin/redaktion/m-um/intern/Dateien/Dokumente/2_Presse_und_Service/Publikationen/Umwelt/Abfallbilanz-2021-barrierefrei.pdf
- [49] "The Baden-Württemberg government's sustainable bioeconomy strategy," [Online]. Available: https://biooekonomie.baden-wuerttemberg.de/site/pbs-bw-mlr-root/get/documents_E1788793024/MLR.Biooekonomie/Biooekonomie-Dateiablage/Anlagen/Landesstrategie_Biooekonomie-BW_en_.pdf
- [50] "Example regions of the industrial bioeconomy," [Online]. Available: <https://www.bmwk.de/Navigaion/Karte/SiteGlobals/Forms/Formulare/karte-beispielregionen-formular.html>
- [51] "To the N! networkBaden-Wuerttemberg," [Online]. Available: <https://www.nachhaltigkeitsstrategie.de/strategie/politik/nachhaltigkeitsstrategie>
- [52] "LANDESSTRATEGIE RESSOURCENEFFIZIENZ BADENWÜRTTEMBERG," [Online]. Available: https://um.baden-wuerttemberg.de/fileadmin/redaktion/m-um/intern/Dateien/Dokumente/6_Wirtschaft/Ressourceneffizienz_und_Umweltechnik/160301_Landesstrategie_Ressourceneffizienz.pdf
- [53] "Sustainable building for the future," [Online]. Available: <https://www.holzbauoffensivebw.de/de>
- [54] "Ministry of Economics, Labor and Tourism Baden-Württemberg," [Online]. Available: <https://wm.baden-wuerttemberg.de/de/service/publikation/did/innovationsstrategie-baden-wuerttemberg-2/>
- [55] "Interreg Danube Transnational Programme," [Online]. Available: <https://www.interreg-danube.eu/approved-projects/godanubio>

- [56] "Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz," [Online]. Available: https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Dossier/Industrielle-Biooekonomie/Beispielregionen/222_Region-Stuttgart/00-region.html
- [57] "Die Bioökonomie im System aufstellen: Konzept für eine baden-württembergische Forschungsstrategie Bioökonomie" ("Setting up the bioeconomy in the system"), Ministry of Science, Research and the Arts of Baden-Württemberg, 2013.
- [58] "Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy," [Online]. Available: <https://www.southernassembly.ie/regional-planning/rses>
- [59] "Southern Waste Region," [Online]. Available: <http://southernwasteregion.ie/content/southern-region-waste-management-plan-2015-2021-associated-reports>
- [60] "Learning Region," [Online]. Available: <https://www.southernassembly.ie/regional-planning/learning-region#:~:text='Towards%20a%20Learning%20Region'%20identifies,RSES%20and%20local%20policy%20implementation>
- [61] "National Smart Specialisation Strategy for Innovation 2022-2027," [Online]. Available: <https://enterprise.gov.ie/en/Publications/Publication-files/National-Smart-Specialisation-Strategy-for-Innovation-2022-2027.pdf>
- [62] "Regional Approach for development of a Smart Specialisation Strategy in the Southern Region," [Online]. Available: https://www.southernassembly.ie/uploads/general-files/SRA_S3_Final_Report.pdf
- [63] "Ireland's Bioeconomy," [Online]. Available: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/d9a88a45154849eb9866dd262e5800e7>
- [64] "Support Scheme for Renewable Heat," [Online]. Available: <https://www.seai.ie/business-and-public-sector/business-grants-and-supports/support-scheme-renewable-heat/>
- [65] "Biofuels Obligation Scheme," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/publication/91f03c-biofuels/#:~:text=This%20scheme%20was%20introduced%20in,across%20their%20general%20fuel%20mix>
- [66] "Minister McConalogue and Minister of State Heydon announce €9.6 million in research grants for projects across agri-food and bioeconomy," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/press-release/daf26-minister-mcconalogue-and-minister-of-state-heydon-announce-96-million-in-research-grants-for-projects-across-agri-food-and-bioeconomy/>
- [67] "Inform Bio," [Online]. Available: <https://informbioproject.ie/>
- [68] "NXTGENWOOD," [Online]. Available: <https://biorbic.com/nxtgenwood/>
- [69] "Science Foundation Ireland," [Online]. Available: <https://www.sfi.ie/funding/>
- [70] "Postgraduate Diploma in Bioeconomy with Business," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ittralee.ie/en/InformationAbout/Courses/ParttimeStudy/PostgraduateDiplomainBioeconomywithBusiness/>

- [71] "Project Ireland 2040," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/campaigns/09022006-project-ireland-2040/>
- [72] "Renewable Gas Forum Ireland," [Online]. Available: <https://www.renewablegasforum.com/projects/graze/>
- [73] "LEADER Programme 2014-2020," [Online]. Available: <https://www.pobal.ie/programmes/leader-programme-2014-2020/>
- [74] "LEADER and the Bioeconomy," [Online]. Available: <https://www.nationalruralnetwork.ie/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/LEADER-and-the-Bioeconomy-Booklet-2021-Final.pdf>
- [75] "EIP-AGRI Supporting innovation, competitiveness and sustainability in agriculture and forestry.," [Online]. Available: <https://www.nationalruralnetwork.ie/eip-agri/>
- [76] "BIOMASS TO BIOCHAR FOR FARM BIOECONOMY," [Online]. Available: <https://www.biomassstobiochar.ie/>
- [77] "Biorefinery Glas -Small-scale Farmer-led Green Biorefineries," [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/find-connect/projects/biorefinery-glas-small-scale-farmer-led-green>
- [78] "NATIONAL WASTE PREVENTION PROGRAMME Preventing Waste Driving the Circular Economy," [Online]. Available: https://www.epa.ie/publications/circular-economy/resources/Circular_Economy_8PP_fa_v9_digital.pdf
- [79] "Environmental Protection Agency," [Online]. Available: <https://www.epa.ie/our-services/monitoring--assessment/circular-economy/green-enterprise/>
- [80] "Minister of State Smyth opens Circular Economy Innovation Grant Scheme 2022 for applications," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/press-release/4fe2a-minister-of-state-smyth-opens-circular-economy-innovation-grant-scheme-2022-for-applications/>
- [81] "CIRCULÉIRE THE NATIONAL PLATFORM FOR CIRCULAR MANUFACTURING, " [Online]. Available: <https://circuleire.ie/>
- [82] "AgriChemWhey," [Online]. Available: <https://www.agrichemwhey.com/>
- [83] "Farm4more," [Online]. Available: <https://www.farm4more.ie/>
- [84] "F. Supports," [Online]. Available: <https://www.enterprise-ireland.com/en/Productivity/Build-a-green-sustainable-Business/GreenStart/>
- [85] "European Circular Bioeconomy Fund," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ecbf.vc/>
- [86] "Community Climate Action Programme: Climate Education, Capacity Building and Learning by Doing (Strand 2)," [Online]. Available: <https://www.pobal.ie/programmes/community-climate-action-programme-climate-education-capacity-building-and-learning-by-doing-strand-2/#:~:text=Overview,further%20engage%20in%20climate%20action>

- [87] "National Mitigation Plan," [Online]. Available: <https://www.rte.ie/documents/news/national-mitigation-plan-2017.pdf>
- [88] "National Renewable Energy Action Plan IRELAND," [Online]. Available: <https://www.ifa.ie/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/2013-National-Renewable-Energy-Action-Plan-2010.pdf>
- [89] "Offshore Renewable Energy Development Plan II: Strategic Environmental Assessment - Scoping Report," [Online]. Available: <https://www.seai.ie/publications/OREDPA-II-SEA-Scoping-Report.pdf>
- [90] "National Energy Efficiency Action Plan (NEEAP)," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/ga/foilsuichan/93ee2-national-energy-efficiency-action-plan-neeap/>
- [91] "BioEnergy Action Plan for Ireland," [Online]. Available: <https://www.teagasc.ie/media/website/crops/crops/BioenergyActionPlan.pdf>
- [92] "South-West Regional Enterprise Plan to 2024," [Online]. Available: <https://enterprise.gov.ie/en/publications/south-west-regional-enterprise-plan-to-2024.html>
- [93] "South-East Regional Enterprise Plan to 2024," [Online]. Available: <https://enterprise.gov.ie/en/publications/south-east-regional-enterprise-plan-to-2024.html>
- [94] "First Climate Action Plan 2021 Progress Report highlights impactful delivery across key sectors, but challenges remain," [Online]. Available: <https://www.gov.ie/en/press-release/dd9b4-first-climate-action-plan-2021-progress-report-highlights-impactful-delivery-across-key-sectors-but-challenges-remain/>
- [95] "Regional Spatial & Economic Strategy for the Southern Region," [Online]. Available: <https://www.southernassembly.ie/uploads/general-files/Southern%20Regional%20Assembly%20RSES%202020%20High%20Res.pdf>
- [96] "Andalusian circular bioeconomy strategy," [Online]. Available: <https://www.bioeconomiaandalucia.es/documents/1056091/1056698/Estrategia+Andaluza+Bioeconomia+Circular+%5BEABC%5D+%5B18.09.2018%5D/e0b87df0-73a8-43f2-ba9d-da0ad9b312e9>
- [97] "Andalusian sustainable development strategy," [Online]. Available: <https://www.famp.es/export/sites/famp/.galleries/documentos-consejo-andaluz-gobiernos-locales/DOC-AGENDA-21.pdf>
- [98] "CIT Oliva," [Online]. Available: <http://www.citoliva.es/>
- [99] "Centro Tecnológico De La Acuicultura," [Online]. Available: <http://www.ctaqua.es/>
- [100] "Andalusian Public Foundation CENTA," [Online]. Available: <https://www.iagua.es/fundacion-centa>
- [101] "Donana Biosphere Reserve," [Online]. Available: <https://www.donana.es/>
- [102] "CiDAF," [Online]. Available: <https://www.cidaf.es/>
- [103] "A Research Center at your service," [Online]. Available: <https://cicap.es/>

- [104] "CTGARUM," [Online]. Available: <http://www.ctgarum.com>
- [105] "Fundacionceas," [Online]. Available: <http://www.fundacionceas.es>
- [106] "Fundación MEDINA Discovering the Future," [Online]. Available: <http://www.medinadiscovery.com>
- [107] "CEIA3 Campus of International Agri-Food Excellence," [Online]. Available: <http://www.ceia3.es/>

9. Appendix

9.1 ANNEX A

INTERVIEW GUIDE

Welcome to ROBIN

“The project ROBIN – Deploying circular bioeconomies at regional level with a territorial approach” invites you to participate in this face-to-face interview. It will take approximately 30 minutes of your time. Thank you very much in advance for your support, which is very much appreciated. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to ask at any stage. There are no right or wrong answers, and all the information you will provide should reflect only your own ideas, concerns and perspectives and not the organization you are affiliated with.”

INTERVIEW GUIDE | Total duration: 30'

Part 1 | Opening (Warm-Up questions) | Duration:10'

Introduction of ourselves, the project, and the interview process.

My name is XXXXX, and I am the representative of the *name of the pilot region* in the ROBIN project.

Random questions such as “How are you?” to make the interviewee feel comfortable and break the ice (build rapport with the interviewee).

The interview will consist of some warm-up, core, and closing questions. At the end of the interview, we will ask you for some short background information about yourself.

“You have been invited to represent your regional area regarding the uptake of regional governance models with a focus on bioeconomy”.

- 1) “How long have you been in the position you are in now?”
- 2) “How familiar are you with the concept of bioeconomy?”

Now we will proceed with the main part of the interview which will last approximately 15'.

Part 2 | Main part (Core Questions) | Duration: 15-20'

Category 1: general bioeconomy characteristics of the region (appr. duration: 10')

- “Where does *name of the pilot region* stand on the way to the bioeconomy? “
- **A bioeconomy governance model describes the process that has been developed, through rules and institutions, to coordinate collective action among stakeholders, that accounts for social, economic, and environmental dimensions, with the aim to promote the circular bioeconomy in the region.** “Is there a specific governance model with a bioeconomy focus in place in your region? If yes, could you shortly explain when was established and describe its dimensions briefly?”

- “Which are the stakeholders involved in the development of regional bioeconomy governance models/bioeconomy strategies?”
- “Are there specific bioeconomy practices that are adopted in your region? If yes, could you shortly describe them?”
- “What is your role in the implementation of bioeconomy strategies?”
- “What are the main action areas of these strategies?”

Category 2: discovering barriers and obstacles (appr. Duration: 10’)

- “Can you describe specific challenges in the uptake of your regional bioeconomy strategy that pushes the bioeconomy development backward?”
- “Which are the hardest to engage stakeholder groups? Could you elaborate on why they need further effort for their engagement in a regional bioeconomy strategy?”
- “Based on your experience, in what aspect is it difficult to set up a regional bioeconomy strategy?”

Category 3: understanding drivers and opportunities (appr. Duration: 10’)

- “*Name of the pilot region* has its own bioeconomy strategy. What are the benefits of it/ How is the region benefited from it?”
- “From your perspective, to what extent is a bioeconomy strategy in the region necessary and why?”
- “Why does the development of a sustainable bioeconomy require an effective governance framework?”

Part 3 | Closing (Clean-up) | (appr. Duration: 5’)

- “Moving forward to our last question. What type of experience is needed for the further uptake of regional bioeconomy strategies?”
- “Which is the “successful recipe” to create a successful regional governance model with a focus on bioeconomy?”

Part 4 | Background information | (appr. Duration: 1’)

“Now, we have reached almost the end of the interview. I would like to ask you for some final background information.”

Which category of the following does your current occupation falls under?

- Academic institutions
- Local government
- Business community
- Civil society
- Primary biomass producers

Gender:

- Female
- Male

Other

Nationality: _____

What is your highest educational degree achieved?

- anchored by less than high school
- high school/GED
- some college but no degree
- bachelor's degree or equivalent
- master's degree or equivalent
- doctoral or professional degree (PhD/JD/MD)

I would like to thank you for taking the time to provide valuable insights from your perspective.

Examples of probes and techniques to elicit information

“Could you give me an example?”

“What do you mean by that?”

“How did that make you feel?”

“Can you tell me more about that?”

9.2 ANNEX B

INFORMED CONSENT FORM

Who we are:

On behalf of White Research SRL and [name of organisation(s) performing the interview], we are contacting you in the framework of the ROBIN project, funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Programme for Research and Innovation. A detailed description of how ROBIN handles personal data is presented in the project's Privacy Policy that accompanies this Consent Form (see below).

Project: ROBIN - Deploying circular BIOecoNomies at Regional level with a territorial approach (GA Number 101060504).

Partners involved:

#	Organisation name	Role	Address	Phone	E-mail
1	White Research SRL	Data collection, storage and analysis	Avenue de la Toison d'Or, 67	+32 2 520 00 09	info@white-research.eu

Responsible persons:

#	Role	Name	E-mail
1	ROBIN Project Manager	Ioanna Nydrioti	inydrioti@white-research.eu
2	ROBIN Associate Project Manager	Pinelopi Kaslama	pkaslama@white-research.eu

What do we need from you?

You have been invited to take part in this interview because you have been member of the Multi Actor Regional Constellations (MARC)s of the ROBIN project.

There are approximately 10 questions in this questionnaire related to (i) familiarity with the concept of "circular bioeconomy"; (ii) personal past and current experiences in regional bioeconomy initiatives; (iii) type of personal engagement in bioeconomy initiatives; (iv) limitations and space for further improvement for further stakeholder engagement and support of these initiatives; (v) views on how to design and implement a robust bioeconomy initiative based on circular economy principles; (vi) some background information.

This will ultimately help us better shape the perceived barriers, opportunities, and incentives concerning your involvement in collaborative governance schemes. The interview is expected to last no more than 30 – 35 minutes and will be performed by the ROBIN partners of each region, who will take written notes during the interview.

To effectively conduct this interview, we need to process some of your personal data (background information):

- Some basic demographics (e.g., age, gender).
- Your professional info (organisation, job position, field of expertise).
- Your education level.
- Your personal opinions on the subject matter.

Why do we need your data & what will we do with them?

We need your data to contact you in order to plan and carry out the aforementioned interview and to resolve any ambiguities, questions, and other issues that may arise after and as a result of the interview. We also need to keep your data in the written notes to keep track of the interview process. The project’s deliverables that will be derived from the interview will not include your personal data or any other information that could identify you. Your personal data will remain on our written notes we will make during the interview.

We will mention only that you are a MARC member (anonymously).

We will share your data with the other ROBIN project partners involved in this task and who will participate in the drafting of the relevant deliverables. We are also obliged to grant access to your data to:

- EU officials such as our Project Officer for purposes related to the project’s evaluation;
- EU agencies and other authorities for project auditing purposes.

Your data will be stored internally by the ROBIN partnership throughout the duration of the project (August 2025). In particular, the data will be stored in a secured cloud environment of the project, where only project partners have access to.

We would also be very happy if you give us your consent to contact you in the future to ask you to participate in other project activities and also to inform you about the project’s progress (e.g., by sending you a newsletter or similar messages).

How can you withdraw your consent?

You should know that you can withdraw your consent at any time by communicating either on the phone or by email with the responsible persons listed on the previous page. With regards to the informational messages and newsletters, you can always opt out by simply clicking the link “Unsubscribe” or something similar included at the end of all the relevant messages.

I hereby give my consent to the processing of my personal data needed for:

*(Please, tick the boxes below to confirm that you give us your consent for the respective subject. Any boxes left unticked mean that **you do not consent to the relevant subject.**)*

#	Consent Subject	Tick box
---	-----------------	----------

1	My participation in an interview that will be carried out by ROBIN to learn more about my experience and personal views on bioeconomy initiatives in my region and the involvement of general public and stakeholders in it	
2	My participation in future activities of ROBIN	
3	Receiving newsletters regarding ROBIN activities	

Name of participant

Date

Signature

9.3 ANNEX C

9.3.1 Questionnaire

Questionnaire for interviews with individuals involved in the design and implementation of each regional bioeconomy strategy
Could you please describe 1-2 major challenges that you have faced during the design of strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in your region, and if/how you managed to solve them?
Please describe which you consider to be the strong points and the facilitating factors that support the design of strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in your region?
Which are your suggestions to improve the design process of the strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in your region?
Could you please describe 1-2 major challenges that affect the smooth implementation of the strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in your region, and if/how you managed to solve them?
Please describe which you consider to be the strong points and the facilitating factors that support the implementation of strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in your region?
Which are your suggestions to improve the implementation process of the strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in your region?
Which was the stakeholder involvement during the preparation and the implementation stages of the strategies relevant to the circular bioeconomy in your region?
Which are your plans for the short, medium and long term? (NEW)
Which are key actions or aspects that have not been considered yet in your region and that you would like to address in the future? (NEW)

Any other question that has not be filled in the Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profile template

9.3.2 *Informed consent form*

CONSENT AFTER INFORMATION
Version 1.0, 4 November 2020

I. INFORMATION SHEET

Study title: Analysis of the regional policy mix in the ROBIN regions

Principal Investigator of the project for AUTH: Prof. Efstratios Stylianidis (AUTH)

The study is being conducted in the context of Horizon Europe Project: “ROBIN – Deploying circular BIOecoNomies at Regional level with a territorial approach”

Data Controller: Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH)

Names of the coordinators of the research/scientific coordinator:

Prof. Efstratios Stylianidis (AUTH)

Email: sstyl@auth.gr

TeL: 2310995973

Address: University Campus, 54124, Thessaloniki

Data Protection Officer (DPO): data.ptotection@auth.gr

Important Information

You will be given information on the research to be conducted and you will be invited to take part in the study. Your participation is voluntary.

You can talk about this study and the consent form with other people such as family/friends/or whoever you feel comfortable with. You do not have to decide right away. You can decide whether you want to take part in the study after you have thought/ discussed this.

There may be words you do not understand or some things you would like for me to explain to you in detail. You can stop anytime and ask questions.

Purpose: Why are we conducting this study?

The H2020 EU-funded project “ROBIN – Deploying circular BIOecoNomies at Regional level with a territorial approach” (GA No 101060504) aims at empowering regional authorities to fulfil the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation and accounting for different territorial contexts.

The current study is being performed to map the current circular bioeconomy policy mix in the 5 ROBIN regions which function as the case studies of the project. The objective of this interview/questionnaire survey is to collect insights on the successful circular bioeconomy strategies conducted within your region as well as identify success factors and strong points, but also barriers and challenges.

The information collected during all the survey that will be implemented will be used to perform a mapping among the local policy ecosystems identified and investigated in the course of the study. The results of the analysis will help ROBIN regional partners generate the circular bioeconomy governance profiles of ROBIN regions and help regional authorities in the co-creation of successful regional governance models, through support actions and tools that are aligned with circular bioeconomy principles.

Subject Selection: Why are we requesting your participation?

You have been selected and invited to this survey because you represent a type of stakeholder that can provide further information on the circular bioeconomy policy mix in your region. We consider your participation very important because it will give us an opinion from a stakeholder with a big amount of expertise on the level of readiness, the circular bioeconomy parameters that are in effect in the region and the uptake level that the region can develop in order to further foster its circular bioeconomy policy mix.

Your participation is voluntary: Do I have to do this?

You do not have to take part in the study if you don't want to. Even if you say “yes” now, you can change your mind later and pull out of the study at any time.

Participation cost: What will this cost me?

No cost is involved

Procedure: What will happen if you take part in the study?

If you accept the invitation, you will be asked to take part in a 25-30 minute interview/or to fill in a questionnaire on your experience on the bioeconomy governance models and region policy mix in their particular ROBIN region.

Data: What kind of data will be collected?

- The information will be collected in the form of written minutes by the participant, in a properly formatted form. The information to be collected refers to your experience on the bioeconomy governance models and region policy mix in their particular ROBIN region.
- Apart from your views on the previously mentioned subject we will collect some personal data namely: Your name and e-mail, the organization you belong to, the position that you hold in your organization.
- The personal data will be handled in accordance with the GDPR and will be stored securely for the entire period stipulated for the research project and for possible checks by EU authorities (i.e., 3 years).
- The data collected will be anonymized before being analyzed.
-

Who will receive or to whom maybe distributed the collected personal data?

All the data collected will be received and handled by the ROBIN consortium.

Personal data is intended not to be transferred to a third country or to an international organization provided that in any case appropriate safeguards are taken.

Risks: Is this bad or dangerous for me?

There are no risks involved in this study.

Benefits: Will this be beneficial for me?

With the information that you provide, we will be able to develop tools and methodologies related to the uptake of regional circular bioeconomy models and strategies with which you will have the opportunity to collect material to further support the uptake of bioeconomy in your region. On top of that, should you wish to, you may get the chance to participate in future project activities.

Sharing the results: Will you inform me on the conclusions?

When the research is finished, a report namely “Circular Bioeconomy Governance Profiles of ROBIN Regions” will be published outlining the methodology and the findings of the regions analysis conducted. The results of this study are also likely to be presented in relevant project events or printed material or withing scientific publications to be developed by the members of the consortium.

Right to refuse or withdraw: I can choose not to be part of this study? Can I change my mind?

Your participation is not forced. You can stop the research at any time if you wish.

Consent is provided for 3 years until it is revoked by sending the application form enclosed at the end of this document to the address of the coordinator of the research/scientific. The right to withdraw consent at any time does not affect the lawfulness of the processing based on the consent given before its withdrawal.

Data managing

The processing of your personal data is based on consent to this processing for specific purpose. Your personal data will be codified and saved at computers in accordance with appropriate technical and

organizational measures to ensure secure safeguarding of data such as appropriate software to negate access to non-authorized persons.

You have the right to request from the Head of the Research access to or rectification or erasure of your personal data or restriction of processing concerning your data or to object to processing as well as the right to data portability. For any enquiry or guidance regarding your rights, you could send an email to data.protection@auth.gr or phone at [2310-995973]. Any change in your personal data will take place within 30 days of your communication with Principal Investigator.

If you have any questions about your personal data and your relevant rights or if you believe that your rights are being violated, you can contact the Data Protection Officer of the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (dataprotection@auth.gr). For additional protection you have the right to lodge a complaint with the Hellenic Data Protection Authority (www.dpa.gr).

If you finally decide that you would like to take part in the study, you will receive a copy of this sheet.

II. CONSENT

“ROBIN – Deploying circular BIOecoNomies at Regional level with a territorial approach”

I the undersigned,

I declare that:

- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed by Prof. Efstratios Stylianidis, scientific coordination of the interview/questionnaire survey for the purposes of the research in which I will participate, and which is part of the research project “ROBIN – Deploying circular BIOecoNomies at Regional level with a territorial approach” - Project number: 73904.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about the method and sources of the research financing.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about what my participation in this research entails. In particular, I have been informed of all the rights and obligations I will have as a participant in the research comprising the obligation of confidentiality (if the latter is required).
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about any positive or directly negative, short-term or long-term consequence my participation in this research is expected to have concerning me or in relation with third parties.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about how my personal data related to this research is processed and protected.
- I have been adequately and comprehensively informed about how my personal data related to this research is processed and protected.
- I am aware of the fact that my participation is voluntary and that I can withdraw my participation from the research at any time for any reason and without any impact on me (as well as of the fact that the same applies to the person I represent).
- I know the Head of the research to whom I can address to withdraw my participation from this research or to notify any potential problem that might arise during my participation or after the completion of this research.
- No pressure was exerted to me, and I was given enough time to think and decide.

I consent to participate in the above research.

Participant’s Signature: _____

Date:_____

day/month/year

III. WITHDRAWAL OF CONSENT OF THE PARTICIPANT

“ROBIN – Deploying circular BIOecoNomies at Regional level with a territorial approach”

I the undersigned,

hereby withdraw my consent concerning my participation in the research study ROBIN, which I had given on ____/____/____

Signature of the participant

Date: ____/____/____

day/month/year

Full name

DEPLOYING CIRCULAR BIOECONOMIES AT
REGIONAL LEVEL WITH A TERRITORIAL APPROACH

About the project

Europe's regional authorities have a crucial role to play as agents of inclusive and resilient economic development for their territories. ROBIN sets out to empower them to fulfil this role with support to co-shape their governance structures in to accelerate the deployment of their circular bioeconomy targets, while also promoting social innovation. We demonstrate the potential of innovative circular bioeconomy governance structures and models in 5 regions within Ireland, Germany, Spain, Slovakia and Greece. We set-up Multi-Actor Regional Constellations engaging key stakeholders to co-create novel governance structures, well-embedded within existing structures of our regions and mandated to execute circular bioeconomy strategies and to coordinate effectively with the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative – Coordination and Support Office (CCRI-CSO). We also provide them with tailored support for enhanced stakeholder engagement, as well as a practical toolbox to improve the operation and monitoring of their models. In the process we coordinate our actions with the CCRI-CSO.

Partners	URL
Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	www.qplan-intl.gr
FUNDACION CORPORACION TECHNOLOGICA SE ANDALUCIA	www.corporaciontecnologica.com
WHITE RESEARCH SRL	www.white-research.eu
PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	www.pedal-consulting.eu
STEINBEIS 2I GMBH	www.steinbeis-europa.de
ROZVOJOVA AGENTURA ZILINSKEHO SAMOSPRAVNEHO KRAJA NO	www.razsk.sk
MUNSTER TECHNOLOGICAL UNIVERSITY	www.circbio.ie
ARISTOTELEIO PANEPISTIMIO THESSALONIKIS	www.auth.gr
REGION OF CENTRAL MACEDONIA	www.pkm.gov.gr
CONSEJERÍA DE AGRICULTURA, PESCA, AGUA Y DESARROLLO RURAL	www.juntadeandalucia.es
INSTITUTO ANDALUZ DE INVESTIGACION Y FORMACION AGRARIA PESQUERA ALIMENTARIA Y DE LA PRODUCCION ECOLOGICA	www.juntadeandalucia.es
BIOPRO BADEN-WUERTTEMBERG GMBH	www.bio-pro.de
SOUTHERN REGIONAL ASSEMBLY	www.southernassembly.ie

CONTACT US: info@robin-project.eu

VISIT: www.robin-project.eu

Robin project

@Robinproject

Robin Project

Robin Horizon Europe Project